

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D3.1

Process Evaluation and Recommendations for Practitioners

Info Sheet

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Table of Contents

List of Tables	6
Glossary	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction.....	10
2. The Iterative Design Process of the CCLAB Model.....	12
2.1 The CCLAB Model.....	12
2.2 Evaluation Approach and Objectives	13
3. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 1	16
3.1 Descriptions of the Labs and KPIs	16
3.2 Evaluation Approach, Methods, and Instruments.....	20
3.3 Outcomes of Cross-Cutting Analysis of the PAR Cycle 1.....	27
4. First Redesign Iteration: Areas of Improvement for PAR Cycle 2	53
4.1 Building a Shared Understanding of Learning and Expected Learning Outcomes	55
4.2 Supporting a Stronger Understanding of Youth’s Perceptions of Eco-social Phenomena, Democracy, and Agency.....	70
4.3 Redesigning of the Evaluation Instruments.....	71
4.4 Improving, Systematising and Documenting the Model’s Methodological Strategies.....	73
4.5 Developing and Validating a Shared Protocol for Stakeholder Needs Assessment.....	75
5. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 2	77
5.1 Description of the Labs and KPIs.....	77
5.2 Evaluation Approach, Methods, and Instruments.....	83
5.3 Outcomes of the Cross-Cutting Analysis of PAR Cycle 2	85
5.4 Evaluating the Pedagogical Effectiveness of the CCLAB	100
5.5 Reflecting on Methodological Choices.....	108
5.6 Evaluation of the Competences Framework.....	130
6. Second Redesign Iteration: Areas of Improvements for PAR Cycle 3	132
6.1 Revising the Competence Model.....	132
6.2 Integrating of Youth’s Voices, Experiences, and Ways of Doing into the Model.....	137
6.3 Strengthening the Methodological Structure of the CCLAB Model.....	138
7. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 3.....	140
7.1 Description of the Labs and KPIs.....	140

7.2 Evaluation Approach, Methods, and Instruments	149
7.3 Outcomes of Cross-Cutting Analysis of the PAR Cycle 3.....	150
7.4 Overall Considerations on the Outcomes of PAR Cycle 3.....	201
8. Final Reflections on the Iterative Design Process	209
9. Recommendations for Practitioners	212
9.1 General Recommendations	212
9.2 Recommendations for the Implementations of the CCLAB Model.....	216
10. References	223
Annexes.....	228
Annex 1. Evaluation Report for PAR Cycle 2.....	228

List of Tables

Table 1. <i>Overview of How Evaluation has Been Framed Through the Different Cycles</i>	14
Table 2. <i>Participants in PAR Cycle 1</i>	16
Table 3. <i>Summary of the Evaluation Instruments</i>	21
Table 4. <i>Structure of the Template for the Researchers’ Diaries</i>	22
Table 5. <i>Script for the Interviews With Educators</i>	25
Table 6. <i>Script for the Focus Groups With Youth</i>	26
Table 7. <i>Youth’s Concerns and Interests</i>	36
Table 8. <i>Methods of PAR Cycle 1 Iteration</i>	45
Table 9. <i>Summary of Key Areas of Improvement and Derived Actions</i>	53
Table 10. <i>Identified key competences</i>	57
Table 11. <i>Evaluation Rubric Based on the Identified Competences</i>	63
Table 12. <i>Template to Systematise Methods Collection and Evaluation.</i>	74
Table 13. <i>Overview of PAR Cycle 2 labs</i>	77
Table 14. <i>Revised version of the Competence Model</i>	133
Table 15. <i>Overview of PAR Cycle 3 Labs</i>	140
Table 16. <i>Participants in PAR Cycle 3</i>	143
Table 17. <i>Summary of the Diversity of Goals on the Envision Phase</i>	179
Table 18. <i>Summary of Key Outcomes</i>	204

Glossary

AE	Ars Electronica
CCLAB	Critical ChangeLab
Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets Arts: Critical ChangeLabs for Building Democratic Culture Through Creative and Narrative Practices
DYFC	Design Your Future City
DYFF	Design Your Future Fingal
EUROALTER	European Alternatives
ISRZ	Institute for Social Research in Zagreb
KI	Kersnikova Institute
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OULU	University of Oulu
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PAR Cycle	Participatory Action Research Cycle
TT	Tactical Tech
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
UB	University of Barcelona
UDDP	School Dormitory Dora Pejačević
UDMJ	School Dormitory Marija Jambrišak
UDNZ	School Dormitory Novi Zagreb
WAAG	Waag Futurelab

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D3.1), *Process Evaluation and Recommendations for Practitioners*, outlines the key efforts and outcomes of Work Package 3 (WP3), specifically Task 3.1, which focused on the process evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab (CCLAB) Model and its implementation across diverse settings. The evaluation centred on analysing the Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycles conducted with both youth and educators, aiming to assess how the model was applied in practice.

The primary objective of this task is to generate insights that will inform the iterative refinement of the CCLAB Model and support the development of evidence-based recommendations for future implementations.

This deliverable builds upon the foundational work carried out in WP1 (Map & Design) and the empirical studies conducted under Task 1.4 (WP1), as well as Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 (WP2 Implement), which oversaw the implementation of CCLABs across 21 locations.

The report is structured around three main components: (1) evaluation of each PAR cycle, (2) redesign iterations of the model, and (3) recommendations for practitioners.

- **PAR Cycle 1 (2024)** adopted an exploratory approach, examining how participation, power distribution, learning, and youth citizenship were enacted. Findings highlighted the importance of self-organisation, multimodal expression, and creative methods, while also identifying challenges such as time constraints, institutional hierarchies, and limited reflective engagement.
- **First redesign iteration** addressed these challenges by clarifying expected learning outcomes, strengthening competence-based assessment, revising evaluation instruments, and systematising methodological strategies.
- **PAR Cycle 2 (2024–2025)** aimed to enhance the integration of youth perspectives within the model's design. It examined how young people perceive and make sense of eco-social issues, democratic processes, and their potential as agents of transformation. The evaluation showed significant shifts in youths' perspectives but also tensions between abstract notions of democracy and meaningful experiential practices. Artistic and participatory methods proved highly effective in engaging

students, although institutional constraints and limited time continued to pose barriers.

- **Second redesign iteration** refined the competence model, integrated youth voices more directly, and reinforced the methodological structure of the CCLAB model.
- **PAR Cycle 3 (2025)** focused on testing and consolidating the model across the different phases that conform the model. The analysis revealed both opportunities (e.g., collaborative knowledge-building, creative envisioning, embodied and affective engagement) and transversal challenges (e.g., risks of symbolic participation, mismatches with traditional schooling, intersectional dynamics).

The **final reflections** emphasise the value of treating design and evaluation as inseparable, iterative processes that adapt to diverse contexts. The cumulative findings demonstrate that the CCLAB model supports youth in developing democratic competences when grounded in lived experiences, creative practices, and meaningful participation.

The report concludes with **recommendations for practitioners**, stressing the need to:

1. Transform learning environments into everyday democratic spaces.
2. Recognise democracy as a lived practice that validates and enables youth voices and agency.
3. Embrace epistemological pluralism and creative methods.
4. Remain attentive to risks of symbolic participation and structural barriers.

By synthesizing evidence from over 51 **labs** in 10 **countries**, this deliverable provides both theoretical insights and practical tools for educators, policymakers, and civil society actors committed to fostering democratic, critical, and transformative education in Europe.

1. Introduction

The main objective of the Critical ChangeLab project is to strengthen democracy in Europe through the creation and implementation of a flexible model of democratic pedagogy, the CCLAB model. The design of this model is grounded in an iterative and participatory process that brings together young people, educators, and civil society organizations.

This document focuses on reporting the iterative design, evaluation, and refinement of the CCLAB model. Building on three cycles of Participatory Action Research (PAR) conducted across diverse educational contexts in Europe, the report synthesizes empirical findings on youth participation, learning processes, democratic agency and employed methodological approaches. Through this iterative evaluation, the deliverable identifies challenges, opportunities, and methodological insights that inform the progressive redesign of the CCLAB model. The aim is to provide a robust framework and practical recommendations for educators and institutions seeking to foster democratic, critical, and transformative practices in education. Furthermore, it aims to provide evidence that supports the production of actionable recommendations for educators as well as guide the content design of the Educators' Handbook (Deliverable 2.3) and to the final design of the model (Deliverable 3.2)

This deliverable is not intended to provide a narrative description of each Critical ChangeLab since this information has already been detailed in Deliverable 2.1 and 2.2. In this sense, D2.1, D2.2 and D3.1 will serve as complimentary deliverables, one providing a narrative picture of the labs and their efforts, the other delving into analysis and key insights on implementing the labs overall.

- **Chapter 1. Introduction** introduces the document and its scope.
- **Chapter 2. The iterative design process of the CCLAB model** explains the participatory and research-based approach guiding the model's development.
- **Chapter 3. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 1** presents the evaluation of the first implementation of the model.
- **Chapter 4. First redesign iteration** summarizes improvements made after Cycle 1, focusing on competences, evaluation tools, and methodological strategies.

- **Chapter 5. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 2** presents the evaluation of the second implementation of the model, alongside a review of pedagogical effectiveness.
- **Chapter 6. Second redesign iteration** summarizes improvements made after Cycle 2, focusing on integrating youth voices, competence revision, and methodological strengthening.
- **Chapter 7. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 3** presents the evaluation of the third implementation of the model.
- **Chapter 8. Final reflections on the iterative design process** reflects on the overall evolution and learning from the three PAR cycles.
- **Chapter 9. Recommendations for practitioners** provides practical guidance for educators to adopt and adapt the CCLAB model in diverse educational contexts.

2. The Iterative Design Process of the CCLAB Model

The design of the CCLAB model is grounded in an iterative and participatory process that brings together young people, educators, and civil society organizations. The aim is to develop a general framework for the model, define a set of tools and methods for its practical application, and formalize strategies to integrate and sustain the model across diverse learning contexts.

To this end, the design process draws on traditions from both Participatory Design (Druin, 2002; Muller & Druin, 2012) and Design-Based Research (Barab & Squire, 2004; Wang & Hannafin, 2005). On the one hand, the Participatory Design tradition emphasises the importance of recognising and incorporating the interests, understandings, and socio-cultural values of individuals and institutions into the design process (Muller & Druin, 2012). On the other hand, the Design-Based Research tradition provides a structure that frames the workflow as an iterative cycle of design and evaluation. By treating design and evaluation as inseparable, mutually reinforcing processes, this approach enables continuous assessment of how well the emerging model aligns with its intended purpose.

Building on this perspective, the model has been developed and refined through the implementation of three PAR cycles with young people and educators. The purpose of the evaluation is to generate empirical insights that inform the iterative design process and contribute to strengthening the model. In the following sections, we briefly introduce the initial model as defined in Deliverable 1.4 and outline the approach taken for evaluation.

2.1 The CCLAB Model

The CCLAB model (described in detail in Deliverable 1.4) is grounded in a vision of democratic education aligned with the democratic culture advocated by Dewey (1966) and the Council of Europe's *Reference Framework on Competences for Democratic Culture* (2018). This perspective views democracy as more than a system of governance; it sees democracy as a collective way of life underpinned by values, attitudes, and skills necessary for citizens to flourish in culturally diverse, democratic societies (Council of Europe, 2018). To

achieve these aims, the CCLAB model integrates principles of the *Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework* (described in Deliverable 1.4) with the *ChangeLab Intervention Method* (Engeström et al., 2013), alongside the use of creative and arts-based methods.

On the one hand, the *Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework* is designed to guide the planning and facilitation of CCLABs, ensuring participants develop comprehensive critical literacies. Building on Paulo Freire's notion of *conscientização* (2005) it emphasises fostering critical consciousness so that individuals can identify and challenge power dynamics and systems of oppression. Furthermore, relational perspectives from ethics, pedagogy, sustainability, social sciences, design, human-computer interaction, posthumanism, and futures literacy (De La Bellacasa, 2012; Metz & Miller, 2016; Biesta et al., 2004; Hickey & Riddle, 2022; West et al., 2020; Powell & Dépelteau, 2013; Selg, 2016; Nielsen & Bjerck, 2022; Sheridan et al., 2020; Zapata et al. 2018) enrich its scope and dimensions.

On the other hand, the ChangeLab intervention method (Engeström et al., 2013) provides a methodological structure for the implementation, organised according to an expansive learning cycle. This intervention method is grounded in cultural-historical activity theory (Vygotsky, 1978; Leont'ev, 1978) and is designed to facilitate collaborative problem-solving by helping participants identify, analyse, and resolve systemic contradictions (Kajamaa & Hyrkkö, 2022). Within the CCLAB, this model adopts Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology to engage young people in identifying, questioning, and analysing issues that generate tensions in their everyday lives through six phases (P), namely (0) OnBoard, (1) Question, (2) Analyse, (3) Envision and Examine, (4) Act, and (5) Reflect. This initial structure of the model served as a starting point to guide the first cycle of iteration and its subsequent improvements.

2.2 Evaluation Approach and Objectives

The evaluation process followed an iterative approach structured around the three PAR cycles implemented throughout the process. A total of 51 CCLABs were implemented through the overall process across 10 countries, including formal and non-formal education spaces. The evaluation served four main purposes:

- To assess the development and outcomes of each specific cycle.
- To inform and refine the design of subsequent cycles.

- To produce recommendations for educators and practitioners and guide the content design of the Educators' Handbook (Deliverable 2.3).
- To inform the iterative redesign of the model (Deliverable 3.2).

The evaluation is therefore conceived not only as a mechanism of accountability, but as a formative and generative process aimed at enhancing the overall pedagogical model. In Table 1, we will briefly offer an overview of how evaluation has been framed through the different cycles, highlighting the focus and main objective of the evaluation of each cycle. Subsequently, in the sections that follow, we provide a detailed account of the evaluation process conducted during each PAR cycle. This includes an overview of the methodological approaches adopted, a synthesis of the main outcomes, and an analysis of how evaluation contributed to the iterative development of the model. Based on this cumulative knowledge, the report concludes with a general overview of the changes that were implemented through the three cycles and with a set of concrete recommendations aimed at supporting educators and institutions interested in fostering democratic, critical, and transformative practices.

Table 1. Overview of How Evaluation has Been Framed Through the Different Cycles

PAR Cycle	Goal of This Stage of the Evaluation
PAR Cycle 1 From January until May 2024	The initial stage of evaluation, conducted during and after the first PAR cycle, adopted an exploratory perspective. The primary aim at this stage was to initiate observation and generate a foundational understanding of how the model was being enacted in diverse contexts. Specifically, this first evaluative approach aimed to explore: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How participation, power distribution, and mutual learning were conceptualised and enacted within the CCLABs, as well as the enabling and hindering factors influencing these dynamics. • How learning was understood and facilitated within the context of the PAR methodology, and what pedagogical conditions supported or constrained these processes. • What the cycles revealed about young people's roles and identities as active citizens. • How the sustainability and adaptability of the PAR model could be addressed across formal and non-formal educational settings.

PAR Cycle	Goal of This Stage of the Evaluation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What kinds of tensions, challenges, strengths, and opportunities emerged in the implementation of the PAR model.
<p>PAR Cycle 2 From August 2024 until March 2025</p>	<p>The second stage of evaluation built upon insights from PAR Cycle 1 and adopted a more focused and analytical approach. The main objectives at this stage included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigating how young people conceptualise and engage with eco-social phenomena, democratic values, and their own transformative agency. Assessing the pedagogical effectiveness of the CCLAB model in fostering critical competences. Analysing the strengths and limitations of the participatory and artistic methodologies employed across the sites. Evaluating the relevance and applicability of the competence model that had been defined after PAR cycle 1.
<p>PAR Cycle 3 From February until June 2025</p>	<p>The final stage of evaluation aimed at building on the outcomes and insights generated in the previous stages, with the specific goal of producing actionable recommendations for practitioners and informing the final redesign of the pedagogical model. To this end, evaluation focused on the following dimensions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examining how the different phases of the model were implemented across partner institutions and identifying variations in practice. Identifying critical moments within each phase that require particular attention for successful implementation. Reviewing and assessing the methodological approaches used throughout the different stages of the CCLABs Mapping which competences were activated and developed at different stages of the process. Uncovering tensions, contradictions, or emergent challenges that shaped learning and participation dynamics within each stage. <p>This phase was explicitly oriented towards generating knowledge that could feed into the final version of the model (Deliverable 3.2) and support the development of the Handbook for Practitioners (Deliverable 2.3), offering guidance for educators interested in adopting or adapting the model in their own educational settings.</p>

3. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 1

3.1 Descriptions of the Labs and KPIs

A total of **12** Critical ChangeLabs were implemented during PAR Cycle 1 across nine countries: Finland (University of Oulu, OULU), Spain (University of Barcelona, UB), Ireland (Trinity College Dublin, TCD), the Netherlands (Waag Futurelab, WAAG), Austria (Ars Electronica, AE), Slovenia (Kersnikova Institute, KI), France (European Alternatives, EA), Greece (LATRA), and Croatia (Institute for Social Research in Zagreb, ISRZ). Additionally, **11** external labs were coordinated by Tactical Tech (TT) and carried out in Portugal, North Macedonia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, England, Italy, Hungary, Scotland, the Czech Republic, and Germany. These external labs are not included in this report because they were facilitated by external partners and did not have an on-site researcher to make observations. Consequently, the absence of detailed evaluation data prevented their inclusion in the crosscutting analysis.

The following section provides general descriptions of the internal labs conducted, along with numerical data on participants (see Table 2).

Table 2. Participants in PAR Cycle 1

	Finland	Spain	Ireland	The Netherlands	Austria	Slovenia	France	Greece	Croatia	Total
Young People	22	7	10	13	27	9	5	20	13	126
Educators	9	2	4	3	-	1	-	3	3	25
CCLAB Team Members	6	4	3	3	2	1	1	2	1	23
Others^A	2	-	3	1	1	5	1	-	1	14

Note: ^AOthers include institutional and NGO representatives, as well as other pedagogical agents.

Lab #1 (Finland, OULU-Norssi) was organised in a formal education context (a high school in the Oulu area), as part of an elective course on sociology. Four participants aged 15–17 years agreed to take part in the lab, which was also organised in collaboration with FabLab Oulu. Lab #1 participants explored aspects they felt uncomfortable and concerned about in their everyday life such as societal polarization and marginalisation. During the five sessions of the lab, participants looked at the past of a given issue to envision their preferred futures. Based on these visions, participants generated messages aimed to trigger reflection on the societal issue. These messages were printed on everyday objects at the FabLab.

Lab #2 (Finland, OULU – Tyttöjen Talo) was organised in collaboration with “Girls’ House” (Tyttöjen Talo), an informal organisation that provides a safe space for girls to indulge in hobbies and other leisure activities after school. Overall, the group consisted of three 15–16-year-olds girls, who attended two sessions focused on the theme “Self-Love in the age of False Idols and Social Pressures”. The sessions were organised at the Girls’ House and at the city FabLab. The FabLab session was open to all Girls’ House members and focused on the challenges that girls face in terms of one’s looks and appearance and what they can do to make things better in the future. Based on these reflections, participants were encouraged to design activist jewellery in which they engraved messages to show appreciation towards important relations in their lives and foster self-love.

Lab #3 (Finland, OULU – Haltia) was organised in collaboration with a public school (formal education) and a nature school (non-formal education) in the Helsinki metropolitan area. The group consisted of 15 participants (five girls and 10 boys) aged 14 to 15. The group studies in a weighted curriculum program, which means that they have two extra lessons of nature and science education weekly. During the labs the students worked in group on their chosen topics, which were connected to the overall theme of the lab: democracy and human-nature relationship. One of the lab sessions was organised at the nature school and facilitated by its nature education experts; the other sessions were held at the school during school days and were facilitated by the CCLAB researchers.

Lab #4 (Ireland, TCD) was organised with inSync Youth & Family Services, an organisation providing support and services for young people and families in the Kildare/West Wicklow area. TCD lab researchers worked with their Junior Board (approximately ten participants, aged 17–24, and three educators) on the theme of “Community and Identity”. The theme was chosen in collaboration with the educators and youth. The youth considered questions

of identity, community, inclusion and belonging, and created zines that expressed their thoughts while the researchers provided the methods and materials.

Lab #5 (Spain, UB) took place in a public secondary school on the outskirts of Barcelona. The group consisted of seven participants (five girls and two boys) aged 14. This group is participating in a Service-Learning (SL) programme. This SL programme is a part of their academic training and consists of forming and establishing themselves as a mediation team within the school. The lab adopted a collaborative approach in which the participants decided the topic –the adultcentrism– and the goals, while researchers brought resources, and methodological and theoretical structure to materialise their ideas.

Lab #6 (The Netherlands, WAAG) was organised with Weekendschool on tour, an organisation which educates children who are refugees and are living in temporary housing in the middle of the Netherlands. Participants worked on the theme “Identity” through the design of a costume that represented the whole group. Participants used democratic principles to work together and make decisions.

Lab #7 (Austria, AE – Linz) was organised with a public secondary school in Linz with students aged 12. During the sessions at the school, facilitated by the researchers, the students were encouraged to analyse societal structures about a variety of human and non-human agents. This was achieved through a series of narrative and artistic practices focusing on past and present imaginations of the future and which ultimately led to the articulation of the students' own demands and desires for future change. To achieve this, the laboratory's facilitator provided the methodological framework and resources, but themes were determined by the participants.

Lab #8 (Austria, AE – Vienna) was organised with 17- to 18-year-old students from Vienna who had previously participated in the Create Your World Prize, the youth category of the Prix Ars Electronica. It took place in a cultural space providing resources to community groups engaged in participatory, educational, and cultural initiatives. The outcomes of the lab served as the foundation and guidance for a series of podcasts made by the youth and as a starting point for the discussion at the Critical Change Conference organised by the participants and other youths during the Ars Electronica Festival 2024.

Lab #9 (KI – Slovenia) took place at three Kersnikova Labs for Artificial Life. Kersnikova Labs combines intense artistic production at the intersection of art, science and technology, with

an extensive educational programme. Lab #9 participants were aged between 9 and 13. The five workshops planned for the CCLAB PAR Cycle 1 focused on democratic learning, democratic pedagogy and imagining the perfect learning model through the eyes of children and youngsters. Kersnikova labs also connected democratic learning to nature—the world of mycelium—drawing examples of biomimicry based on the concept of cooperation and connectivity in nature. It also linked democratic learning to technology, using Arduino as an example of an open-source tool intended for the free sharing of knowledge and demonstrating how technology can be used creatively for positive purposes in society and nature.

Lab #10 (France, EA) engaged participants on questions of participatory democracy in alternative forms. The topic framing was defined beforehand to provide a clear subject to start the lab and was progressively led by the participants throughout discussion-based activities. Participants were university students from various areas of France who had moved to Paris or were living in a Parisian suburb to complete a period of civil service or internship at Maison de l'Europe in line with their studies, all within the sphere of European politics and culture. In this CCLAB youth reflected on their lived experiences of democracy in action engaging in discussion and joint ideation of alternative spheres and spaces of democracy.

Lab #11 (Greece, LATRA) participants were university students aged between 19–25 years and consisted of 8 female students and 7 male students from the University of the Aegean. Some of them were familiar with each other through university or social life, and most of the students resided in the nearby city of Mytilene. The lab focused on the recent national law paving the way for the privatisation of universities, and the discussion was geared towards the ways in which this process affected the democratisation of education. The students also focused on the long-term effects of this process for the local communities and society at large, as Lesvos holds a large university with the local economy dependent on the influx of students. The lab's outputs were discussed and explored with local civil society organisations such as THEORI, ILIAKTIDA and Creative Hub.

Lab #12 (Croatia, ISRZ) took place in a secondary art school in a rural area of Croatia. Most of the students participating in the lab (11 out of 13) had taken the civic education subject "School & Community". This CCLAB aimed to dig deeper into possible causes and barriers to youth's cultural participation. Through various participatory, as well as creative and arts-

based methods such as Photovoice, Discussion forum and Speculative design, participants questioned the concept of cultural rights, explored issues they face related to participation in cultural activities and envisioned a preferable future for their local community where barriers to cultural participation will no longer be present.

3.2 Evaluation Approach, Methods, and Instruments

The first evaluation cycle had an exploratory focus. Its main objectives were to observe:

- How participation, power distribution, and mutual learning were conceptualised and enacted within the PAR cycles, as well as the enabling and hindering factors influencing these dynamics.
- How learning was understood and facilitated within the context of the PAR methodology, and what pedagogical conditions supported or constrained these processes.
- What the cycles revealed about young people's roles and identities as active citizens.
- How the sustainability and adaptability of the PAR model could be addressed across different educational environments.
- What kinds of tensions, challenges, strengths, and opportunities emerged in the implementation of the PAR model.

To this end, the evaluation plan was made up of three main instruments that combined both qualitative methods and generative techniques: the researcher's diaries, which compile evidence of what happened during the PAR cycle sessions, the "quick and dirty" assessment instruments, the focus group with the participants and the interviews with the educators. Table 3 shows the distribution of the evidence-gathering tools and the corresponding analysis processes.

Table 3. Summary of the Evaluation Instruments

Evidence-Gathering tools		Analysis Process
PAR Cycle		Researchers' diaries + "quick and dirty" assessment instruments ↓ Thematisation by categories
<i>CCLAB Model Phase</i>	<i>Session^A</i>	
Onboard	Session 1	
Question and Analyse	Session 2	
	Session 3	
Envision and act	Session 4	
	Session 5	
Reflect	Session 6	
Focus Group		Audio recording and visual trajectory ↓ Thematisation by categories
Interview		Audio recording ↓ Thematisation by categories

Note: ^AThe session distribution varies by each implementation according to the specific needs of the institution and the local team. Nonetheless, the phase structure remained the same in all PAR cycles.

3.2.1 Researchers' Diaries

To compile evidence of what happened during each CCLAB, a common template was developed and shared among partners. Each local research team oversaw filling the template after each session to systematise the notes they collected through participant observation during the session. The structure of the template is reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Structure of the Template for the Researchers' Diaries

Descriptive Sheet	<p>Inventory of facilitation methods used.</p> <p>Ethnographic description of what took place during the session.</p> <p>List of keywords: The most recurring concepts and ideas during the session.</p>
Section on Participation, Power Distribution, and Mutual Learning	<p>A. Participation, roles, and responsibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describes the level and manner of involvement of participants during the session. • Identifies the roles assumed by each participant (or group of participants), the distribution of responsibilities, and how participants expressed their ideas and actively engaged. • Notes any barriers that may have hindered participation. <p>B. Power distribution: Explores decision-making processes and how participants' objectives, statements, and requests were considered.</p> <p>C. Mutual learning: Provides evidence or signs of learning during the session by participants.</p>
Section Specific to the Implementation Phase	<p>Depending on the phase, the following evidence is documented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboard Phase: Describes how the problem to be addressed in the PAR cycle was defined and participants' opinions about the cycle's approach and their role as a participant group. • Question and Analyse Phase: (1) Outlines participants' expectations for this phase of the cycle, the relevance of the chosen problem to them, their perspectives on the issue, and its relation to democratic values; (2) Notes their views on their role as agents of change and how the methods employed facilitated participation, power redistribution, learning, and debate. • Envision and Act Phase: Explains how the session encouraged participants to explore the issue from different perspectives and highlights significant collective insights reached. • Reflect Phase: Summarizes participants' contributions regarding whether their expectations were met, the CCLAB's continuity, and the process's impact on their lives.
Reflective Section	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodological considerations: Evaluates how the methods used promoted participation, power redistribution, mutual learning, and debate. • Researchers' reflexivity: Documents what the researchers learned during the session and includes notes for improving future sessions.

3.2.2 “Quick and Dirty” Assessment Tools

“Quick and dirty” assessment tools were designed to capture young people’s ongoing perceptions as part of the evaluation process. These included two short exercises for participants to complete at the end of each lab session: a participation scale, and an evaluation activity in which participants identified methodological elements to keep, discard, or rethink. Both tools are described below. The results from these participatory evaluation exercises were documented in the researchers’ diaries.

Participation Scale: Participants individually select one of five options on a youth participation scale in decision-making, based on Charles and Haines’ (2014) proposal (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Participation Scale Sheet Distributed Among Participants

Source: Own elaboration based on Charles & Haines (2014).

Participatory evaluation of the session: Participants individually write notes about aspects of the session they value positively and want to keep, those they would discard, and those they believe need rethinking. Notes are placed into three envelopes or boxes, respectively labelled (see Figures 2 and 3): (1) *Washing machine* (elements to keep); (2) *Trash bin* (elements to discard); (3) *Refrigerator* (elements to rethink).

Figure 2. *The Participatory Sessions' Evaluation Instrument Model*

Figure 3. *The Participatory Sessions' Evaluation Instrument in a Classroom During the Implementation of the PAR Cycle 1*

3.2.3 Interviews and Focus Groups

After the end of a CCLAB, each partner oversaw carrying out an interview with the collaborating educator(s) and a focus group with the participants. A semi-structured script was developed to facilitate these tasks. Both scripts were structured in thematic areas: (1) general views and opinions on the model; (2) participation, power relations and role distribution; (3) lessons learned; (4) considerations on facilitation methods; (5) impact on the implementation context; (6) sustainability of the lab; (7) final considerations. Outcomes

from the interviews and focus group were reported by each local team in a predefined template to facilitate the analysis. Tables 5 and 6 provide the detailed script for interviews with educators and the Focus Group.

Table 5. Script for the Interviews with Educators

General Opinion	Overall, how do you consider your experience and the participants during the whole process? Did the overall process meet your expectations? How? Is there anything that happened during the process that surprised you?
Participation	Did you observe any changes in participants' relations/power distribution and participation during the process? Which ones? Did you observe any changes in the roles assumed by participants and stakeholders over time? Did you feel that the distribution of responsibilities changed over time?
Learning	Did you observe any changes in participants' understandings regarding the topic? Which ones? Did you observe any change in the selected competences? remind the stakeholders about the competences that they consider as more relevant during the stakeholders' needs assessment interview). Did you observe any changes in participants' own agency and their power to have an influence regarding the topic under analysis? Which ones?
Methodological Considerations	Among the activities that were carried out in the lab, which do you think have been useful? Which do you think have not been appropriate/effective? Why?
Impact in Your Context	Do you think this experience was of any use to the people who participated? In what ways? Do you think the lab produced any changes in your context? Do you think the lab was well integrated into your pedagogical space? Or was it disruptive in some way?
Sustainability of the lab	Do you think that the project that we worked on in the CCLAB can have continuity in the centre/school? As a school/centre, would you consider repeating an experience of this type?
Final and Closing	What did the experience allow you to think about? Since we will repeat this process with other groups of young people, do you have any suggestions that we should consider in the future?

Table 6. Script for the Focus Groups With Youth

<p>General Opinion</p>	<p>Overall, how would you consider your experience during the whole process? Did the overall process meet your expectations? How? In the cycle, we focused on [topic]. Was the topic relevant to you? How? Were there any changes in your understanding of the [topic] during the workshop? What were they?</p>
<p>Session-by-Session Recap</p>	<p>In this part, we will share students' opinions and our observations for each session (collected through researchers' diaries + "quick and dirty" assessment instruments) to have feedback on them and discuss them with students. Before the focus group, the researchers should prepare a short summary of their observations (researchers' diaries) and the feedback obtained from the quick and dirty assessment tools, focusing on the most relevant aspects related to participation, conflicts and tensions, and employed methods and tools.</p> <p>Possible questions about participation (depending on the outcomes of observations + quick and dirty assessment tool):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You said/we observed that you feel comfortable/uncomfortable in participating during this session. Can you explain more about it? • You said/we observed that you were able/unable to express your ideas during this session. Can you explain more about it? Is there any idea that you couldn't express, and you want to do it now? • Did you feel your ideas were represented in the workshop outcomes? <p>Possible questions about conflicts and tensions (depending on the outcomes of observations):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You said/we observed that there was some resistance to participating during this session. Can you explain more about it? What stopped you from participating? • You said/we observed that you feel uncomfortable, stressed or angry at some point during the workshop. Can you explain more about it? <p>Possible questions about methods and tools (depending on the outcomes of quick and dirty assessment tools):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You said that you didn't like this activity. Can you explain more about it? Why do you think it didn't work? • You said that you liked this activity. Can you explain more about it? • You said that this activity needs to be rethought. Which aspects would you change to make it work better?
<p>Final Questions</p>	<p>If you were to share something from this workshop with a friend, what would you tell them? Has anything changed for you after the workshop? Since we will repeat this process with other groups of young people, do you have any suggestions that we should consider for the future?</p>

Additionally, a visual summary of the lab was elaborated by the researchers and given to the participants during the Focus Group (see Figure 4). In it, each participant generates a graphical representation through a line showing the levels of motivation and involvement during each session, with the top of the page being the maximum level of involvement and the bottom of the page being the minimum level of involvement.

Figure 4. Visual Trajectory Sheet Given to the Participants During the Focus Group

	Presentar-nos a partir d'objectes	De què estic fent/a?	Experiències d'adultcentrisme: què vol dir adultcentrisme per mi?	Imaginant un món no-adultcentrista: Cap al disseny d'una acció	Dissenyant l'espai	Normes de l'espai i planificació
+						
-						

3.3 Outcomes of Cross-Cutting Analysis of the PAR Cycle 1

Two researchers conducted a cross-cutting analysis of the evaluation reports of all the CCLABs conducted during PAR Cycle 1. A total of 12 reports, including researcher's diaries and outcomes from the interviews and focus groups were systematically analysed. Researchers applied a thematic analysis approach to identify recurring themes, key

insights, and critical feedback across the reports. Key outcomes of the cross-cutting analysis will be reported in the next sections.

3.3.1 Participation, Engagement and Power Distribution

Since participation, engagement and power distribution represent core values of PAR approaches, a central focus of this initial evaluation stage was to analyse how participation, power distribution, and mutual learning were conceptualised and enacted within the labs, as well as the enabling and hindering factors influencing these dynamics.

Across the different labs there was a shared understanding of participation as dynamic and evolving processes, conceiving participation as an increased student autonomy, self-organization and creation of collaborative and less hierarchical learning environments.

Overall, the cross-cutting analysis showed that across all labs, there was a gradual transition from researcher-led to student-led activities. However, it remains unclear whether this shift resulted from the methodological design or the natural appropriation of the CCLAB's process by the students. Furthermore, the analysis revealed several factors that influenced students' participation, engagement, and power distribution. These factors either enhanced or hindered the overall dynamics within each lab.

Within the factors enhancing participation and engagement, the following aspects were identified:

- 1. Self-organization and freedom:** In several labs, researchers reported that providing participants with the freedom to self-organise and make decisions on their projects was a significant factor in supporting participation. For instance, in the Haltia lab (OULU), researchers reported that participants were more engaged during the sessions where they could work on their own. Similarly, in the Tyttöjen Talo (OULU), the TCD and the ISRZ labs, the participants showed higher engagement when designing their own prototypes during the Act phase; they seemed enthusiastic, self-organised and autonomous in giving life to their own ideas.
- 2. Maker and design activities:** Practical, hands-on activities such as maker sessions and design tasks were highly successful in promoting participation, shared decision-making, and democratic engagement. Examples can be found in the Norssi Lab (OULU), in the TCD Lab, in the WAAG Lab and in the IRSZ Lab, where students

were especially engaged during the Act phase when they were creating artifacts based on their own projects. These maker activities offered an immediate, tangible way for participants to express their ideas visually and directly.

- 3. Multimodal tools for expression:** The use of various methods of expression—verbal, written, artistic, etc.—enabled more diverse forms of participation. This approach allowed students to engage in ways that felt most comfortable to them, which broadened the inclusivity of the process. A clear example of it can be found in the WAAG Lab, where due to language barriers, multimodal and creative tools showed to be crucial to enable participation beyond the verbal language. Similarly, in the Haltia Lab, while boys tended to dominate verbal discussions, girls found alternative means of expression through written notes and collaborative boards. Also, in the UB Lab, working in small groups with the support of visual materials allowed the participation of voices that were less dominant in the debate and discussion.
- 4. Small groups and multiple facilitators:** In several labs, researchers reported that working in small groups enhanced participation, especially for those students that are shyer and more reserved. In this sense, also having multiple facilitators was beneficial to manage the groups and support students more effectively.
- 5. Connect with “outside the institution”:** Engaging with external elements, such as visits from other stakeholders or field trips (e.g., visiting an exhibition), positively impacted participation. These external interactions provided real-world context, which increased the relevance of the tasks. An example can be found in the ISRZ lab, where an NGO representative and a local government representative joined in. In the session dedicated to preparing the presentation for the government representative, participants were very engaged during the discussions. Similarly, in the Haltia Lab (OULU), visiting an exhibition was described by the researchers as a crucial turning point since participants started participating more. In this lab, the exhibition provided concrete and relevant data about the topic of the lab and encouraged participants to explore it from a sensorial perspective, going beyond the discursive framework.
- 6. Narrating their personal experiences:** Encouraging participants to share their personal experiences around the defined topic proved to be relevant for facilitating a comfortable environment and enhancing their engagement with the topic of the

CCLAB. These observations were reported in the UB lab and in the Tyttöjen Talo lab (OULU). In the UB lab, personal experiences regarding the topic of adultcentrism were used as a starting point to co-construct meaning around this phenomenon. This helped students connect with the topic on a deeper level and created a sense of ownership of the lab. In the Tyttöjen Talo lab (OULU), the goal of the lab was to explore tensions and challenges caused by social media for young people today. Within this process, participants started narrating personal experiences and incidents related to the topic and explored how social problems and phenomenon appear in their everyday lives.

- 7. The participation of facilitators:** Having facilitators engage with participants at an equal level significantly supported participation. This implies having facilitators and educators carrying out, together with the youth, the same activities that we ask them. The benefits of this facilitation strategy were observed, for instance, in both the Linz and Viena AE labs and in the UB lab, where researchers and educators were involved in all the proposed activities. This approach fostered a more collaborative and less hierarchical environment, making participants feel more comfortable and willing to contribute.

On the other hand, the following aspects were observed as hindering participation and engagement:

- 1. Time constraints:** Time constraints significantly impacted every stage of all the reported labs, presenting a recurring challenge. Researchers, stakeholders and participants identified the lack of time as a relevant limitation, affecting engagement, depth of discussion, and opportunities for achieving impact. The following key issues emerged:
 - **Limited time for deepened participation:** Across all labs, researchers noted that some participants wished to engage more deeply but were limited by time constraints. Although participants showed interest in more extended discussions and activities, sessions often had to be cut short to accommodate the schedule.
 - **Limited time to establish confidence:** The time required for students to build confidence and feel comfortable within the group was often insufficient.

Several researchers observed that “it takes quite a lot of time for students to feel safe in the group” and that “it took a while before everyone felt safe enough to speak.” This shortage of time prevented the establishment of the trust needed for open communication.

- **Limited time for producing tangible change:** The aim of achieving tangible changes within a limited timeframe was seen as overly ambitious. Researchers noted that achieving significant outcomes in a compressed timeframe was often unrealistic. This limitation suggested the need to extend engagement beyond the sessions planned for the labs.
 - **Limited time for reflection:** Time was also an issue for going deeper in reflection since often reflective time was compressed to finish specific designs and prototypes. This shortage of reflective time prevented participants from fully processing and discussing their experiences.
 - **Limited opportunity to address more serious research and include diverse perspectives:** Researchers pointed out that time constraints restricted the opportunity to involve students more deeply in the “research” stage and limited the possibilities of bringing in additional perspectives.
2. **Gender and participation dynamics:** In the Haltia Lab (OULU), gender influenced participation. Boys were more vocal in discussions, while girls were often more reserved. Although girls found ways to participate through written or non-verbal methods, this highlights the importance of offering multiple modes of engagement to balance power dynamics and participation levels.
 3. **Pre-existing social dynamics:** In labs that took place with established groups of young people, such as classrooms, existing social roles and dynamics were difficult to overcome. Students tended to default to familiar roles within the group, making it challenging to break established patterns of behaviour and collaboration. As noted in the WAAG lab, “it became clear that the students are used to taking on certain roles, and it is hard work to break free from that.”
 4. **Drop in engagement during reflective stages:** In several labs researchers reported that, while students were highly engaged in hands-on, creative tasks, their participation tended to decrease during more reflective stages of the process.

Reflective activities, which required deeper thought and analysis, were often less stimulating for students compared to active, maker-oriented tasks.

Finally, the role of digital tools to support or hinder participation was unclear. For instance, in Norssi and Tyttöjen Talo labs (OULU), tools such as Padlet, which allowed for anonymous participation, were particularly effective in the early sessions for encouraging quieter students to contribute. Instead, in the UB lab, students explicitly refused to use digital tools and did not participate in any online space. This may be because these digital tools are commonly used by the participants for their school tasks. No other remarkable observations regarding digital tools appeared in the reports.

Overall, this overview of factors influencing youth participation provides an initial starting point for identifying the key elements that the iterative design of the model should take into account. Among these, particular emphasis should be placed on addressing time constraints as well as the resistance observed during the more reflective stages.

3.3.2 Conceptualizing Learning

A second focus of this evaluation stage centred on the following aspects: how learning was understood and facilitated within the context of the PAR methodology, and what pedagogical conditions supported or constrained these processes.

3.3.2.1 Conceptualizing Learning in CCLABs

The observations about learning within the CCLABs varied significantly across different contexts, reflecting diverse interpretations of what learning entails. Within them, the conceptualization of learning ranged from the acquisition of novel knowledge to the development of specific competences. In some cases, for instance, learning was understood primarily as the acquisition of new knowledge on a predefined topic. Examples of this can be found in the TCD lab and the LATRA lab. In the first one, the development of a timeline of LGBTIQ+ rights in Ireland enabled students to develop a new understanding of the topic of discrimination and encouraged them to embrace multiple perspectives. In the second one the historical analysis of the phenomenon helped participants to contextualise the topic and understand its broader future implications. For example, looking at how the privatisation of education in other EU countries has evolved, helped participants in

understanding how it might affect Greece. It also helped certain participants get a better grasp on the subject as they lacked historical background and other similar cases.

In other circumstances, instead, learning was mainly understood as the development of specific competencies. Researchers' diaries highlighted the development of the following competencies:

- 1. Broadening of the understanding of a phenomenon:** In different labs, researchers observed learning outcomes related to changing perspectives on the understanding of a topic. For instance, at WAAG, researchers observed that participants moved from understanding democracy as an abstract idea to recognising it as an everyday practice and understanding the complexities of democratic ways of doing. Similarly, in the UB lab, the process of reflecting on adultcentrism allowed participants to move from the complaints about their everyday lives toward a systemic understanding of the phenomenon, where everybody plays a role. In a similar vein, researchers noted that dialogical activities prompted participants to confront differing opinions and eventually change them by including different perspectives. This learning outcome is well exemplified in the Linz lab (AE) where some participants through listening to others' reasonings, shifted their viewpoints about desirable futures.
- 2. Critical reflection on everyday experiences:** In several labs, researchers observed that the PAR cycle enabled participants to critically reflect on their personal experiences and connect them to broader societal themes. On the one hand, this allowed them to reflect on how the topic is visible in everyday life. On the other, it supported the understanding that personal issues are often part of a shared and common problem. Examples of these can be found in the UB lab and the Norssi and Tyttöjen Talo (OULU) labs. In the Tyttöjen lab, for instance, reflecting on personal experiences related to pressures caused by social media to self-esteem allowed deepening into the relation between wellness and social media. In the UB lab, similarly, reflecting on their everyday experiences related to adultcentrism allowed them to identify how this phenomenon is embedded in the multiple spaces that they inhabit (e.g., school, family, public spaces, health systems) and enriched their systemic understanding of the phenomenon and their ability to identify it.

- 3. Development of practical and creative skills:** Evidence about specific skills development was also collected in the researchers' diaries. Specifically, researchers pointed out that participants developed skills related to collaborative work, maker competencies, and project proposal development. In this sense, participants learned about using tools, materials, and creative processes to design and construct solutions as well as formulating structured project proposals.

Overall, the initial evaluation of learning within the analysed CCLABs highlights two key aspects that should be considered for future iterations. These include the need to establish a shared understanding of what learning entails across contexts, as well as the importance of better systematizing the competences that the Critical ChangeLab model seeks to scaffold.

3.3.2.2 Factors Enhancing or Hindering Learning

From the analysis a series of factors that either enhanced or hindered the learning process of participants were identified. On the one hand, the following factors were identified as supportive of learning processes:

- 1. Learning through personal interests:** Choosing topics of personal interest, such as in the Haltia and Tyttöjen Talo labs (OULU) and UB lab, engaged participants and helped them to learn from their lived experiences. In these labs, participants were encouraged to choose the topic according to their interests. As stated in the evaluation reports, this fostered engagement and significant learning. One of the participants in the UB lab expressed during the focus group: "It was nice to let us choose the topic and work on adultcentrism. At the school, many times we work on sexism and racism. Those are important topics, but somehow repetitive" (UB1, FG_report). Choosing the topic allowed participants to take ownership of the lab, connect it to their everyday concerns, and generate meaningful learning from their experiences.
- 2. Mutual learning:** Mutual learning was evident in collaborative discussions, peer-to-peer exchanges, and informal learning during activities (e.g., Haltia-OULU, LATRA, TCD and UB). Moreover, forms of non-verbal collaboration were observed as relevant for mutual learning. As reported from the WAAG lab: "It is fascinating to see how much collaboration and decision-making takes place without using language. Students

act out something, demonstrate something or touch each other. They convince each other by making and presenting something” (WAAG1, Research diaries).

- 3. Broadening perspectives:** Activities like historical analysis (LATRA) and speculative futures (AE) helped participants contextualise learning, linking past, present, and future to create a deeper understanding. In the LATRA lab, exploring the issue from a historical perspective allowed participants to better situate it within a broader context and reflect on its possible future outcomes. As mentioned above, studying how education privatisation has progressed in other EU nations helped them anticipate its potential effects in Greece. Similarly, timeline proposals (TCD) enable participants to connect their learning to social and political contexts, fostering critical thinking; creating a timeline of LGBTIQ+ rights in Ireland helped students gain a deeper insight into discrimination and motivated them to consider diverse viewpoints.
- 4. Learning by doing:** Hands-on activities, such as zine-making (TCD), jewellery-making and serigraphy (OULU), encourage active engagement and foster informal exchanges of knowledge. While producing their artistic objects, participants tended to talk in small groups or among peers about their ideas and reflections on the topic of the lab, blurring the barriers between doing and thinking/practice and theory. Moreover, visual tools like mind mapping (OULU Norssi and Haltia) help participants organise and expand their ideas, enabling them to explore connections within their topics. According to the reports, mind mapping allows for a visual organisation of the collective reflections that strengthens the sharing and enables the participants' findings to be recorded so that they can be better explored in greater depth.

On the other hand, the analysis also revealed several factors that hindered the learning processes. First, as mentioned earlier, in several labs, participants lost interest during the more reflective phases. In some ways, they showed signs of fatigue and a lack of motivation to engage in deeper debate or reflection. Second, introducing the labs through abstract concepts such as democracy or social change also proved to be an obstacle to the learning process, since the young participants often perceived these notions as distant, abstract, and not directly relevant to their own experiences.

Overall, the review of the learning processes across the different labs confirms the importance of principles derived from critical pedagogy and experiential learning as key

elements for the development of the model. Particular emphasis is placed on situated knowledge in the process of constructing knowledge collectively. At the same time, specific challenges were also identified. Among these, the abstraction of the concept of democracy deserves particular attention. In this regard, it becomes necessary to reflect on how this theme can be introduced in ways that are more accessible, meaningful, and relevant to young people.

3.3.3 Youth as Active Citizens

The third focus of the first stage of evaluation was to observe how young people conceptualise their role as active citizens. This involved both mapping their concerns and interests, as well as gaining an initial understanding of their conceptions of democracy.

3.3.3.1 Youth’s Concerns and Interests

During PAR Cycle 1, young people expressed concerns about several themes. These can be categorized broadly into concerns related to social issues, concerns related to environmental issues and concerns related to digital worlds (summarized in Table 7).

Table 7. Youth’s Concerns and Interests

Concern	Topic	Description
Societal Concerns	Equality and fairness	Questions of equity and fairness, especially regarding majority and minority dynamics, and ensuring everyone’s voice is heard
	Polarization of society and concerns about the influence of radical ideologies	Concerns about increasing divisions within society and how they affect community cohesion and decision-making
	Education system	Concerns about the future of education and the impact of privatization of education, especially universities, and its impact on access and quality
	Discrimination, prejudices, racism and Islamophobia	
	Adultcentrism	

Environmental Concerns	Climate change	Concerns about the environmental crisis and its implications for the future
Media and Digital World	Media discourses, manipulation, and fake news	Worries about how narratives in the media shape perceptions, manipulate public opinion and make it difficult to distinguish truth from misinformation online
	Cyberbullying	Concerns related to online harassment based on appearance, speech, ethnicity, or gender
	Concerns about how social media affects self-esteem	

However, the evaluation instrument employed demonstrated clear limitations in capturing participants' situated perspectives and understandings of the issues under consideration. Given the importance of grounding the PAR process in topics that resonate with young people's lived experiences, it is therefore necessary to design instruments that are more attuned and responsive to these concerns.

3.3.3.2 Youth's Ways of Understanding and Doing Democracy by Young People

The reports show that, in general, young people's understanding of democracy is oriented towards situated practice and embodied in their own experience. Instead, the discursive understanding of political notions such as democracy, society or participation is limited and usually focuses on general and imprecise definitions of these notions. In several reports, we can observe a clear contrast between democracy as a complex, abstract idea and as a practical, embodied activity. In the case of WAAG, participants initially found democracy hard to define, but when it was reframed through codesign, collaboration, and joint decision-making, democratic values became more understandable. In this report, researchers stated that although "it was difficult for the participating young people to express their opinion about something complex such as democracy or society [...] the theme mainly lingered in the form of 'equal cooperation' and democratic principles that can help you make joint decisions" (WAAG1, Research diaries).

These reflections are aligned with the outcomes of other reports that showed that where young people have shown the greatest potential in understanding and doing democracy is through feeling recognised and listened to, and through concrete practices and

collaborating with their peers. Across multiple contexts, being heard emerges as a foundational experience of democracy for young people. Tyttöjen Talo (OULU), WAAG and UB labs emphasised the importance of young people feeling that their voice matters. In the OULU lab being listened to is described as “validating” and “empowering”. In the youths’ own words: “It was really helpful to have a feeling that somebody is interested in listening to what I say, or somebody is interested in what I think or what my opinion or point of view is regarding a certain issue” (OULU, Focus group). Similarly, in the UB lab, several participants highlighted during the focus group the fact that they chose the topic of the lab was significant, as in their school the projects’ topics and orientation are usually decided by teachers.

Alongside these considerations, collaboration also emerged as a key democratic skill for youth. For instance, the WAAG report highlights non-verbal cooperation, suggesting that democratic processes can extend beyond spoken discussion. However, participants also indicated that they still find collaboration very difficult. ISRZ participants were less inclined to take control or initiative, revealing potential gaps in confidence or readiness to engage collaboratively. In this sense, fostering team building can contribute to creating an environment of collaboration and teamwork. This could be observed in the UB lab, where the group was very small, and they had a very good relationship with each other beforehand. This created a teamwork environment where all voices were heard and taken into account.

Finally, a recurring theme was the limited sense of agency and the lack of motivating spaces for democratic participation. The ISRZ report showed that young people are not always aware of the spaces for democratic participation in society where they can have an impact: “They are not aware of the opportunities for their involvement in the creation of cultural politics. It seems that they do not have ideas of cultural activities in which they would like to participate, suggesting a lack of motivation and/or agency for cultural participation”. This was also observable in the UB lab: for the participants, the idea of bringing about change in society was, at the beginning of the lab, inaccessible. This was the case even when they were aware of participation mechanisms in their immediate environment, such as the ‘children’s council’ in their school, where students can make proposals for improvement in the organisation of the school. Nonetheless, they reported that these kinds of structures are not meaningful to them since their voices tend to not be taken seriously.

Overall, the analysis showed that, while the notion of democracy seems abstract and difficult to grasp, participants construct their democratic skills through experiential learning and meaningful situations and understand democracy through personal experiences of voice and recognition, rather than formal structures or definitions. These outcomes align with Dewey's perspective on democracy as a lived experience and suggest that experiential engagement with democratic practices is more effective than speaking about abstract political concepts to learn about democracy. From the perspective of the model design, these findings suggest the need to more clearly frame how we conceptualise democracy education within the model and to find proper strategies to support a meaningful experiential learning of democracy. On the other hand, the tensions between the need for being heard and the lack of space for democratic participation requires further reflections in relation to educational policies.

3.3.4 Impact and Sustainability

A fourth focus of the evaluation aimed at assessing the sustainability of the labs. According to the researchers' reports, the long-term impact and sustainability of the labs are shaped by a range of contextual and structural factors. These include how well the activities are integrated into existing institutional programmes, their alignment with educational goals and curricula, the relevance of the topics addressed, and the observable changes in participants' lives. At the same time, certain barriers can limit the potential for continued implementation and scalability. These include misalignment with institutional frameworks, dependence on individual facilitators, and lack of ready-to-use resources.

In some cases, integration into existing programmes and alignment with curricula and institutional goals increased the likelihood of long-term adoption. For instance, at the Vienna lab (AE), participants' involvement in the Create Your World Prize programme ensures continued engagement with the issues raised, embedding the model into broader institutional activities. Similarly, at the Linz lab (AE), outcomes from the process fed both podcasts and discussions at the Ars Electronica Festival and supported participants' long-term engagement. In IRSZ, the local government representative offered to help with a transport problem in order to address part of the problem that participants raised up. This positive feedback encouraged participants for further engagement. Similarly, in UB the final project elaborated by the participants aligned with the goals of the Service-Learning Programme they were attending, which facilitated the sustainability of the process beyond

the lab implementation. During the interview, the educator said: “In the end it all came together: their training as conflict mediators, their interest in adultcentrism... and the school welcomed the proposal very well” (UBI, interview).

On the other hand, instead, mismatch with institutional constraints impeded long term engagement. For instance, Nature School in Haltia lab (OULU) found the multi-meeting format unsuitable, suggesting the model may not align with their operational structures and time constraints. Within this line, some partners also noted that future implementations depend on who is working in the institution, highlighting the vulnerability of sustainability to staff turnover and individual commitment. Both in OULU and WAAG, educators expressed uncertainty about replicating the lab with different participant groups, raising concerns about the model’s adaptability to varying contexts. Teachers, specifically, pointed out the need for clear, pre-designed instructions that are easy to implement for teachers (OULU). Without these, the burden on teachers to adapt or interpret materials could hinder future implementations.

On the other hand, while evaluating the broader institutional or environmental impact of the labs can be challenging, the influence on participants’ personal lives was more tangible. Across various contexts, several participants reported making small but meaningful changes in their daily lives, guided by a more critical and conscious perspective. For example, at Tyttöjen Talo (OULU), where the lab focused on self-esteem and the influence of social media, one participant noted, “From now on, one thing that would change is maybe paying less attention to others’ opinions about me” (OULU, Tyttöjen Talo Focus Group). At Norssi (Oulu), where participants designed tote bags with messages about media manipulation, one participant shared his surprise at how the bag he had created became a means of dialogue with his grandfather during a weekend ice-fishing trip. At LATRA, researchers and facilitators emphasised a focus on behavioural change, which they believe was achieved to some extent.

This overview highlights the structural challenges of ensuring long-term sustainability and underscores the need for the model to incorporate specific strategies that align more effectively with the scope, calendars, and working structures of different educational institutions, as well as the development of tailored materials for educators. At the same time, the findings point to the necessity of improving the evaluation instrument to more consistently capture changes in participants.

3.3.6 Challenges and Tensions of the CCLAB Model

To sum-up, the cross-cutting analysis allowed the identification of several challenges and tensions that occurred during PAR Cycle 1. Specifically:

- 1. Structural and institutional constraints:** One significant challenge faced by the CCLABs was the tension between school structures and the participatory goals of the labs. In traditional educational settings, hierarchical teacher-student relationships often dominate. These dynamics create a power imbalance that limits students' ability to take ownership of the process and engage fully as equal participants. Furthermore, this tension highlights the difficulty of introducing participatory approaches in environments built on traditional hierarchies and routines. This issue is clearly expressed in the Haltia Lab (OULU), where researchers reported: "The school context with all of its built-in power relations and needs [...] are in tension with the students' wishes of more free and participatory activities than regular schoolwork" (OULU1, Research diaries). This tension is also reflected in other labs. For instance, in Norssi (OULU), the established roles of teachers as authority figures hindered the labs' aim of fostering open dialogue and collaboration. Similarly, in the Linz lab (AE), researchers specifically report a critical incident where the surprise visit by a teacher at the school (who was not connected to the class or to the lab) led to a reinforcement of the top-down teacher/student relationship and school rules for a part of the session. This issue was also reported in the WAAG lab where students tended to stick to familiar patterns and the authoritarian supervision by educators further compounded the problem. Specifically, in this case, facilitators observed that strict, top-down interactions by school staff confused students and made it difficult for them to adapt to the labs' collaborative goals. Consequently, students were less willing to speak openly or participate fully, fearing judgment or reprimand from authority figures.

However, tensions related to the institutional setting were not only related to hierarchical structure and authority but also to the habits and norms of the school setting. As stated in the Linz (AE) and ISRZ labs, institutional habits and practices often clashed with the model's participatory intentions. In Linz, for instance, school rules, such as enforcing silence, orderly behaviour, and strict adherence to predefined tasks, contradicted the labs' emphasis on free expression and open-

ended exploration. Similarly, in IRSZ, researchers reported that “participants do not take the time (or even a few moments) to think through the activity, which can be related to the school setting which emphasises the execution of the task and not necessarily its quality” (IRSZI, Researcher diaries). Similarly, in both cases, researchers reported that students in school environments expected clear outputs, creating tension with the exploratory approach of the labs. These tensions created a mismatch between the environment students were accustomed to and the more fluid, participatory framework of the labs.

- 2. Time limitations:** As previously mentioned, a recurring challenge in the implementation of CCLABs was the insufficient time allocated for activities, which limited their overall effectiveness. The short durations of the labs presented obstacles in several key areas. For instance, in Norssi (OULU), Vienna (AE), Linz (AE), and ISRZ, there was not enough time for participants to deeply reflect on their experiences, thoroughly explore different perspectives, or build the trust necessary for open and meaningful collaboration. Additionally, the complexity of the concepts addressed in the labs further emphasised the need for extended timeframes. Topics such as democracy, critical thinking, and social change require participants to not only grasp abstract ideas but also apply them in practical ways. This depth of understanding often necessitates activities over time, which was not feasible in the short timeframe of the labs. Similarly, several researchers reported that expecting tangible change within limited timelines was overly ambitious, particularly in school settings. In this sense, timing challenges were not only related to the limited number of sessions but also were compounded by the academic calendar. Incidentally this happened, where the labs were scheduled near the end of the school year. This late timing left little room for the implementation of broader changes beyond the immediate classroom context. The conclusion of the academic term also created logistical hurdles, as participants and educators were often preoccupied with completing regular schoolwork and preparing for year-end assessments.
- 3. Pedagogical challenges:** In some cases, researchers’ diaries reflect challenges related to the complexity of the contents and ambitious goals of the model. Specifically, in WAAG, AE Linz, LATRA and UB researchers reported that participants faced significant challenges in engaging with abstract concepts such as democracy, critical thinking, and empathy mapping, which often felt complex and

intangible. These ideas required a level of cognitive and reflective engagement that many students found difficult to achieve, particularly within the time constraints of the sessions. In the WAAG lab, researchers reported: “It was difficult for the participating young people to express their opinion about something complex such as democracy or society” (WAAG1, Researcher diaries). Similarly, in Linz (AE), researchers observed that: “it is not easy to ignite critical thinking and make them think beyond what they already know” (AE1, Research diaries). In this sense, facilitators struggled to ignite deeper critical thinking and encourage students to move beyond surface-level interpretations and felt that they needed more time and tailored strategies to help participants explore diverse perspectives and develop a more nuanced understanding of these concepts.

- 4. The challenges of supporting reflection:** As previously mentioned, in several labs, researchers reported that, while students were highly engaged in hands-on, creative tasks, their participation tended to decrease during more reflective stages of the process. Reflective activities, which required deeper thought and analysis, were often less stimulating for students compared to active, maker-oriented tasks. In particular, researchers reported that, for instance, sessions that entailed a lot of discussion resulted in a lack of interest in some participants (IRSZ) and drop in engagement. Furthermore, sessions that strongly relied on debate produced exclusionary patterns since it was a format that mainly supported those who have experience with such participation.
- 5. The tensions between freedom and structure:** The tension between freedom and structure was also a recurring issue in researchers’ reflections on PAR Cycle 1. This issue is well reflected in the UB lab, specifically during the 3rd session, where researchers found themselves dealing with the tensions between being more directive in order to achieve a concrete output or letting students lead the process, running the risk of not achieving any intended results. Similarly, other reflections address issues related to the flexibility of the CCLAB model. Flexibility, while intended to foster adaptability, introduced challenges related to ambiguity in both objectives and outcomes. In practice, this openness sometimes left participants uncertain about the purpose or direction of the activities, hindering participants’ engagement and making it difficult to assess progress or achieve meaningful results. This issue, for instance, is reported in the Norssi lab (OULU), where researchers pointed out that

the ambiguity of the CCLAB outcomes creates some uncertainty that youth are not used to in school context. Similarly, in the TCD lab, researchers reported that students would need a more defined action. Finally, in ISRZ, reflecting on the current lack of a clear structure can make the process feel as though "everything goes," diluting its impact and making it harder to maintain coherence across sessions.

- 6. Needs to deepen participation and research components:** Additional reflections on the current limitation of the model address the need to deepen the participation of students and stakeholders in defining the model and its unfolding. Furthermore, further emphasis should be placed on the research dimension since the participatory research component in some cases ended up being under utilised, with a limited involvement of students in a truly research-based process.

3.3.7 Strengths and Opportunities of the CCLAB Model

The cross-cutting analysis enabled the identification of key strengths and opportunities of the CCLAB model that emerged during the first PAR cycle. Specifically:

- 1. Methodological richness:** The cross-cutting analysis revealed a diverse array of methods used to address the different stages of the process. Specifically, we identified 14 distinct methods employed during the Onboard stage, 22 methods in the Question & Analyse stage, 13 methods in the Envision & Act stage, and 3 methods in the Reflect stage. This methodological richness is one of the key strengths of the model, providing flexibility and adaptability across different contexts. The following table provides a short description of the methods employed, grouped in stages (Table 8).

Table 8. *Methods of PAR Cycle 1 Iteration*

Stage	Partner	Method	Description
Onboard	UB	Performative Still Lives	Students brought objects representing themselves and explained their personal significance, fostering self-expression and peer understanding.
	OULU	Feelings Mapping	After watching a bullying-related video, students reflected on their feelings using a “me-we-us” structure: individually, in pairs, and then as a group.
		Building Connections to Democracy	Students discussed how human relationships relate to democracy, linking these ideas to insights from the feelings mapping activity.
		Mapping Common Interests	Using Padlet and sticky notes, participants anonymously shared topics they wished to explore, ensuring everyone could contribute regardless of tech access.
	TCD	Team Building: String & Marker Exercise	Groups used strings and markers to collaboratively write “CCL”, encouraging teamwork and creative problem-solving.
		Walking Debate	Students positioned themselves on either side of a line in response to provocative statements, sparking discussion and reflection on diverse viewpoints.
	WAAG	Agree/Disagree Discussion	Participants engaged in group dialogue around various statements, deciding collectively whether they agreed or disagreed.
		Identity Collage	Each child created a collage that visually represented their identity, promoting self-reflection and creative expression.
	AE	Yes/No Ice-Breaker Game	Participants responded to fun and thought-provoking yes/no questions, from light topics to deeper themes like democracy and participation.

Stage	Partner	Method	Description
		The Line-Up Game	Participants formed lines based on different prompts (e.g., birth dates, number of siblings), creating a fun way to learn about each other.
	LATRA	Two Truths and a Lie	Each person shared two truths and one lie about themselves, with the group guessing which statement was false.
		Perspectives Map	A reimagined version of the empathy map used to document and explore the perspectives of participants.
		Dynamic Governance	Based on consent-based decision-making, this method ensured all voices were heard in group discussions (see: https://www.icmta.com/Dynamic-Governance)
		Participatory Decision Making	Participants jointly discussed issues, addressed challenges, and made collective decisions (see: https://tools4dev.org/blog/what-is-participatory-decision-making/).
Question & Analyse	UB	Collaborative Mural	Participants brought images representing what they're "fed up with" and interested in. A collective mural was created to spark discussion and focus for the lab.
		Mapping and Placing	Using a map of everyday spaces (home, school, street), students plotted experiences of adultcentrism and discussed related power dynamics.
		Visual Retrospective	A digital map summarizing past sessions was shared to support group reflection and future planning.
	OULU	Creating Group Rules	Students proposed rules for group interaction, first individually, then in pairs, then collectively. The final rules were agreed upon and signed by all.
		Exhibition Tour: Human-Nature Focus	During a curated exhibition tour, students engaged in small tasks like interpreting animal expressions and ranking items by their "naturalness."

Stage	Partner	Method	Description
		What Would Nature Say	Students imagined what elements in nature would say to humans, wrote messages in speech bubbles, and photographed them in nature.
		Letter to the Prime Minister	Participants wrote letters titled “What is a good future?” addressed to the Prime Minister of Finland.
		Mirror of Experiences	Students collected digital content related to nature and democracy on Flinga, reflecting their thoughts and lived experiences. (see: https://flinga.fi/).
		Mind Mapping	Small groups explored a chosen topic through a guided mind map covering actors, ideologies, power, perspectives, and temporal aspects.
	TCD	Rapid Ideation	Groups combined a societal group, a social issue, and a creative intervention to brainstorm possible solutions and interventions.
		Values Tree	Participants explored personal, organizational, and shared values, helping to define the Junior Board’s collective value system.
		Mind Mapping Exercise	Participants reflected on experiences of belonging and being heard, mapping spaces and contexts where these occurred.
		LGBTQ+ Rights Timeline Activity	Students sought information to create a timeline of changes in Ireland in terms of LGTBIQ+ rights over the last decades.
	AE	Empathy Map	Participants imagined perspectives of various human and non-human agents in diverse scenarios, then explored challenges and differences.
		Open Discussion	Participants discussed key concepts like democracy, activism, and participation based on their own experiences and understandings.
	ISRZ	5 Whys Analysis	Small groups used the “5 Whys” method to explore root causes of an issue and brainstorm potential solutions.

Stage	Partner	Method	Description
		Photovoice Activity	Participants use photographs to express experiences and discuss concerns.
		Analysing and Choosing Statements	Participants identify barriers to cultural participation and elaborate statements.
		Sharing Opinions with External Stakeholders	Students presented their views to experts and politically influential stakeholders for open discussion and debate.
	LATRA	Dynamic Governance	Based on consent-based decision-making, this method ensures all voices are heard (see: https://www.icmta.com/Dynamic-Governance).
		Participatory Decision Making	Stakeholders collaboratively discuss issues, resolve problems, and reach decisions through inclusive dialogue (see: https://tools4dev.org/blog/what-is-participatory-decision-making/).
Envision & Act (Creative and visual methods)	UB and OULU	Canva for Ideation	Groups reflected on their topic and designed solutions within their sphere of influence using Canva, based on their interests and skills.
	UB	Designing a Mediation Kit	Students created prototypes for a school calm room using recycled materials as part of their final project.
	OULU	Thinking a Slogan	Participants reflected on a personal issue, designed a slogan, and crafted slogan-themed jewelry to raise awareness.
	TCD	Zine Making	Participants created zines capturing reflections on inclusion, belonging, change-making, and visions for the future across six pages.
	WAAG	Co-design Exercise	Participants co-designed a costume using creative constraints (e.g., timers, moodboards), promoting democratic decision-making.
	ISRZ	Reminder Board	A Miro board, posters, and printed photos summarized previous activities and materials, helping students reconnect with past work (see: https://miro.com/).

Stage	Partner	Method	Description
Envision & Act (Speculative and Futures-Oriented Methods)	UB	Guided Visualization	Students engaged in mindfulness to imagine a society without adultcentrism, visualizing its design, relationships, and values.
	UB and OULU	Speculative Scenarios and Timeline	Pairs imagined and illustrated future non-adultcentrist settings (home, school, street), then built a timeline to make them real.
	OULU	Futures Visioning Exercise	After a talk on "making the future," students envisioned a positive future and outlined five steps to get there (used in Question phase).
	AE	Future(s) Exhibition	Participants explored various past depictions of the future (e.g., Metropolis, Mad Max), wrote observations, clustered them, and named key themes.
		Create a Manifesto	Building on the Future(s) Exhibition, participants created manifestos expressing their visions and demands for the future.
ISRZ	Speculative Design	Students learned speculative design and imagined a future with no barriers to cultural participation in their local environment.	
Envision & Act (Interactive and participatory dialogue methods)	AE	Speed Dating	Using rotating partner discussions, participants explored provocative questions about the future of schools and societal roles.
	ISRZ	Presentation to Local Government	Students prepared and presented their CCLAB work to both local officials and the wider community.
	LATRA	Adhocracy	A facilitation style emphasizing decentralised leadership, individual initiative, and organic, flexible decision-making.
		Dynamic Governance	A consent-based decision-making method that ensures all voices are included (see: https://www.icmta.com/Dynamic-Governance).
		Participatory Decision-Making	Stakeholders collaboratively discuss, problem-solve, and decide on actions together (see:

Stage	Partner	Method	Description
			https://tools4dev.org/blog/what-is-participatory-decision-making/ .
Reflect	UB	Pooling of Ideas	Two groups worked on separate assignments and later shared outcomes with the whole class, encouraging collective reflection and feedback.
	TCD	Inside/Outside Circle and Structured Discussion	Participants discussed three levels of questions (information, reflection, meta-reflection) with rotating partners in inner and outer circles.
	Waag	Rating Through Stickers	Participants used stickers to rate different aspects of the activity, providing a quick and visual way to evaluate the session.

- 2. Hands-on and maker activities to enhance engagement:** Maker activities were consistently engaging and well-received across different contexts. This can be seen at OULU, where participants produced outputs with concrete messages (e.g., totebags with critical messages on media manipulation at Tyttöjen Talo and jewelry with messages promoting self-esteem at the Norssi lab), fostering better understanding and engagement; at TCD, where the zine-making process facilitated peer-to-peer discussion and mutual learning; and at IRSZ, where visual and creative methods were particularly helpful in breaking down participation barriers and enabling free expression.
- 3. Co-design and co-creation to experience and learn democratic principles:** Experiencing democracy as a collaborative process was a key strength. A key example can be found in the WAAG lab. In this case participants worked in groups to create a costume that would embody their collective identity. To facilitate co-creation, various strategies were employed, including time constraints for decision-making and experimenting with different ways of reaching shared agreements and asking them to apply democratic principles throughout the making process (e.g., voting, electing a representative, or consulting another group). In that sense, embedding democratic experimentation within the creative act itself created opportunities for reflection, turning concrete situations into entry points for dialogue about democracy, helping participants internalize abstract democratic values like equality and inclusivity through direct experience rather than theoretical discussion.

WAAG especially emphasised this: “It is important to link the content to the creative process so that students experience democratic values and principles instead of talking about them” (WAAG1, Researcher Diaries); “By focusing very much on equality in collaboration, the groups were able to experience for themselves how complicated democracy is” (WAAG1, Researcher Diaries).

- 4. Creative methods to encourage inclusive and open participation:** Many settings demonstrated the effectiveness of creative methods in reducing barriers and fostering inclusivity. For instance, at IRSZ, researchers noted that visual methods created an open space where all participants could contribute equally, regardless of background or ability. Similarly, WAAG highlighted that artistic and visual methodologies helped in creating a more inclusive environment by enabling non-verbal communication, particularly in contexts where participants speak different languages.
- 5. Speculative imagination to broaden perspectives:** The CCLAB model supports participants in connecting their learning to broader contexts. Vienna lab (AE) demonstrated that by encouraging participants to analyse imagined futures from the past, helped them envision how speculative futures could become reality. The participants expressed that analysing examples of imagined futures from the past activated their own thinking about possible futures and made them realise that speculative futures can actually become reality.
- 6. Progressive autonomy to support participation:** At Linz (AE) and UB, participants transitioned from structured methods to open-ended tasks, allowing them to develop confidence and creativity over time. This progression ensures participants are supported early on and gradually empowered to take ownership of the process, fostering both engagement and independence: “The aim was to not enforce hierarchies, neither teacher-student nor with the institutional representative” (AE1, Researchers Diaries). In the UB lab, the transition from a teacher-led process to a more student-led approach allowed students to take ownership of the lab and incorporate their own desires and needs. In this sense, they were able to lead a proposal for change in how the spaces in their school were organised and used, based on their physical and emotional needs.

Overall, the overview of the strengths of the model points out the relevance of art-based, imaginative and creative methods to support a wide set of skills and attitudes. In this sense, further iteration of the model should put a stronger emphasis on these aspects.

3.3.8 Researchers' Feedback on the Evaluation Instrument

The employed evaluation instruments across the CCLABs were met with mixed feedback, revealing both benefits and challenges. Regarding the researchers' diaries, on the one hand, researchers reported that the evaluation tools encouraged internal reflection and served as effective documentation and communication aids. Diaries and reporting mechanisms helped research teams coordinate, share reflections, and maintain continuity, especially when team members missed meetings or sessions. On the other hand, however, the diaries were often long and repetitive, which consumed significant time and resources. Repeated questions were perceived as redundant and occasionally inapplicable. Furthermore, additional issues were identified in the evaluation process about the sensitivity of the instruments to capture participants' voices. Also, "quick and dirty" evaluation instruments for students were considered useful to provide instant feedback but were often too generic, failing to offer meaningful differentiation or insights specific to the participants or contexts. Finally, the evaluation process felt overly ambitious, with certain expectations being unachievable given the limited number of meetings or the early stage of the programme's development.

4. First Redesign Iteration: Areas of Improvement for PAR Cycle 2

The identified outcomes and expert evaluations were shared with the consortium to guide the refinement of the CCLAB model. Through these collaborative reviews, key priorities were identified to be implemented in the next iteration of the model, ensuring that the second PAR cycle built upon the lessons learned. Specifically, the following key priorities and action points were highlighted (see Table 9).

Table 9. Summary of Key Areas of Improvement and Derived Actions

	Key Priorities	Action Points
General	<p>Need to build a shared understanding of learning and expected learning outcomes:</p> <p>The initial evaluation revealed diverse interpretations of what learning entails, as well as early indications of the development of specific competences. It also surfaced preliminary insights into the factors that either facilitated or hindered learning processes. However, there is a need to establish a common conception of learning across contexts and to better systematise the competences that the model seeks to scaffold.</p>	<p>Identification of key learning goals and competences.</p> <p>Identification of key learning goals and competences, aligned with the model’s pedagogical intentions.</p> <p>Design of a validation protocol to co-define and refine these competences in dialogue with participants and key stakeholders.</p> <p>Creation of an evaluation rubric based on the validated competences, to support a more structured and transparent assessment process.</p> <p>Redesign of existing evaluation instruments to ensure stronger alignment with the identified learning goals and competences.</p>
	<p>Need to gain a deeper understanding of how young people perceive eco-social phenomena, democracy, and their own agency:</p>	<p>Improvement of the evaluation instruments and training of facilitators involved in the evaluation.</p>

	Key Priorities	Action Points
	<p>While the first evaluation process provided some initial insights into how participants relate to and interpret these complex issues, the findings also pointed to the necessity of a more in-depth exploration. This should include examining both how young people conceptualise eco-social and democratic issues and the challenges they face in engaging with them meaningfully.</p>	
Methodological	<p>Need to systematise the model’s methodological richness and assess the impact of specific pedagogical strategies:</p> <p>One of the model’s strengths lies in its diverse and creative methodological approaches. Nonetheless, a more systematic documentation and evaluation of these methods is needed to understand their specific contributions and to optimize their use in future iterations.</p>	<p>Improve, systematise, document the model’s methodological strategies</p> <p>Organise recurrent meetings with the Community of Practice to support shared reflection on methods.</p> <p>Create templates or guides to capture methodological practices used in different contexts.</p> <p>Identify which methods are most effective.</p>
	<p>Need to strengthen practices that allow an experiential learning of democracy:</p> <p>Abstract notions of democracy proved challenging. In this regard, it becomes necessary to introduce this theme in ways that are more accessible, meaningful, and relevant to young people. Experiential strategies showed to be particularly effective to this end. In this sense, further exploration is needed to design strategies that frame democracy education through meaningful, experiential engagement, enabling participants to develop democratic skills through lived experiences of voice and recognition, rather than formal definitions alone.</p>	
	<p>Need to place greater emphasis on art-based methods and participatory research techniques:</p> <p>The model’s strengths lie in imaginative, participatory, and art-based approaches. These methodological approaches are considered a core strength and distinctive feature of the model, hence deeper attention should be devoted to their application and implementation.</p>	

	Key Priorities	Action Points
	<p>Need to reframe reflection methods: More attention should be given to the design of methods that support the Reflect stage. Currently, only three methods exist, indicating the need for further development to enhance this critical aspect of the process.</p>	
Evaluation	<p>Need to improve the evaluation instruments: Current tools show limitations in capturing participants' situated perspectives and learning outcomes, highlighting the need for instruments that are more sensitive and responsive to young people's lived experiences and to the assessment of the pedagogical efficacy of the model across contexts.</p>	<p>Redesign of the evaluation instrument</p>
Sustainability	<p>Need to strengthen alignment of the lab with institutional needs and stakeholder priorities: The first PAR cycle revealed the importance of ensuring a better fit between the lab and the specific needs, rhythms, and constraints of the host institutions. The need to systematise the collaborative definition of priorities with key stakeholders and creating structured spaces for co-design was hence defined.</p>	<p>Development of a shared protocol for stakeholder needs assessment.</p>

4.1 Building a Shared Understanding of Learning and Expected Learning Outcomes

To respond to the identified need for establishing a common conception of learning across contexts and to better systematise the competences that the model seeks to scaffold, a significant part of the iteration work focused on the following actions:

- Identification of key learning goals and competences, aligned with the model's pedagogical intentions.
- Design of a validation protocol to co-define and refine these competences in dialogue with participants and key stakeholders.

- Creation of an evaluation rubric based on the identified competences, to support a more structured and transparent assessment process.

In the following sections, we will provide a detailed analysis of these improvements.

4.1.1 Identifying Key Learning Goals and Competences

Following the outcomes and areas for improvements identified in the evaluation of the first PAR cycle and experts' feedback, the consortium decided to more clearly define the specific learning goals and key competences of the model. To define the learning objectives and key competences, we conducted a literature review focused on the development of competences for critical citizenship, alongside a process of integration with the CCLAB model. At the same time, several meetings were held with consortium partners to validate and further develop these proposals. The final outcome was formalized in the following deliverables:

- The definition of eight key competences.
- The development of a protocol to integrate these competences with participants and other stakeholders.
- The creation of an evaluation rubric based on the identified competences.
- The integration of the competences into the evaluation instruments for PAR Cycle 2.

4.1.1.1 The Eight Key Competences

The definition process combined a review of the literature on competences for critical citizenship with the integration of the CCLAB model. As a result, eight key competences were identified: four based on the *Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture* (Council of Europe, 2016), and four developed from the specific characteristics of the CCLAB model. Specifically, the following competences were defined:

- 1. Knowledge and critical understanding of the world.**
- 2. Openness to other beliefs, worldviews and practices.**
- 3. Imaginative and inventive competence.**
- 4. Transformative Agency.**

- 5. **Critical Self-Reflection.**
- 6. **Democratic disposition.**
- 7. **Creative competence.**
- 8. **Research related competence.**

For each competence, a set of related sub-competences was compiled and is presented in the following table. This process of designing and defining the competences was validated through an iterative process during bi-weekly meetings with the consortium.

Table 10. *Identified key competences*

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
<p>Knowledge and Critical Understanding of the World Competence.</p> <p>This competence focuses on actively reflecting on and critically evaluating eco-social issues. It involves identifying tensions, conflicts, and contradictions, assessing the implications of various phenomena, and understanding the historical trajectories that have shaped the current situation. Additionally, it requires recognising the interconnectedness of eco-social challenges and questioning power structures and sources of inequality within them.</p>	<p>Conflict Recognition Competence. Ability to identify conflicts and contradictions in everyday life.</p>
	<p>Critical Assessment Competence. Ability to critically assess the implications of defined phenomena on their everyday experiences and those of their community.</p>
	<p>Historical Analysis Competence. Ability to investigate and understand the historical trajectories that have shaped current situations and issues, linking past events to present conditions.</p>
	<p>Systems Thinking Competence. Capability to recognise and analyse the complex network of interrelated conflicts and contradictions, understanding the interconnected nature of eco-social phenomena.</p>
<p>Openness to Other Beliefs, Worldviews and Practices Competence.</p>	<p>Critical Power Analysis Competence. Ability to identify and critically understand and challenge power relations and sources of inequalities within specific phenomena.</p>
	<p>Bias Identification Competence. Skill in identifying and recognising biases within</p>

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
<p>This competence involves sensitivity to, curiosity about, and a willingness to engage with diverse people and perspectives. It encompasses identifying and recognising biases within different worldviews, understanding and adopting multiple viewpoints, and committing to listening to marginalised voices. It also requires openness and flexibility to revise one's perspectives and opinions when faced with new insights.</p>	<p>various worldviews, including anthropocentrism, eurocentrism, colonialism, and other dominant perspectives.</p>
	<p>Perspective-Taking Competence. Ability to understand, reflect on, appreciate and inhabit multiple, potentially contradictory perspectives and worldviews related to a topic, demonstrating an understanding of diverse viewpoints on a given topic.</p>
	<p>Marginalised Voices Inclusion Competence. Commitment to actively seeking, listening to, and integrating voices that have been marginalised to build a more inclusive understanding of issues.</p>
<p>Imaginative and Inventive Competence. This competence emphasises the ability to envision alternatives beyond existing paradigms. It involves questioning assumptions and accepted norms, exploring unconventional and unestablished possibilities, and engaging with the political and creative potential of "What if?" scenarios. It encourages imagining alternative worlds and futures that transcend current limitations and constraints.</p>	<p>Adaptive Perspective Competence. Openness and flexibility to change one's perspectives and opinions based on new information, understanding, and dialogues with others, demonstrating a willingness to adapt and grow.</p>
	<p>Creative and Critical Inquiry Competence. Ability to explore the political and creative potential of "what if?" questions, using them as tools to imagine alternative scenarios.</p>
	<p>Future Imagination Competence. Skill in imagining possible worlds and futures beyond current constraints, demonstrating the ability to think creatively about alternatives to the present.</p>
<p>Challenging Existing Paradigms Competence. Proficiency in questioning assumptions and accepted norms and thinking about unestablished and unconventional possibilities, fostering critical thinking, innovation, and the ability to disrupt conventional perspectives.</p>	

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
<p>Transformative Agency Competence. This competence focuses on the ability to model new solutions and bring ideas for life change. It involves skills in identifying and articulating clear pathways for justice-oriented change and planning actions to achieve these goals. It includes selecting the most appropriate tools, methods, and resources for effective implementation, adopting a proactive approach, and taking practical steps. Additionally, it emphasises the importance of identifying, fostering, and maintaining collaborations with key stakeholders to work toward shared objectives.</p>	<p>Change Pathway Identification Competence. Ability to identify and articulate clear pathways and planning actions for bringing about justice-oriented change within various contexts.</p>
	<p>Resources and Method Selection Competence. Ability to identify and select the most appropriate tools, methods, and resources to effectively achieve proposed goals.</p>
	<p>Action Initiation Competence. Ability to have a proactive approach and take practical actions that drive meaningful change.</p>
	<p>Collaborative Networking Competence. Capacity to identify, seek, foster, and maintain collaboration with other stakeholders to work towards shared goals and collective actions.</p>
<p>Critical Self-Reflection Competence. This competence involves critically examining one's viewpoints, thoughts, and emotions while recognising inherent biases. It encompasses the capacity to reflect on and evaluate one's learning process, project development, and outcomes. Additionally, it includes the ability to reflect on and understand one's role and agency as an active civic participant.</p>	<p>Knowledge and Critical Understanding of the Self. Ability to critically examine one's own viewpoints, thoughts and emotions, recognise inherent biases, and reflect on how these influence understanding and actions.</p>
	<p>Self-Evaluation Competence. Ability to reflect and critically evaluate one's learning process, project process and project outcomes</p>
	<p>Agency Awareness Competence. Ability to reflect on and understand one's role and agency as an active civic actor, recognising personal responsibilities and contributions within their communities.</p>
<p>Democratic Disposition Competence. This competence focuses on the attitudes and skills needed to foster democratic practices and engage in political participation. It involves the ability to experience, reflect on, and critically engage with the complexities of democracy and cultivate attitudes essential to its</p>	<p>Democratic Reflection Competence. Ability to experience, reflect on, and critically engage with the complexities of democratic practices, understanding the challenges involved.</p>
	<p>Democratic Attitude Competence. Capacity to cultivate attitudes essential to democracy, such as collective decision making, active</p>

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
<p>functioning. Additionally, it includes the proficiency to recognise and assess the presence or absence of democratic values and practices and the ability to advocate for and implement practical strategies that promote and strengthen democratic engagement.</p>	<p>participation, mutual respect, inclusivity, and collaboration.</p>
	<p>Democratic Awareness Competence. Proficiency in recognising and assessing the presence or absence of democratic practices and values within various contexts.</p>
	<p>Democratic Advocacy Competence. Ability to advocate and use practical strategies to promote and reinforce democratic practices in various contexts.</p>
<p>Creative Competence. This competence emphasises using creative and artistic resources to investigate, highlight, and expose tensions, issues, and contradictions across various contexts. It involves employing artistic approaches to make participation and deliberative processes more accessible, fostering collaboration, and facilitating socially engaged initiatives. It also includes the capacity to challenge conventional thinking habits, generate innovative ideas, and leverage creative tools to support and drive transformative processes.</p>	<p>Creative Inquiry of Social Issues. Ability to use creative and artistic resources to investigate, highlight, and make visible tensions, issues, and contradictions in various contexts.</p>
	<p>Creative Approaches for Inclusive Engagement. Skill in employing creative and artistic approaches to make participation and deliberative processes more accessible, inclusive, and engaging for diverse groups.</p>
	<p>Creative Facilitation for Collective Decision-Making. Capacity to utilise creative methods to facilitate collective decision-making and foster collaboration.</p>
	<p>Challenging Norms Through Creative approaches. Capacity in using artistic and creative resources to challenge existing thinking habits and generate novel ideas.</p>
	<p>Creative Facilitation for Community Engagement. Ability to use creative and artistic practices to facilitate socially engaged initiatives, encouraging community involvement and dialogue.</p>
<p>Creative Facilitation for Local transformation. Ability in applying creative and artistic</p>	

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
	resources to support and drive transformative processes within local contexts.
<p>Research Related Competence. This competence focuses on the ability to use research as a tool for transformation. It includes the capacity to identify, articulate, and formulate research questions that are relevant and responsive to community needs and interests. Additionally, it encompasses an understanding of various research approaches and methods, as well as the ability to apply and experiment with participatory research tools to drive meaningful change.</p>	<p>Research Question Formulation Competence. Ability to identify, articulate, and formulate research questions that are relevant and responsive to community needs and interests.</p>
	<p>Research Approaches Competence. Understanding of various research approaches and methods, demonstrating the ability to select appropriate strategies for investigating and understanding specific topics.</p>
	<p>Participatory Research Methods Competence. Proficiency in applying and experimenting with participatory research tools, such as community mapping, photovoice, and participatory workshops, etc. to actively engage communities in the research process.</p>

4.1.2 Designing a Protocol to Validate Competences with Participants and Other Stakeholders

As part of the effort to consolidate CCLAB as a model emerging from a participatory process, a protocol was designed to strengthen the involvement of stakeholders and participants in the model’s design process. Specifically, in this iteration, the focus was placed on engaging stakeholders and participants in validating the competence framework.

For this purpose, the following protocol was developed for use with both educators and young participants. This protocol aimed to explore the relevance, perceived meanings, and priority of the competences through structured, participatory activities. The process was carried out in two main contexts: with stakeholders (educators, facilitators, and institutional actors) and with the young people directly involved in the labs.

1. Validating competences with stakeholders: The protocol applied with stakeholders consisted of three stages:

- **Stage 1. Co-constructing Meaning:** Stakeholders were first introduced to the set of competences through visual cards. Each competence was briefly explained, and stakeholders were invited to reflect on what the competences evoked for them, both conceptually and in relation to their past experiences working with young people. These reflections were recorded directly on large sheets of paper, linking each competence to concrete ideas, projects, or practices.
- **Stage 2. Co-evaluating the Initial Situation:** In this phase, stakeholders were asked to assess the current level of development of each competence among the young people they worked with. This was done using a continuous visual scale (from 0 to 10), where each competence card was placed along the line. The reasoning behind the placements was discussed collectively, allowing for a nuanced understanding of perceived strengths and needs.
- **Stage 3. Identifying Priorities:** Finally, stakeholders were invited to prioritize the competences they considered most relevant for the lab's objectives. This collective exercise served to define a shared focus, grounded in local realities and professional judgment.

2. Validating competences with youth: A parallel version of the protocol was adapted for use with the young participants during the onboarding phase. This version followed the same three stages, with language and facilitation methods tailored to the participants' age and context.

- **Stage 1. Co-constructing Meaning:** Participants were introduced to the competences and asked to explain their personal associations and interpretations. This allowed them to express their initial understanding and to relate the abstract concepts to their own experiences.
- **Stage 2. Self-assessment:** Participants engaged in a self-evaluation activity, placing each competence along a 0–10 scale according to their perceived level of familiarity or confidence.

- Stage 3. Group Prioritization:** In the final stage, participants worked collectively to decide which competences they found most meaningful or necessary to address during the CCLAB process.

The protocol was shared with partners to be implemented in PAR Cycle 2.

4.1.3 Creating an Evaluation Rubric Based on the Identified Competences

In order to support a shared understanding of the competences and to facilitate their observation during the evaluation process by partners, an evaluation rubric was developed. This tool was not intended to guide a numerical or quantitative assessment, but rather to support qualitative field observation. In the following table you can find the outline of the proposed rubrics.

Table 11. Evaluation Rubric Based on the Identified Competences

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
Knowledge and Critical Understanding of the World Competence	Conflict Recognition Competence	Fails to relate identified conflicts to everyday experiences.	Relates identified conflicts to everyday life, but connections are vague or incomplete.	Relates identified conflicts to everyday life with clear, relevant connections.	Expertly relates conflicts to everyday life with deep, relevant, and insightful connections.
	Critical Assessment Competence	Does not assess the implications of phenomena; lacks critical thinking.	Attempts to assess implications but with limited critical analysis or insight.	Critically assesses implications of phenomena with relevant insights and examples.	Demonstrates advanced critical evaluation with thorough, insightful analysis of implications for various contexts.
	Historical Analysis Competence	Unable to identify historical factors influencing current issues.	Identifies some historical factors but lacks clear connection to current issues.	Accurately links historical trajectories to current issues with some understanding of causality.	Thoroughly investigates and understands historical trajectories with a comprehensive link to present conditions.
	Systems Thinking Competence	Does not recognise interrelated conflicts and	Recognises some interrelationships but lacks a	Accurately recognises and analyses interrelationships	Expertly recognises, analyses, and explains complex

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
		contradictions; lacks systemic perspective.	comprehensive or systemic view.	with a systems perspective.	interrelationships with a deep systems perspective.
	Critical Power Analysis Competence	Fails to identify power relations or sources of inequality within phenomena. Does not challenge or critique power relations; lacks critical engagement.	Identifies power relations but lacks depth or critical perspective. Attempts to challenge or critique power relations but lacks depth or specificity.	Identifies and critically analyses power relations and inequalities with some insight. Challenges and critiques power relations with clear and relevant arguments.	Expertly identifies and critically analyses power relations and inequalities with a deep understanding of systemic power dynamics. Deeply challenges and critiques power relations with advanced critical engagement and insightful arguments.
Openness to Other Beliefs, Worldviews and Practices Competence	Bias Identification Competence	Fails to identify or recognise biases in worldviews; lacks understanding of dominant perspectives	Identifies some biases but lacks depth, clarity, or full understanding of their influence.	Accurately identifies various biases (e.g., anthropocentrism, eurocentrism) with clear examples. ☒	Thoroughly identifies and explains biases with nuanced understanding of their impact across multiple contexts.
	Perspective-Taking Competence	Shows limited understanding of multiple perspectives; often sticks to own viewpoint.	Understands multiple perspectives but lacks depth or appreciation for their complexities.	Demonstrates clear understanding and reflection on diverse perspectives with relevant examples.	Demonstrates thorough understanding, reflection, and appreciation of multiple, potentially contradictory perspectives.
	Marginalised Voices Inclusion Competence	Does not seek or include marginalised voices; lacks awareness of their importance.	Includes marginalised voices occasionally but lacks depth or consistency in understanding their importance.	Actively seeks, listens to, and includes marginalised voices with relevant integration into discussions.	Consistently and deeply includes marginalised voices with thorough understanding and integration into broader discussions,

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
					showing a commitment to inclusivity.
	Adaptive Perspective Competence	Shows resistance to changing perspectives or opinions; lacks openness.	Shows some openness to change but struggles to fully adapt or incorporate new information.	Demonstrates openness and flexibility to change perspectives based on new information and dialogue.	Demonstrates advanced openness and flexibility, consistently adapting perspectives with a commitment to growth and learning.
Imaginative and Inventive Competence	Creative and Critical Inquiry Competence	Unable to generate "what if?" questions; minimal creative or critical exploration of scenarios	Generates basic "what if?" questions but with limited depth or creativity.	Generates relevant "what if?" questions that challenge paradigms and explore alternative scenarios.	Generates insightful, politically and creatively potent "what if?" questions that deeply challenge existing paradigms and explore nuanced alternatives.
	Future Imagination Competence	Unable to imagine alternatives to current constraints; thinking is limited to present realities.	Imagines alternatives to the present but lacks depth, creativity, or connection to real-world issues.	Effectively imagines creative, relevant alternative futures that extend beyond present constraints.	Expertly imagines complex, innovative, and compelling alternative futures with clear links to present challenges and opportunities.
	Challenging Existing Paradigms Competence	Remains limited to traditional norms and perspectives; lacks openness to unestablished possibilities and creativity in questioning established ideas	Attempts to transcend traditional norms but lacks depth or consistency in breaking from conventions and thinking beyond established ideas.	Transcends traditional norms, consistently promoting creative and unconventional approaches.	Fully transcends traditional norms, offering deeply creative, unconventional approaches that push the boundaries of established thinking.
Transformative Agency Competence	Change Pathway Identification Competence	Fails to articulate how to achieve	Articulates pathways, but they are not fully	Effectively articulates clear and relevant	Expertly articulates comprehensive,

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
		change; lacks clarity or detail.	developed or practical.	pathways for achieving justice-oriented change.	well-developed pathways for achieving justice-oriented change.
	Resources and Method Selection Competence	Unable to identify resources and methods for achieving goals; lacks understanding of their utility.	Identifies some resources and methods, but they are not fully appropriate or effective.	Effectively identifies appropriate tools, methods, and resources to achieve defined goals.	Expertly selects and integrates the most appropriate tools, methods, and resources with a deep understanding of their effectiveness.
	Action Initiation Competence	Fails to act; lacks initiative or engagement in driving change.	Takes some action but lacks proactivity or consistency in driving meaningful change.	Demonstrates a proactive approach, consistently initiating actions that drive meaningful change.	Demonstrates advanced proactivity, consistently taking bold and strategic actions that drive significant, meaningful change.
	Collaborative Networking Competence	Fails to identify relevant stakeholders for collaboration; lacks awareness of key actors and networks.	Identifies some stakeholders and attempts to seek collaboration but struggles to establish meaningful connections.	Identifies relevant stakeholders and actively seeks for potential collaborators for collective action.	Identifies a broad and diverse range of stakeholders and proactively and effectively seeks and build collaborations with them
Critical Self-Reflection Competence	Knowledge and Critical Understanding of the Self	Lacks awareness or ability to critically examine one's own thoughts, beliefs, or emotions.	Shows limited ability to examine personal viewpoints, recognising some biases but lacking depth.	Critically examines own thoughts, beliefs, and emotions with awareness of inherent biases.	Demonstrates a deep and ongoing examination of personal viewpoints, biases, and how they shape actions and understanding.
	Self-Evaluation Competence	Fails to engage in meaningful self-evaluation; lacks awareness of	Reflects on the process but lacks critical depth or understanding of	Engages in thoughtful self-evaluation, reflecting on	Demonstrates thorough, critical self-evaluation with deep

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
		learning or progress in the project.	personal growth or challenges.	learning, growth, and challenges encountered.	reflection on personal learning, challenges, and progress, leading to growth and improvement.
	Agency Awareness Competence	Lacks awareness of personal role or responsibility as an active civic actor in community or society.	Demonstrates some awareness of personal role in civic actions but lacks full understanding or commitment.	Reflects on personal role and responsibilities as an active civic actor, recognising contributions to community.	Demonstrates deep awareness of personal agency, fully recognising the responsibilities and contributions of one's actions in a community or societal context.
Democratic Disposition Competence	Democratic Reflection Competence	Lacks awareness of the challenges involved in democratic practices.	Shows some awareness of challenges of democratic practices but lacks full understanding or depth in critical reflection.	Understands and reflects on the key challenges of democratic practices.	Demonstrates advanced critical reflection on democratic practices, deeply understanding their complexities and challenges.
	Democratic Attitude Competence	Lacks initiative to participate actively in democratic processes or group activities. Shows minimal respect for others' viewpoints and contributions in group discussions or decision-making.	Participates occasionally but lacks consistency in active engagement. Demonstrates respect for others' views occasionally but may struggle to consistently foster a respectful environment.	Consistently participates actively in democratic processes, contributing ideas and actions. Consistently shows respect for diverse viewpoints and encourages respectful dialogue among participants.	Demonstrates advanced initiative, consistently leading and fostering active participation among all members in democratic processes, fostering an environment of mutual trust and open dialogue.
	Democratic Awareness Competence	Fails to recognise the presence or absence of democratic practices in various contexts.	Demonstrates limited ability to assess democratic practices and values in different contexts.	Recognises and assesses democratic practices and values across different contexts.	Demonstrates advanced ability to critically assess and evaluate the depth, presence, and quality of democratic

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
					practices and values in diverse contexts, with nuanced insights.
	Democratic Advocacy Competence	Does not actively promote or reinforce democratic practices and values within communities.	Uses some resources and strategies but lacks depth or consistency in promoting democratic practices.	Effectively uses resources and strategies to promote and reinforce democratic practices.	Demonstrates advanced proficiency in utilising diverse resources and innovative strategies to consistently promote and reinforce democratic practices.
Creative Competence	Creative Inquiry of Social Issues	Unable to use creative or artistic resources effectively in investigating social issues.	Uses creative or artistic resources to investigate social issues but in a limited or superficial manner.	Employs creative and artistic resources effectively to investigate and illuminate social issues.	Expertly uses diverse creative and artistic methods to deeply investigate and reveal underlying social tensions and contradictions.
	Creative Approaches for Inclusive Engagement	Lacks innovation in creative approaches to engage diverse groups; engagement strategies are traditional or limited.	Demonstrates some creativity in making engagement more accessible but lacks full innovation.	Uses innovative and artistic approaches to enhance engagement, making deliberation more creative and accessible.	Demonstrates advanced creativity in developing and implementing artistic and engaging methods for inclusive participation, ensuring broad, meaningful engagement.
	Creative Facilitation for Collective Decision-Making	Fails to facilitate collective decision-making using creative methods.	Attempts to facilitate decision-making creatively, but the process lacks depth or inclusivity.	Effectively uses creative methods to facilitate collaborative decision-making.	Demonstrates advanced skill in using creative, artistic methods to facilitate inclusive, democratic, and collaborative decision-making.

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
	Challenging Norms Through Creative approaches	Fails to use creative methods to challenge conventional thinking or existing norms.	Uses creative methods to challenge norms but lacks depth or consistency.	Effectively uses creative and artistic methods to challenge existing norms and generate new ideas.	Demonstrates advanced ability to challenge conventional thinking and disrupt established norms through innovative and creative approaches, generating novel ideas and perspectives.
	Creative Facilitation for Community Engagement	Fails to use creative methods to encourage community involvement or dialogue; lacks community connection.	Attempts to facilitate community involvement through creative means, but engagement is limited.	Effectively uses creative and artistic practices to facilitate community engagement and encourage dialogue.	Expertly facilitates community involvement and dialogue through innovative, creative practices, fostering sustained community engagement.
	Creative Facilitation for Local transformation	Fails to use creative or artistic resources to support local transformation; lacks impact or focus.	Uses some creative resources for local transformation but lacks impact and/or alignment with community needs.	Effectively applies creative and artistic resources to drive transformative processes within local contexts.	Demonstrates advanced ability to apply innovative, creative methods to support and drive transformative local change, deeply aligning with community needs and fostering sustainable progress.
Research Related Competence	Research Question Formulation Competence	Research questions are unclear or vague, lacking relevance for community needs.	Research questions are somewhat clear but lack precision or relevance for community needs.	Articulates clear, focused, and precise research questions that are relevant for community needs.	Articulates clear, precise, and highly focused research questions that demonstrate deep engagement with the topic and

Competence		Rubric			
Competence	Sub-dimensions	1. Beginning	2. Developing	3. Proficient	4. Advanced
					community context.
	Research Approaches Competence	Fails to understand or select appropriate research approaches for the topic.	Demonstrates limited understanding of research approaches; selection is sometimes inappropriate.	Demonstrates good understanding of research approaches, selecting appropriate methods for the topic.	Demonstrates advanced understanding of various research approaches, consistently selecting the most effective and relevant methods for the topic.
	Participatory Research Methods Competence	Fails to use or experiment with participatory research tools.	Experiments with some participatory methods, but lacks flexibility or innovation in their application.	Applies participatory methods effectively, with some experimentation to meet the needs of the community.	Demonstrates advanced experimentation with a variety of participatory methods, adapting approaches creatively to foster active, meaningful community involvement.

As part of the process, the evaluation instruments were redesigned to allow for the integration of the competences into the assessment framework and ensure that the competences could be meaningfully observed and documented throughout the labs activities. Further details on this integration are provided in Section 4.1.5.

4.2 Supporting a Stronger Understanding of Youth’s Perceptions of Eco-social Phenomena, Democracy, and Agency

The first evaluation process showed certain limitations in capturing participants’ situated perspectives and conceptions of the issues under consideration. Given the importance of grounding the labs in topics that resonate with young people’s lived experiences, UB identified the need for a deeper understanding of how young people perceive eco-social

issues, democracy, and their own agency. To this end, a set of targeted actions was implemented. These included the improvement of evaluation instruments to better capture young people's conceptualizations and experiences (see section 4.3), as well as the training of facilitators involved in the evaluation process, equipping them with tools and strategies to elicit meaningful reflections, as well as identify and report key challenges faced by participants. These trainings were carried out as part of the Community of Practice (CoP) meetings. The CoP meetings brought together project partners to exchange knowledge and improve practices. It was also open to external stakeholders and guest presentations that enriched the group's work. A detailed description of CoP is available in D2.1 (Report: Critical Changelab Cycle 2).

4.3 Redesigning of the Evaluation Instruments

The redesign of the evaluation instruments responded to two main needs. On the one hand, the need emerged to align more closely with the abovementioned competence framework, integrating the set of targeted competences directly into the observation and documentation process. This shift aimed at allowing for a more coherent and intentional approach, in which evaluation was not only reflective of participants' experiences but also served to trace their learning and transformation in relation to the model's pedagogical goals. On the other, it responded to the need for a deeper understanding of how young people perceive eco-social issues, democracy, and their own agency. In this sense, a central objective of this iteration was to ensure that the evaluation tools could meaningfully capture young people's conceptualizations, lived experiences, and evolving competences in contextually diverse settings.

To this end the evaluation approach within the CCLAB model was significantly revised during the second PAR cycle. One of the key changes was the redesign of the researchers' diaries, which were completed collaboratively by local teams after each session. While researchers considered them useful for internal reflection during the first cycle, the original format was often seen as repetitive and not sufficiently analytical. The updated version streamlined the structure and introduced the Critical Incident Technique (CIT) as its core evaluative lens. The idea of a Critical Incident (CI) is rooted in the work of Flanagan (1954), who defined it as a specific, observable event that has a significant impact on the outcome of an activity. According to Kreps (2018), a CI is meaningful because it signals a turning point, challenge, or breakthrough in the process being studied. In the context of the second PAR

cycle, the focus on Critical Incidents enabled researchers to pay close attention to significant learning moments, conflicts, and transformations, making it a valuable ethnographic tool.

In each session, researchers were invited to document CIs only when relevant, providing detailed descriptions to ensure that the incidents could be thoroughly analysed. The documentation guidelines emphasised capturing both positive developments—such as breakthroughs in learning or collaboration—and challenging moments—such as tensions, resistance, or misunderstandings.

Researchers were instructed to focus their attention on the following areas of competence development:

- 1. Critical Understanding of the World** (e.g., Evidence of learning or struggle in understanding specific phenomena; Identification of everyday contradictions and historical interrelations; Recognition of power dynamics and inequalities).
- 2. Openness to Other Beliefs, Worldviews, and Practices** (e.g., Reflection on multiple perspectives and biases; Openness to revise one's views or listen to marginalised voices).
- 3. Imaginative and Inventive Skills** (e.g., Use of the "What if?" question to challenge norms; Creative envisioning of alternative futures or possibilities).
- 4. Transformative Agency** (e.g., Ability to move from ideas to actions; Collective goal setting and planning for change; Engagement in collaborative processes for transformation).
- 5. Critical Self-Reflection** (e.g., Examination of personal views, biases, and learning processes; Reflection on civic roles and agency).
- 6. Democratic Disposition** (e.g., Recognition of democratic values in context, Promotion of democratic attitudes and practices)
- 7. Creative Competences** (e.g., Use of artistic methods to support analysis, participation, or engagement).

8. **Research Competences** (e.g., Capacity to articulate relevant questions and understand research approaches, Use of research as a tool for transformation).
9. **Conflicts and Tensions** (e.g., Identification of interpersonal or structural tensions that affected the process).

Additionally, less effective tools, such as “quick and dirty” assessments that lacked depth and contextual sensitivity, were discontinued. In contrast, final interviews and focus groups with youth and educators were retained and improved, incorporating prompts based on the competence framework to foster more focused and meaningful reflection. These instruments offered further insight into how young people interpreted their experiences and growth throughout the CCLAB process.

Finally, to support consistent and critical application of the new tools, facilitators were trained in the use of the revised instruments during CoP meetings. This included strategies for identifying significant learning moments, eliciting nuanced reflections, and interpreting participant responses in relation to the competence framework.

The evaluation instruments used for PAR Cycle 2 are available in Annex 1.

4.4 Improving, Systematising and Documenting the Model’s Methodological Strategies

The evaluation of the first iteration highlighted the need to strengthen the methodological approach of the model, as well as to systematically document, organise, and evaluate the methods employed. To address this, several actions were undertaken. First, recurrent meetings were organised with the Community of Practice to support shared reflection on the methods used. These meetings provided a structured space for practitioners to discuss challenges, share experiences, and collaboratively identify opportunities for improving the design and implementation of activities. Second, in response to systematise the model’s methodological richness and assess the impact of specific pedagogical strategies, a standardized template was designed to capture and document the diverse methodological practices applied across different contexts.

Specifically, partners were asked to complete the following template for each method employed during the different sections of the labs (see Table 12).

Table 12. *Template to Systematise Methods Collection and Evaluation.*

Method	
Name	
<p>General Learning Goal. Specify which CCLAB competences the method addresses. You may choose more than one if applicable.</p>	<p>Knowledge and critical understanding of the world competence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness to other beliefs, worldviews and practices competences • Imaginative and inventive competences • Transformative Agency competences • Critical Self- Reflection competences • Democratic disposition competences • Creative competences • Research related competences
<p>Specific Learning Goals. Indicate specific learning goals of the method, if applicable.</p>	
<p>Steps. Provide a short step-by-step description of the method.</p>	
<p>Participation. On a scale of 0 to 5 (0 being the lowest and 5 the highest), how effectively did the method support participation through various means (e.g., oral contributions, written responses, drawings, etc.)?</p>	
<p>Objective Achievement. On a scale of 0 to 5 (0 being the lowest and 5 the highest), how successfully did the method achieve its intended goal?</p>	

Additionally, the evaluation focus for the second PAR cycle was refined to include explicitly the identification and analysis of the effectiveness and limitations of these various methods,

enabling a clearer understanding of which approaches best support the model's learning objectives.

4.5 Developing and Validating a Shared Protocol for Stakeholder Needs Assessment

To systematise the collaborative definition of priorities with key stakeholders and creating structured spaces for co-design, a unified protocol for the stakeholder needs assessment was developed to be implemented with all partners. This shared framework aimed to guide conversations with key stakeholders (e.g., educators, community leaders, and institutional actors) regarding the needs, priorities, and existing work related to the CCLABs core themes. The protocol was structured around four main areas of inquiry:

- 1. Experience and Past Work:** Stakeholders were first invited to reflect on their previous experiences working with the group of young people. Guiding questions included:
 - What issues have you worked on as a group in relation to eco-social conflicts?
 - What issues have you worked on in relation to democratic practices and values?
 - Has this group carried out any community-related projects?
- 2. Relevant Topics:** Participants were then asked to identify the topics they considered most important to address with the group, and to explain why these were relevant in the current context.
- 3. Competences:** This section focused on the key competences defined in the CCLAB model. Stakeholders were asked:
 - Which of these competences have you already worked on with this group?
 - Which competences do you believe are priorities for this group?
 - Which competences should the CCLAB focus on?

4. Expectations: Finally, stakeholders were encouraged to share their expectations for the ChangeLab, including the potential long-term or systemic impact of the initiative. Questions included:

- What expectations do you have for the Critical ChangeLab?
- How do you think the ChangeLab can have an impact beyond the programme?

Each assessment meeting included a documentation phase in which the following aspects were reported:

- The identity and role of the stakeholders involved.
- Their relationship with the group of young people.
- A summary of their responses to the key questions.

5. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 2

5.1 Description of the Labs and KPIs

A total of **18** Critical ChangeLabs were implemented during PAR Cycle 2 across eleven countries (Table 13): Finland (OULU), Spain (UB), Ireland (TCD), the Netherlands (Waag), Austria (Ars Electronica), Slovenia (KI), France (EUROALTER), French Guiana (EUROALTER), Italy (EUROALTER), Greece (LATRA), and Croatia (ISRZ). This PAR cycle reached about **843** young people who participated in the Labs.

Table 13. Overview of PAR Cycle 2 labs.

Partner	Lab	Location	N. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
Trinity College Dublin	CrossCare	Arklow, Wicklow, Ireland	7	Climate Action, focused on local river	15 participants (3 male and 12 female), aged 14–18
Trinity College Dublin	Design Your Future City	Dublin, Ireland	5	Future of Dublin with focus on sustainability	18 participants, all aged 15–16 (gender data not disaggregated)
University of Oulu	Growing up with social media: Kastelli school	Oulu, Finland	8	Online wellbeing and digital empathy	43 participants, aged 12–14. Group A: 25 students (10 female, 15 male). Group B: 18 students (10 male, 8 female)
University of Oulu	Growing up with social media: Norssi school	Oulu, Finland	7	UNESCO-aligned social themes in social media	21 participants (11 male, 10 female) ages 12–14
European Alternatives	Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni	Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni, French Guiana	2	Food, fishing, and environmental access	85 participants aged between 11–14 (gender data not disaggregated)

Partner	Lab	Location	N. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
European Alternatives	Lycée Michel-Ange	Villeneuve La Garenne, France	2	Artificial intelligence and social media	18 participants aged 17 years old (gender data not disaggregated)
European Alternatives	Palermo (Exploratory Lab)	Palermo, Italy	2	Human-animal relations and ecology	10 participants aged 3–11 (gender data not disaggregated)
LATRA	Loutra Elementary School	Lesvos, Greece	12	Democracy, inclusion, and community via theatre	394 participants (gender data not disaggregated)
Institute for Social Research	School Dormitory Dora Pejačević	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Youth mental health and educational inequality	14 female participants aged 15–18
Institute for Social Research	School Dormitory Novi Zagreb	Zagreb, Croatia	8	Stigma and invisibility of dormitory students	14 participants aged 15–18 (gender data not disaggregated)
Institute for Social Research	School Dormitory Marija Jambrišak	Zagreb, Croatia	8	Inequality in secondary school enrolment	15 female participants aged 17–19
Ars Electronica	Open Lab - Create your World	Linz, Austria	6	Imagining futures, social tech impact and mental health	12 participants aged 14–18 (gender data not disaggregated)
Ars Electronica	HTL Spengergasse	Vienna, Austria	5	Human rights, discrimination, and climate change	29 participants aged 17–18 (gender data not disaggregated)
Kersnikova	Center Rog	Ljubljana, Slovenia	8	STEAM, digital governance, civic engagement	10 participants aged 11–15 (gender data not disaggregated)
Waag Futurelab	Corderius College	Amersfoort, Netherlands	3	Identity, relations, and racism	100 students aged 15–17 (gender data not disaggregated)

Partner	Lab	Location	N. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
University of Barcelona	BAU	Barcelona, Spain	7	Lack of affective responsibility in society	26 participants (22 female, 4 male) aged 17–18
University of Barcelona	Vapor Moli	Barcelona, Spain	7	Seven youth-defined topics incl. racism, safety, rent	25 participants aged 15 (gender data not disaggregated)
University of Barcelona	Can Fabra	Barcelona, Spain	9	Lack of care toward others (humans and non-humans)	9 participants aged 12–14 (gender data not disaggregated)

Additionally, 9 external labs were coordinated by Tactical Tech (TT) and carried out with the following collaborators: Sofia Professional School “Knyaginia Evdokia” (Bulgaria), 2nd Farnham Scout (UK), 105 VIERTEL HAMBURG GmbH (Germany), Televele Media Education Association (Hungary), LINKS Foundation (Italy), Ciência Viva (Portugal), Colegiul Național Costache Negruzzi (Romania), Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade (Serbia) and Teyit (Turkey). These external labs are not included in this report due to the absence of a consortium researcher in the labs and therefore a lack on evaluation data.

Since the detailed description of each lab has already been reported in the Deliverable 2.1, the following section only provides general descriptions of the internal labs conducted to contextualize the evaluation process.

Lab #1 (TCD – CrossCare): In Arklow, Ireland, a lab focused on climate action was conducted over seven sessions, led by Trinity College Dublin in partnership with CrossCare Ireland. Approximately 15 young participants, primarily female (around 12 girls and 3 boys), aged 14–18, took part. The lab engaged members of the Monday Mixers and LGBTQI+ afterschool youth groups. Through a participatory approach, the group explored climate action, ultimately narrowing their focus to the local river. The theme was collaboratively chosen based on the educator’s insights and ongoing work with the youth.

Lab #2 (TCD – Design Your Future City): The Design Your Future City (DYFC) lab took place in Dublin, Ireland. 18 young people (9 male, 9 female), all aged 15–16 and in their Transition Year of school, took part in the five-day lab. The lab was part of the Trinity Climate Action

and Biodiversity Week and was hosted by the Academy of the Near Future in collaboration with TCD.

Lab #3 (OULU – Kastelli school): In Oulu, Finland, 43 seventh-grade students (25 boys and 18 girls, aged 12–14) from Kastelli school participated in two parallel labs as part of their ICT compulsory course. Across eight sessions, the labs focused on online wellbeing, empathy, digital collaboration, and responsible use of social media. The initiative was linked to the *Oulu Loves Me* campaign, promoting anti-racism and social inclusion.

Lab #4 (OULU – Norssi school): In Oulu, Finland, 21 seventh-grade students (11 boys and 10 girls, aged 12–14), many with migrant backgrounds and multilingual family contexts, participated in a seven-session lab at Norssi school. As part of their Intercultural Competence Training (MOK) course, aligned with the Finnish national curriculum's emphasis on phenomenon-based learning, the lab addressed themes like tolerance, democracy, and sustainable development through the lens of social media interactions. The lab was conducted in collaboration with the University of Oulu and the Designing for Children's Rights (D4CR) association.

Lab #5 (EUROALTER – Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni): The lab took place in Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni, French Guiana with 85 students aged 11–14. The Lab was facilitated by Fondazione Studio Rizoma in collaboration with a local art teacher. During three sessions they focused on themes of food, fishing, the environment, and access to food in aquatic areas.

Lab #6 (EUROALTER – Lycée Michel-Ange): At Lycée Michel-Ange in Villeneuve La Garenne, France, 18 students aged 17 years old, with no prior experience in eco-social issues participated in a two-session lab on AI and social media. Facilitated by European Alternatives with a teacher and educator, the lab provided a space to critically examine AI's opportunities and risks through debates and creative activities. The sessions aimed to develop key competencies—critical understanding of the world, democratic disposition, imaginative thinking, and transformative agency—while drawing on students' lived experiences in their suburban context. Teacher involvement was essential in enabling participation.

Lab #7 (EUROALTER – Palermo [Exploratory Lab]): At Ex-Cinema Edison in Palermo, Italy, Corrente Associazione conducted an exploratory lab with children aged 3–11, younger than the typical 11–18 target group. This pilot adapted the methodology in two keyways: using

documentary and participant-made films as reflective prompts, and tailoring activities for isolated underage migrants unable to attend multiple sessions. The lab –focused on themes like environment, displacement, and democracy– served as a prototype for future CCLABs planned with disadvantaged youth in Palermo and Paris.¹

Lab #8 (LATRA – Loutra Elementary School): In Loutra, Mytilene, a lab at the local elementary school brought together Greek and refugee students to explore democracy, inclusion, and fairness through twelve interactive sessions using theatre, role-play, and discussion. The lab aimed to bridge social and cultural divides in a community where local and refugee children had little prior interaction. Through collaborative and creative methods, facilitators helped participants gradually break down barriers, challenging preconceptions and fostering a deeper understanding of power, representation, and shared community life.

Lab #9 (ISRZ – UDDP): The lab at Zagreb’s Dora Pejačević Student Dormitory (UDDP) engaged high school girls (ages 15–18) from across Croatia in a seven-session inquiry into educational inequalities, with a focus on mental health. Despite differing ages and academic backgrounds, the group demonstrated strong cohesion and a shared openness to complex topics. Educators observed that while older participants were initially more confident, the supportive, dynamic environment encouraged increasing involvement from younger students, who benefited from peer guidance throughout the process.

Lab #10 (ISRZ – UDNZ): The lab at the Student Dormitory Novi Zagreb (UDNZ) engaged a mixed gender group of upper secondary students in examining gender inequalities in education. Over eight sessions, ISRZ employed interactive methods like structured debates, role-playing, and creative exercises to prompt critical analysis and self-reflection. The process facilitated a shift in understanding: participants progressed from seeing challenges as personal failures to analysing them as outcomes of systemic structures. Engaging in exercises designed to explore alternative viewpoints was crucial in developing this more nuanced, systemic awareness and a greater openness to others’ experiences.

Lab #11 (ISRZ – UDMJ): At Student Dormitory Marija Jambrišak (UDMJ), 15 upper secondary students examined the equity of enrolment practices in Croatia’s educational transition, a

¹ The outcomes of this lab were excluded from the analysis due to the participants’ age range being younger than that of the other labs.

pivotal moment where students enter differentiated academic or vocational tracks. While enrolment is primarily merit-based, bonus points are awarded for various achievements and other socio-economic circumstances. Initially, most participants viewed these policies as individually unfair and inequality-reinforcing. However, through eight sessions involving policy analysis, debates, role-play, and creative exercises which included creating a theatre play with community actors, students developed critical and reflective insights into the structural dimensions of educational justice.

Lab #12 (AE - Open Lab): During the 2024 Ars Electronica Festival in Linz, Austria, a five-day lab engaged twelve youth participants (aged 14–18) with the theme "Hope: Who Will Turn the Tide?". The lab fostered creative, technology-driven explorations of future societal visions. Participants were recruited through the Jugendbegegnungsprojekt youth exchange and the festival's existing "Create your World" initiative, forming a diverse cohort with varying prior exposure to the festival's context. The programme centred on using media and technology to critically and imaginatively address societal issues.

Lab #13 (AE - HTL Spengergasse): The lab at Vienna's HTL Spengergasse engaged 29 students in the "Envisioning Futures" theme as part of their media curriculum. Through five sessions involving discussion, interviews, and creative production, students developed podcasts exploring their capacity for societal influence. The lab integrated democratic engagement, research, and creative expression. Although participation was mandatory, a pre-workshop survey indicated strong student interest in social issues, and prior collaborative experience with socially engaged projects provided a solid foundation for their active involvement in the research and production process.

Lab #14 (KI - Center Rog): An eight-week lab at Ljubljana's Center Rog, organised by Zavod Kersnikova and Društvo Rampa, engaged adolescents (ages 11–15) in exploring the intersection of democracy and technology. The cohort, primarily from middle-class backgrounds with some participants from systemically minoritized groups, generally had limited prior critical engagement with technology's role in governance. Through weekly Friday sessions involving hands-on activities, debate, and creative problem-solving, the lab fostered new understandings of technological literacy and participatory democratic processes.

Lab #15 (WAAG - Corderius College): At Corderius College in Amersfoort, approximately 70 pre-vocational (VMBO) students participated in a lab integrated into their final-year

curriculum. Facilitated by Waag Futurelab, this three-session intervention addressed themes of identity, democracy, and creative expression through interactive pedagogical methods. Although participation was mandatory, facilitators, including philosophy teachers and external experts, sought to cultivate student engagement by employing creative and discussion-based activities designed to stimulate reflection and critical discourse.

Lab #16 (UB - BAU): A lab was implemented within the curriculum for first-year design students at BAU College of Arts and Design to investigate affective responsibility. Through a structured series of six interactive sessions, the lab facilitated the development of key academic and civic competences –including research, critical thinking, and creative expression– to promote critical reflection and democratic engagement among participants.

Lab #17 (UB - Vapor Moli): This lab was conducted at Institut Escola Vapor Molí, a public primary and secondary school in Barcelona's Sant Andreu district. The cohort consisted of 25 fourth-year secondary education students, selected by three teachers based on their identified need for pedagogical intervention. This need arose from the students' inability to meet the learning objectives of a prior activity requiring them to identify an eco-social issue, connect it to a Sustainable Development Goal, and develop a transformation proposal, a task closely resembling the structure of a CCLAB.

Lab #18 (UB - Can Fabra): This lab took place as an extracurricular initiative in Barcelona's Library Ignasi Iglesias-Can Fabra maker space and engaged a core group of 4–6 adolescents (from an initial nine registrants). The lab's focus emerged directly from participant-identified concerns, such as pollution and injustice, which consistently highlighted a theme of widespread societal apathy. This led to the lab's central research question: examining the prevalent disinterest people show toward others, both human and non-human.

5.2 Evaluation Approach, Methods, and Instruments

Following the model adopted in PAR Cycle 1 and the redesign carried out after this first iteration, the evaluation process in PAR Cycle 2 was structured around three main instruments:

1. The revised version of the researchers' diaries, used to compile evidence of what occurred during the lab sessions (see Section 4.3).
2. The final focus group with participants (see Section 4.3).
3. The final interviews with educators (see Section 4.3).

For this second stage, the evaluation approach took a less explorative approach and focuses specifically on the following aspects:

- Exploring how young people understand eco-social phenomena, democracy, and their own agency.
- Assessing the pedagogical effectiveness of the CCLAB model.
- Analysing the strengths and weaknesses of the methods used.
- Reflecting on the model's strengths and limitations.

To address the defined evaluation goals of the CCLAB model implemented during PAR Cycle 2, a cross-cutting analysis of the reports produced in each of the labs was carried out by a team of three researchers. This analysis focused on a total of 18 evaluation reports, each corresponding to a different local CCLAB conducted as part of the PAR cycle.

The researchers employed a thematic analysis approach, using the software Atlas.ti to support the coding, organization, and interpretation of qualitative data. Each report was systematically reviewed and coded according to a combination of top-down and bottom-up categorization strategies.

- The top-down approach was guided by a predefined framework of key competences, as established in the design of the evaluation instruments (e.g., critical understanding of the world, imaginative competences, transformative agency, democratic disposition, etc.). This allowed the researchers to trace how each competence was represented across different contexts and sessions.
- The bottom-up approach enabled the identification of emergent themes and patterns grounded in the data itself, beyond the original framework.

Through this process, recurring strengths and limitations of the model became visible, both in relation to the facilitation of competences and the overall structure of the labs.

In the following sections, we present key outcomes of this cross-cutting analysis, as well as a set of evidence-based recommendations that guided the ongoing development and refinement of the CCLAB model for PAR Cycle 3.

5.3 Outcomes of the Cross-Cutting Analysis of PAR Cycle 2

The following section presents the key findings that emerged from the cross-cutting analysis of the evaluation reports, organised into three main thematic areas. This structure has been designed to capture both the conceptual and pedagogical dimensions of the labs, as well as reflect on the methodological choices that shaped their implementation. Each thematic area is composed of sub-sections that offer a more detailed account of specific outcomes.

1. Exploring how young people understand eco-social phenomena, democracy, and their own agency: This section explores how the labs served as valuable entry points to better understand how young people perceive and relate to the notion of active citizenship. Drawing on the evidence collected through Critical Incidents, interviews, and focus groups, the analysis is organised around three key axes:

- Youth's ways of understanding contemporary eco-social issues: Insights into how participants perceive and make sense of pressing global and local challenges.
- Youth's ways of understanding and doing democracy: A focus on how young people conceptualise democratic values, practices, and institutions, as well as their engagement—or lack thereof—with democratic processes.
- Youth's ways of understanding their role in transforming and changing society: Reflections on how participants view their agency and capacity to contribute to societal transformation, including the obstacles and opportunities they perceive.

2. The pedagogical effectiveness of the labs: This section examines the extent to which the labs contributed to meaningful changes in participants' knowledge,

attitudes, and competences. It evaluates the pedagogical impact of the experience along the same three axes outlined above, but with a specific focus on observable shifts and developments that occurred throughout the process:

- Changes in youth's ways of understanding contemporary eco-social issues.
- Changes in youth's ways of understanding and doing democracy.
- Changes in youth's ways of understanding their role in transforming and changing society.

3. Analysing methodological choices: This section critically reflects on the methodological and pedagogical tools used during the labs, evaluating their effectiveness, relevance, and limitations. This includes a review of:

- The use of art-based methods.
- The use of participatory research methods.
- The use of debate and dialogue-based methods.
- Strategies to connect with outside the institution.
- Strength and weaknesses of the methodological approach.

4. Reflecting on the model's limitations: This section critically reflects on the CCLAB model to identify key areas of improvement to be implemented in PAR Cycle 3. This includes a review of:

- Evaluation of the competence framework
- Feedback on the evaluation instruments

5.3.1 Exploring How Young People Understand Eco-social Phenomena, Democracy, and Their Own Agency

This section explores how the labs served as valuable entry points to better understand how young people perceive and relate to the notion of active citizenship.

5.3.1.1 Youth's Ways of Understanding Contemporary Eco-social Issues

This section presents key insights into how young people engage with and make sense of contemporary eco-social phenomena, drawing on data collected from the diverse educational settings across labs. At the same time, it highlights a number of challenges in how young people understand these complex phenomena. In the following sections, we will explore these dimensions in greater depth, offering a broader analysis that can inform the development of specific pedagogical recommendations aimed at addressing these issues.

5.3.1.1.1 Youth's Worries About Contemporary Eco-social Issues

Overall, CCLABs provided a privileged lens into the contemporary concerns of the young participants. Through the different labs, a range of pressing issues emerged as particularly relevant for them, including climate change, sustainability, well-being, the impact of social media, inclusion, mental health, inequality, discrimination, racism, gender discrimination, safety, and a perceived lack of care in interpersonal and societal relationships.

The participants expressed a strong emotional connection to their immediate environment and a deep sense of being affected by what happens around them, especially when the effects are tangible and visible. However, this awareness was often accompanied by a sense of powerlessness regarding their capacity to act meaningfully on these issues. Many reported feeling that their perspectives are often dismissed or ignored by adults, particularly when it comes to matters that directly concern them.

Closely related to these experiences, a recurring theme was the rejection of narratives that blame young people for current global crises, as well as a resistance to catastrophic or fear-based discourses. For instance, during the DYFC lab (TCD), students openly challenged the dominant "doom and gloom" tone frequently associated with climate change communication. They noted that emphasizing distant and apocalyptic consequences weakened their emotional connection to the issue and diminished their motivation to engage. Similarly, at the Open Lab (AE), participants responded most positively to discussions and activities that imagined hopeful, alternative futures. These examples suggest that young people are not indifferent to eco-social challenges, but that they are more responsive to constructive, imaginative, and empowering narratives.

5.3.1.1.2 Relevance of the Local and Situated

In general, students exhibit a more explicit interest in topics that directly impact their everyday lives, including their family, school, or community environments. There is a clear

tendency to prioritize local issues—perceived as immediate and relevant—over global challenges that are distant in time and space.

This local orientation was particularly evident in the CrossCare lab (TCD), where focusing on a nearby river enabled participants to contextualize climate change through a grounded, place-based perspective. Students reported that this territorial anchoring fostered stronger emotional and cognitive engagement with the topic. They noted that they were more likely to care about issues occurring in their immediate surroundings than about abstract or distant global concerns. A similar logic emerged in Design your City (TCD), where discussion groups appreciated the programme’s emphasis on feasible, local or domestic actions, rather than overwhelming global problems perceived as beyond individual reach. As one student expressed: “It’s way easier to care about something when it’s in front of your face, than 100 miles away.”

In parallel, specific concerns related to identity and vulnerability also emerged. LGBTQ+ student groups, in particular, voiced anxiety regarding their safety and well-being. Other key issues included sexism, emotional responsibility, and misinformation—topics that directly affect students’ daily lives and elicit significant concern. Examples of them can be found in the Can Fabra lab (UB), where students decide to focus on the injustices they perceive in their school environment. Similarly, in the UDMJ (ISRZ) lab, which focused on inequality in education, students decide to address their direct experiences related to access to upper secondary education. Participants also showed a remarkable knowledge regarding the inner workings of algorithms of their usual social networks. Considering that for the young generations these online platforms are considered a main source of socialization, it is noteworthy that they took on the task to rethink how to make these spaces safe and inclusive for everyone. This was particularly evident in the Kastelli (OULU) lab where the process helped participants become aware of the array of issues that can occur in different online experiences.

These observations point to the critical importance of rooting CCLABs in students’ lived realities. When young people are invited to engage with topics that intersect directly with their identities, environments, and daily experiences, their involvement deepens, and their sense of agency grows. This suggests the need for designing experiences that connect global challenges to local contexts, and that validate the perspectives and expertise young people bring from their own lives.

5.3.1.1.3 Difficulties in Connecting the Personal and the Social

In some settings, there was a noticeable tendency to focus on individual experiences rather than collective or systemic reflections. This dynamic was evident in the case of Can Fabra (UB), where students frequently centred on highly specific personal experiences, such as feelings of unfairness when peers received higher grades without apparent effort, or annoyance over littering in public spaces. The school educator expressed surprise at the group's low level of social awareness, noting that students often appeared disconnected from broader social issues. According to her account, when students did engage with an issue, they either approached it from a strictly individualistic lens or referenced abstract, distant ideals, such as "world peace", without engaging with more tangible, intermediate layers of social reality.

Similarly, in the UNDZ lab (ISRZ) researchers reported that participants tended to build their understandings of eco-social issues based on their own experience and the experiences of their friends and families and struggled to identify educational inequities based on concrete experiences. In this sense, researchers observed that they often take an individualistic perspective and believe that outcomes depend on the qualities of the individual, as well as that anyone can achieve anything if they want it and make an effort. They generally overlook the significance of privileges and disadvantages that arise from established social structures and relationships.

Similarly, at Lycée Michel-Ange (EUROALTER), students demonstrated interest in the topic of AI's impact on their daily lives, though their focus remained narrowly centred on its perceived effects on their learning behaviours, expressing particularly concerns about long-term reduced effort due to an increasing dependency on the technology.

These difficulties in building connections between broader social issues and personal or everyday experiences was also present when students were prompted to work from general issues to personal experiences. For instance, at Norssi school (OULU), students had trouble connecting concepts such as racism or bullying to their own lives. A key component of this project was "Researcher ID: All of Us Are Researchers!", where students collected social media screenshots illustrating digital issues like bullying, misinformation, and appearance-related pressures. They uploaded their findings and wrote brief reflections. While some engaged deeply, others found it difficult to relate their research to personal experiences. Facilitators noted that while students could analyse public online behaviours, they were

hesitant to share or reflect on their own experiences, often framing the discussion in a detached, analytical tone.

Likewise, at Kastelli school (OULU), conversations about media influence revealed a disconnect between students' awareness of risks and their personal investment in the topic. While acknowledging potential dangers of social media, it remained unclear to what extent students felt personally affected or concerned.

This evidence points out the need for strategies that enable students to create bridges between individual concerns and inequalities with structural issues and understand themselves as part of broader and more complex systems.

5.3.1.1.4 Difficulties Understanding the Complexity of Contemporary Social Phenomena

Closely related to the previous aspect, another challenge identified was students' difficulty in grasping the interconnected and systemic nature of social issues. In settings like Can Fabra (UB) and CrossCare (TCD), students often approached problems in reductive ways, focusing on isolated behaviours rather than broader dynamics.

At UB Can Fabra, students struggled to understand how different actors and behaviours contribute to social phenomena. When discussing pollution, they only mentioned littering or smoking, overlooking more significant sources of environmental harm. At CrossCare (TCD), a disconnect emerged between individual actions and their broader impact, with students finding it hard to see how their choices linked to larger-scale issues.

At Spengergasse (AE) students succeeded in identifying important issues regarding human rights violations or state control but framed them as problems that happen substantially outside the EU, thus exhibiting a Eurocentric approach. In that sense they failed to recognise subtler forms of democratic erosion such as racial profiling, digital surveillance or biometric data collection, all of which happens within EU borders. Students thus revealed themselves as dislodged observers of global issues rather than situated participants in interconnected struggles.

In conclusion, these findings highlight a common challenge among students in recognising the interconnected and systemic nature of social and eco-social issues, whether through a narrow focus on isolated behaviours, a limited geographic perspective, or a disconnection

from the structural roots of problems. This suggests a need for approaches that provide conceptual and practical tools to navigate the complex entanglement of contemporary issues, instead of trying to reduce them to issues that can be tackled from a reductionist point of view.

5.3.1.1.5 Resistance to Reflection

As in PAR Cycle 1, as well as in this second iteration, students in several settings showed a certain reluctance to deeply engage in critical reflection on social issues. In many labs, researchers reported a lack of motivation to participate in activities involving deliberation, decision-making, or self-reflection.

This resistance was particularly pronounced at Can Fabra (UB), where students explicitly expressed a preference for action-oriented tasks over reflective processes. One emblematic comment was: "I don't want to think; I just want to do what you tell me." The educator confirmed this tendency, highlighting that one of the lab's main challenges was fostering engagement and encouraging active participation. Many students found activities requiring critical thinking boring or uninteresting. According to the educator, this may be linked to students' expectations that, since the programme was held in a makerspace and outside of regular school hours, the focus would be solely on technological tinkering, without reflective components. Furthermore, the pedagogical sequence - thinking before doing - was a significant challenge for the group, which added to their resistance to reflect or immerse themselves in social issues. In discussion groups, students themselves admitted that reflective sessions felt obligatory and dull, and they did not view them as an essential part of the process.

A similar resistance was noted in the HTL Spengergasse lab (AE), where participants struggled with self-assessment and showed discomfort with exercises that required them to think critically about their own work. At Corderius College (WAAG), educators also observed that discussion spaces were perceived as unattractive by students, and that encouraging dialogue and peer reflection was one of the lab's major challenges. Additionally, a recurring obstacle across multiple sites was the lack of continuity between sessions. Researchers observed that students often forgot previous discussions, making it difficult to build sustained, meaningful learning over time.

This evidence suggests a resistance toward certain kinds of reflective practices that appears to be tied not only to students' preferences for more action-oriented, hands-on activities but also to their expectations about the nature of the programmes and the perceived relevance of reflective practices. In this sense, further reflection should be devoted to rethinking how deliberative and reflective practices can be framed in a way that better aligns with students' ways of constructing knowledge.

5.3.1.2 Youth's Ways of Understanding and Doing Democracy

This section presents key insights into how young people understand and do democracy, drawing on data collected from diverse educational settings across PAR cycle 2. Furthermore, key tensions and challenges in youth's ways of understanding democracy are highlighted, in order to inform recommendations for practitioners.

5.3.1.2.1 Speaking About Democracy VS Enacting Democracy

Across most of the analysed labs, students demonstrated widespread difficulty in understanding and using the concept of democracy. A common thread across different contexts was a general sense of dissatisfaction with how current democratic systems function. These perspectives go along with a clear antipathy that many students expressed toward politics and a general distrust of institutional democratic systems. A significant number of participants frequently stated that they do not trust politicians and are not interested in politics, which contributes to their detachment from the concept of democracy itself.

Broadly speaking, democracy tended to be understood in a narrow way, mainly associated with institutional political systems and the act of voting. This limited view prevents students from recognising the everyday, relational dimension of democracy, which can be practiced in various spaces beyond formal government institutions.

When the term *democracy* was introduced in activities or discussions, most students immediately linked it to government structures and electoral processes. There was a marked difficulty in conceiving democracy as a set of social practices that could take place in daily life, such as in schools or communities. Only when broader frameworks were offered, through facilitation, examples, or collaborative exercises, some participants recognised democratic elements in everyday interactions, such as teamwork, shared decision-making, or inclusive

dialogue. For instance, in the Kastelli lab (OULU), students responded to a Mentimeter activity asking, "What is democracy?". Their answers ranged from references to national voting systems to more process-oriented definitions like "everyone gets to make their opinions heard" and "deciding together." However, these more nuanced understandings tended to be exceptional or dependent on guided scaffolding within the lab context.

That said, when it came to *enacting* democracy rather than discussing it abstractly, many students showed the ability to engage in democratic practices. While voting was often proposed as the default mechanism for democratic participation, some groups went beyond this and adopted more deliberative, consensus-oriented approaches. A notable example comes from the BAU lab (UB), where students initially voted on potential project themes. Although "sexism" received the most votes, the group ultimately chose to focus on "affective responsibility"—a topic with fewer votes but stronger collective support that emerged through open dialogue and shared reasoning.

This contrast reveals a key divergence: while students often struggle to define democracy in theoretical terms, they are frequently capable of enacting its core principles when placed in participatory, dialogic settings. This suggests that democratic understanding cannot be fully developed through abstract or institutional discussions alone. Instead, it must be nurtured through lived experience, collaborative decision-making, and opportunities to practice democracy in meaningful, contextually relevant ways. Bridging the gap between knowing *about* democracy and learning to *do* democracy may therefore require a shift in pedagogical focus, from theory to practice.

5.3.1.2.2 Lack of Democratic Experiences

Closely linked to this distrust toward institutional democracy, the labs of this second iteration confirmed the findings of PAR 1. In several labs, researchers observed a pervasive sense of powerlessness: many students feel they lack a voice and the ability to influence their surroundings. This feeling is reinforced by the absence of real democratic spaces within the school environment. Several reports point out that opportunities for meaningful participation in school decision-making are extremely limited.

A clear example of this was observed in Can Fabra (UB). When students were invited to discuss decision-making possibilities within their school, they reported having very little room to participate or influence decisions, highlighting the lack of agency and inclusion in

institutional processes that directly affect them. Similarly in the Loutra lab (LATRA), one participant shared that, at school, decision-making is often limited to just a few people, which he found unfair. He expressed a desire to have more opportunities to take part in school decision-making processes. His comment encouraged the entire group to discuss what they could do to foster more inclusive decision-making at school.

This evidence again reinforces the need to place a stronger effort in designing experiences that, instead of teaching about democracy, enable students to experience democratic participation and provide spaces where they can exercise agency, engage in dialogue, and influence decisions that matter to them.

5.3.1.2.3 Ambivalent Attitudes Toward Collaborative Work

Collaborative work was often recognised as a stance of a democratic practice by the participating students. Nonetheless, across the different CCLABs, researchers observed an ambivalent stance toward collaborative work among students.

In some cases, such as the CrossCare Lab (TCD) students identified collaborative work as a core value that the group wishes to foster. In particular, these students emphasised the importance of bringing together people with diverse abilities and skills, ensuring that everyone has a place and role within the team. Their reflections highlighted inclusivity and productivity as key elements: valuing different types of contributions and making sure that the group can benefit from everyone's strengths.

In other cases, however, several tensions emerged in the actual practice of collaboration, especially regarding how responsibilities are distributed within groups. While working in small groups was generally seen as beneficial, diverse levels of participation and engagement often led to frustration or conflict.

For instance, at Vapor Molí (UB), students were organised into small teams. In several cases, only a few group members took on most of the work, while others adopted a passive attitude, seemingly comfortable waiting for their peers to complete the tasks. A similar pattern appeared at Ars Electronica, where some participants showed little interest in becoming actively involved, displaying a degree of resistance to deeper engagement.

At Corderius College (WAAG), students openly commented on unequal workload distribution within their groups. Some team members had not participated in the lab work,

leading to complaints about the lack of shared responsibility. Communication problems within the teams were also mentioned as a source of tension.

In both Norssi and Can Fabra, there was evidence of rejection of group work altogether. At Norssi (OULU), one student mentioned that their favourite part of the lab was the individual work phase, stating that they generally preferred not to work in groups. At Can Fabra (UB), two students refused to collaborate and instead developed separate ideas independently, unwilling to engage with or negotiate around each other's perspectives.

These challenges surrounding collaborative work reveal important entry points for reflection. An exemplary way to address these issues can be found in the Corderius College (WAAG) and BAU (UB) labs. In these contexts, facilitators, rather than viewing such difficulties as failures, used them as opportunities to engage students in critical reflection on the complexities of democratic practices and recognising that democracy is not only about agreement or cooperation, but also includes disagreement, negotiating roles, and taking shared responsibility.

5.3.1.2.5 The Importance of Equity

Across different labs, various reflections emerged around the theme of equity. For instance, in the Loutra lab (LATRA), students pointed out tensions related to equity and decision-making. One student noted that sometimes the people who speak the loudest end up getting their way, even if they're not necessarily right. Furthermore, in this lab, a significant dilemma was stated in the sense that participants and their families questioned the correlation between the concepts of fairness and equity thus opening a discussion regarding what happens when unequal distribution of certain resources is necessary to foster equity of opportunity. This advancement towards more democratic resource allocation practices happens not without controversy, since it was triggered in the context of social policies in favour of the inclusion of refugee families.

Similarly, in the UDNZ lab (ISRZ), researchers reported that the young participants were highly mindful of fairness. While they weren't inclined to impose strict rules, they were careful to avoid any instruction or activity that could give one group an advantage over another. In that sense they remained fixed with a meritocratic way of thinking, disregarding the systemic inequalities and social structures that may influence a person's outcome in terms of opportunity. However, through the photovoice activity, participants gained a deeper

understanding of how the broader social and historical context shaped not only their everyday lives but also those of their predecessors. Throughout the lab, they developed a clearer grasp of the evolving social norms and expectations across generations, as well as the factors driving these changes. Additionally, they developed a heightened awareness of the gender disparities that persist in modern society.

In the case of HTL Spengergasse lab (AE), equity awareness and gender perspective were also present as emerging topics. For instance, while doing fieldwork, students came across a woman mechanic who explained the difficulties associated with working in a gendered field.

These reflections across different labs reveal the complexity and evolving nature of students' understanding of equity. While initial perspectives often leaned toward meritocratic and individualistic views, engagement with real-life experiences prompted deeper conversations about fairness, inclusion, and the systemic factors shaping opportunity. The evolution underscores the importance of creating spaces where equity can be explored not as an abstract ideal, but as a lived and contested practice.

5.3.1.2.6 Challenges in Inhabiting Other Perspectives and Listening to Marginalised Voices

In several cases, researchers reported persistent difficulties among students in adopting perspectives other than their own. This was observed across multiple labs, including those at UNDZ (ISRZ), UDMJ (ISRZ), Loutra (LATRA), Can Fabra (UB), and Ars Electronica.

At UNDZ (ISRZ), students explored educational inequality. Initially, many saw these disparities as personal or individual problems rather than structural issues. However, by the final sessions, some students began recognising the social structures shaping educational experiences. In the UDMJ lab (ISRZ), which focused on equality and access to upper secondary education, students viewed affirmative actions (e.g., awarding extra points to underrepresented groups) as unfair and themselves a form of discrimination. They did not consider how life circumstances and systemic barriers affect educational outcomes. Educators expressed surprise and concern about these perspectives.

In the Loutra lab (LATRA), which brought together local and refugee children, researchers reported tensions around balancing the experiences of both groups. Many local children entered the process with prejudices and misconceptions about refugees, leading to

resistance during discussions. At Can Fabra (UB), similar difficulties emerged during a debate on school injustice. Students expressed ableist views, such as complaints about “wasting time” due to classmates needing more support, and suggestions to segregate students based on academic performance. Notably, no effort was made by participants to adopt alternative viewpoints or understand classmates’ experiences.

In the Ars Electronica lab, participants also struggled to engage with a podcast highlighting emotional experiences of marginalised individuals. Many found the content “too emotional” and had difficulty connecting to the suffering and fears described.

Overall, the experiences revealed a tendency among participants to emphasise individual effort over systemic analysis, often overlooking structural inequalities such as class, race, and ableism. In summary, across these varied contexts, students often struggled to move beyond their own perspectives and develop empathy or understanding for experiences different from their own. This evidence suggests the need for intentionally supporting strategies to cultivate perspective-taking and critical empathy.

5.3.1.3 Youth’s Ways of Understanding Their Role in Transforming and Changing Society

This section presents key insights into how young people understand their own agency and their possibilities to imagine and enact change in society. Furthermore, key challenges are highlighted.

5.3.1.3.1 Feeling of Being Unheard

Across the various CCLABs analysed, there is a consistent pattern of young people perceiving a lack of agency. This feeling is expressed both through apathy toward the possibility of creating change and through the sense that their voices are neither heard nor valued in participatory spaces.

In the lab at CrossCare (TCD), for example, the group openly expressed disinterest and scepticism about the effectiveness of democracy, stating that their participation had no real impact. This perception leads to a sense of resignation: young people believe that their individual actions lack the power to change a system they see as too large, rigid, and complex.

A similar idea emerged in Can Fabra (UB), where students said, “It’s not worth doing things right if everyone else does them wrong” (UB, Can Fabra Researcher diaries), revealing a logic in which individual effort is seen as meaningless without collective impact. This sense of futility in the face of change reinforces a passive attitude and a shared narrative of powerlessness: “One person alone cannot change things” (UB, Can Fabra Researcher diaries).

Likewise, in the Vapor Molí lab (UB), participants also expressed feelings of helplessness as agents of change, stating that their voices were not heard by the institutions with the power to implement transformation. One student said, “You can do whatever you want, but it won’t change the problem” (UB, Vapor Molí Focus Group).

This feeling also emerged in UDNZ (ISRZ), where students, although aware of social issues, reported not feeling capable of doing anything concrete in response.

Beyond these general beliefs, the perception of limited agency is further intensified by certain identity-related characteristics. In the lab DYFC (TCD), several young people said that being young limited their ability to be heard, noting that their ideas weren’t taken seriously, and their voices were systematically ignored. This perception of exclusion becomes even more complex when intersected with dimensions such as gender or sexual identity. In the same group, a trans student pointed out that someone like him “would never be elected” and therefore could never create real change, highlighting how social and political structures reproduce exclusionary logics that undermine confidence in the possibility of transformation.

Taken together, the findings reveal a generally negative understanding of personal agency. Students tend to see themselves as marginal actors in processes of social change, which reinforces a stance of disengagement and disaffection. Such considerations reinforce the need for policies and educational practices aimed at generating meaningful spaces for participation, without tokenizing it.

5.3.1.3.2 Resistance to “Projects That Go Nowhere”

Closely tied to the feeling of being unheard, several participants also expressed concerns, and at times explicit resistance, regarding the perceived lack of impact of the actions developed within the CCLAB framework.

In the HTL Spengergasse lab (AE), for example, participants openly voiced doubts about the relevance of their work, stating that the podcast they were producing would likely go unheard and have little to no impact. Similarly, during a focus group at Vapor Molí (UB), a student remarked that they were tired of constantly being asked to think and develop projects that “lead nowhere and have no real impact” (UB, Vapor Molí Focus Group). This critique is especially significant given the school’s strong emphasis on project-based learning; students reported feeling disillusioned, noting that “most of the projects we do are useless” (UB, Vapor Molí Focus Group). These sentiments echo those shared by students in the CrossCare lab (TCD), where participants openly stated that their involvement would not result in any tangible change, which they identified as a key source of demotivation.

In some cases, this scepticism translated into a lack of engagement or reluctance to take responsibility for the process. At Can Fabra (UB), for instance, students resisted making decisions about the lab and consistently avoided assuming leadership roles. The educator noted that while democratic practice requires a willingness to take responsibility, this was something the students struggled with throughout the sessions. A similar pattern was observed in the CrossCare lab (TCD): although students expressed a clear interest in improving their local environment, they were unable, or perhaps unwilling, to envision concrete actions or take initiative.

These observations raise important ethical questions about the focus on production and action in educational projects. There is a pressing need to reflect critically on the potential consequences of involving students in initiatives that ultimately lead nowhere. While such projects may be grounded in good intentions, they risk reinforcing disillusionment and disengagement if students perceive them as ineffective. An ethical approach to participatory education must consider not only what students are asked to produce, but also how their efforts are valued, sustained, and meaningfully connected to real-world outcomes.

5.3.1.3.3 Challenges in Imagining Other Possibilities

In many researchers’ diaries, a recurring challenge emerged: both educators and researchers often struggled to support young people in imagining alternative possibilities and envisioning different futures. This difficulty is explicitly noted in the TCD, UB, and OULU labs where the teams reported that the envision’ process posed significant challenges during the process.

For instance, in the CrossCare lab (TCD), researchers observed that instead of exploring radical possibilities, many participants remained grounded in present realities. They were hesitant to propose changes that felt too ambitious or distant. This became evident in their suggestions for improving a riverside area: the only concrete idea was to repaint the bridge crossing the river, a proposal quickly dismissed by the rest of the group.

A similar dynamic surfaced in the Design Your City lab (TCD). While participants showed critical awareness of systemic problems, especially in relation to climate change, they offered limited suggestions for alternatives. Despite their clear dissatisfaction with the status quo, they struggled to imagine futures beyond the current system. As a result, their contributions tended to focus on practical solutions rather than more radical or transformative visions.

This challenge of imagining otherwise also appeared in the Can Fabra lab (UB), where participants were invited to model 3D monsters representing a social issue they had identified: *indifference*. Here too, researchers noted that most participants failed to connect their creations with the earlier thematic discussions. The resulting designs often lacked depth and did not reflect the complexity of the issues explored.

Similar patterns were observed in the Norssi and Kastelli labs (OULU). When invited to envision possible futures, students often relied on generic science fiction tropes or examples introduced during the activity, rather than developing original or unexpected ideas.

These findings suggest that while young people may be capable of critiquing the present, imagining alternative futures requires deliberate pedagogical strategies that go beyond the initial proposals carried out in the CCLABs.

5.4 Evaluating the Pedagogical Effectiveness of the CCLAB

This section presents key insights into the pedagogical effectiveness of the PAR cycle 2 according to the competence framework described in section 4.1.

5.4.1 Changes in Youth's Ways of Understanding Contemporary Eco-social Issues

Overall, there is evidence that the PAR interventions have generated significant shifts in participants' understanding of their social and ecological contexts. The following items group the most relevant events regarding the observed transformations in youth's ways of understanding contemporary eco-social issues.

5.4.1.1 Shift from Individualistic Understandings to a More Systemic Perspective

As discussed in the previous section, many participants initially tended to understand phenomena from a fundamentally individualistic perspective. However, across different CCLABs, a key shift was observed: participants moved from individualistic understandings towards more situated and systemic perspectives, particularly using situated learning methods. This change became evident in cases such as CrossCare (TCD), UDDP (ISRZ), UDNZ (ISRZ), BAU (UB), and Loutra (LATRA).

At CrossCare (TCD), for example, it was reported that the guided tour through the Avoca river helped deepen participants' understanding of the interrelations between local ecological phenomena, global environmental issues, and their historical trajectories. In particular, it was highlighted that the programme enhanced participants' comprehension of the relevance of climate action by connecting it to the condition of the local river. Researchers noted that participants shifted from a general, abstract understanding of climate change to a more concrete, localized perception, beginning to see the importance of specific actions within their immediate environment. Additionally, participants developed a temporally situated awareness that showed appreciation of the past as a key element in shaping the circumstances that condition present day issues.

A similar dynamic was observed at UDDP (ISRZ), where researchers reported a change in participants' perspectives on mental health. While initially students tended to view mental health predominantly as an individual condition, through the participatory activities they began to recognise mental health as deeply interconnected with broader social factors and systemic issues.

Similarly, in the UDNZ (ISRZ) lab, students also demonstrated a significant change in perspective. Initially, their views on academic performance were rooted in a strongly

meritocratic and individualistic framework, believing that academic success was solely dependent on individual characteristics. Furthermore, participants initially perceived the allocation of power within gendered situations as being based primarily on individual merit. However, through dialogue and the exchange of experiences, they came to recognise the existence of pervasive structural inequalities and to realize that academic achievement is influenced by a wide range of factors beyond individual control, including one's intersectional positioning and broader social and familial contexts.

At BAU (UB), students similarly reported a shift in their understanding of affective responsibility. Whereas at the beginning they associated affective responsibility mainly with romantic relationships, by the end of the process they had developed a broader perspective, recognising it as a community-related issue, intertwined with social relations, neighbourhood dynamics, and collective well-being.

Finally, in the Loutra lab (LATRA), some participants acknowledged the role of their island in the context of broader global dynamics, recognising that local experiences are interconnected with more complex processes affecting many other regions.

Across the mentioned cases, participants took a step beyond personal viewpoints to grasp systemic understandings, recognising the broader social, historical, and environmental factors that shape their experiences. This shift was catalysed by situated, action-oriented learning that connected abstract concepts to lived realities.

5.4.1.2 Growing Awareness of Power Dynamics

In various contexts, participants showed a growing critical awareness of social and institutional power dynamics based on some of the activities elaborated in the CCLABs. An example of this can be seen in the activities related to the analysis and role play of Orwell's *Animal Farm* in Loutra (LATRA). One participant commented: "Why do the pigs think they're smarter than everyone else? Maybe the other animals didn't even get a chance to prove themselves" (LATRA, Researcher Diaries). This affirmation led to the questioning of power structures in their own immediate contexts, for example in the implementation of school rules, community dynamics and the treatment of refugees.

Similarly, in the UNDZ (ISRZ) lab students' research on the intersectional dimensions related to academic achievement led them to assume agency and contact professionals in gender-

atypical roles. Through this initiative, they critically examined gendered power hierarchies in the workplace through firsthand experiences. Ultimately these testimonies helped them approach a deconstruction of structural inequities tied to occupational gender segregation. Similarly, in the HTL Spengergasse lab (AE), participatory activities such as field interviews, the yes/no icebreaker dynamic, and the podcast reflections revealed nuanced grasps of democratic power imbalances. Through these processes, students were able to map social hierarchies (art students vs technical students) and identify polarization in a micro-level scope. This helped them recognise how identity groups are positioned in power relations.

5.4.2 Changes in Youth's Ways of Understanding and Doing

In general, CCLABs allowed generating relevant shifts in participants' ways of understanding and doing democracy. The following items group the most relevant events regarding the observed transformations.

5.4.2.1 Changes in the Conceptualization of Democracy

Prior to the labs, students' conceptualization of democracy was largely tied to its formal dimension, predominantly understood as a political system centred on voting and government institutions. However, across several cases, a significant shift in this understanding was observed as a result of the participatory processes.

In the Can Fabra lab (UB), students reported that they had re-evaluated their initial notion of democracy. They explained that they no longer viewed it merely as a political system defined by electoral participation but had developed a broader, more nuanced perspective connected to their everyday experiences. Democracy, they noted, now also meant listening to others, valuing diverse opinions, and engaging in practices of mutual respect and collaboration. A similar transformation was evident in the Corderius College lab (WAAG), where students expressed that democracy was no longer associated exclusively with formal governmental processes, but rather "also concerns them" since it relates to collective action and working together in groups.

Conversely, in the Open Lab (AE), by the end of the process, one participant noted that even having the freedom to choose the topics of their podcast episodes felt like a form of democracy. This indicates a significant cognitive understanding of democratic processes

but as it is framed within a predesigned structure without real empowerment, the experience runs the risk of reinforcing a passive disposition.

These reflections indicate that, through the labs, students began to move beyond a narrow, institutional understanding of democracy towards a more relational, practice-based conception, recognising its presence in daily social interactions as well.

However, it is also important to highlight the limitations of such processes when opportunities for genuine agency remain constrained. While cognitive shifts are evident, especially in the redefinition of democracy as collaborative and everyday practice, the persistence of adult-led structures and symbolic actions suggests the need for deeper transformations.

5.4.2.2 Growing Awareness Regarding the Complexities of Democratic Practices

A critical shift occurred in terms of realizing the investment of effort and time it takes to develop a consensus that is fair. In contrast it was also made clear that the lack of democratic experiences at the immediate level makes it difficult for democratic practices to materialise in the labs. This was observed especially in Loutra (LATRA), Corderius College (WAAG) and Can Fabra (UB).

For example, in the Loutra lab (LATRA), during the final discussion, some students mentioned that they hadn't realized how difficult it is to make fair decisions until they had to do it themselves during the activities. One student noted that this experience made them understand the importance of thinking carefully before making decisions, while another pointed out that, even when decisions are made with good intentions, they can sometimes end up causing more problems. In this same context, participants also shared different reflections on the process of making collective decisions. For instance, one student commented: "What would happen if everyone had to agree before establishing rules? It would probably take more time, but it would be fairer" (LATRA, Researcher Diaries). Both the researchers and the teachers present at this lab observed that the activities helped students begin to think more critically about how decisions are made and how they treat their peers during this process.

In the cases of Corderius College (WAAG) and Can Fabra (UB), students also shared similar reflections about how these activities prompted them to think about the complexities of

acting democratically within a group. At Can Fabra Lab (UB), while initially several tensions around group work emerged, through the process a shift towards consensus was achieved when a friendlier environment was created. Similarly, in the Corderius College lab (WAAG), participants recognised crucial changes in self-awareness and collaboration. They came to understand that true collaboration is complex and often unequal, requiring a lot of energy to work as equals. Moreover, this insight was accompanied with a feeling of collective pride towards the final product that the groups had developed. They expressed that it is not as easy as it might seem, acknowledging that there is a strong risk of being unfair and that working together equitably is a real challenge.

In conclusion, across several CCLAB contexts, students began to develop a more nuanced understanding of the complexities and challenges involved in democratic practices by offering them experiences that allow them to experience and enact democracy. This growing awareness signals an important shift, from viewing democracy as a set of abstract ideals to experiencing it as a demanding, sometimes messy, but ultimately meaningful process. At the same time, it underscores the importance of creating more spaces in education where students can practice and reflect on democratic engagement in tangible ways.

5.4.2.3 Growing Sensibility Toward Other Voices

In many cases, a significant shift was observed in participants' willingness to listen to the voices and experiences of others. This change was evident both in the direct practice of group work and in reflections on broader systemic phenomena, particularly regarding who has a voice and who remains unheard.

A key shift observed across nearly all educational settings was the emphasis on building rapport. Successful interventions incorporated active listening exercises, which fostered empathy and encouraged participants to reassess prior assumptions. For example, at Can Fabra (UB), students who initially reported difficulties working collaboratively came to recognise, through the process, the importance of listening to others' opinions. They highlighted that engaging in the practice of active listening not only improved the quality of their group work but also transformed their ability to understand and appreciate perspectives different from their own. These observations were also shared by the educator, who, in the final interview, reported a noticeable change in students' participation over time. Similarly, also in the Corderius College lab (WAAG), students and educators reported that the lab allowed them to learn how to collaborate better and how to know themselves better.

From a more systemic perspective, students also showed relevant changes in relation to their openness to other people's view and their ability to inhabit others' perspective. For instance, in the Design Your City lab (TCD), students argued that role-playing different viewpoints allows one to understand others' views. This perception was also shared in the Loutra lab (LATRA), where students reflected that the play provided an opportunity to reconsider the importance of hearing multiple voices, rather than just those in positions of power. By sharing experiences with refugee students, they came to appreciate the value of recognising and engaging with diverse perspectives. Furthermore, local parents who participated in this lab showed a shift in their understanding of others. One of them, specifically reported that initially he believed refugee families "kept to themselves" due to unwillingness to integrate. However, after hearing firsthand about the language barriers and cultural challenges they faced, the parents recognised the significant effort required to join a new community.

Similarly, in the HTL Spengergasse lab (AE), conducting interviews enabled participants to become more aware of voices that are often silenced and to acknowledge the need to consider alternative perspectives in their understanding of social realities. In particular, participants pointed out that collecting other voices through interviews helped them to open up to other viewpoints they don't come across in their daily life and that this activity allowed them to make conversations more relevant as they compared and contrasted different opinions.

To sum up, across diverse settings, the CCLABs helped foster a deeper appreciation for listening, not only as a communication skill but as a democratic practice and as a critical awareness to question whose voices are heard and whose are silenced.

5.4.2.4 Recognising the Affective Dimensions of Democracy

Across several cases, a growing awareness of the affective dimension of democracy emerged. This was the case of Loutra lab (LATRA), where local students showed a growing openness to understanding the difficulties experienced by their refugee peers, shifting from attitudes of judgment or indifference to ones of deep empathy and curiosity. Something similar happened in HTL Spengergasse lab (AE), where students valued empathy and collaboration as key elements to addressing social issues.

Also, in the BAU lab (UB), participants expressed that their understanding of emotional responsibility gradually expanded beyond personal relationships to include community, family, and educational contexts. This broader understanding allowed exploring an additional dimension of democratic participation, as students were able to recognise their roles and responsibilities toward other people's wellbeing within various social structures.

These examples underscore the central role of emotionality not only in shaping interpersonal dynamics but also in enabling deeper, more sustained engagement with democratic practices.

5.4.3 Changes in Youth's Ways of Understanding Their Role in Transforming Society

Less evidence was reported regarding meaningful changes related to participants' understanding of their role in transforming and changing society. Although the CCLABs fostered greater autonomy and deeper understandings of civic engagement in many participants, there was little direct evidence of explicit change regarding their roles as active agents of societal transformation. Across the cases, no participant clearly articulated a shift in their fundamental beliefs or self-perception in this regard. While some demonstrated increased initiative within the confines of the lab activities, these changes did not necessarily translate into sustained transformations or long-term commitment to social action.

Nevertheless, consistent patterns emerged indicating that the CCLABs helped participants grow in confidence and begin to explore forms of decision-making and problem-solving. Through participatory tools such as voting, role-playing, and collaborative design, students gradually took more ownership over the process. This was particularly notable in DYFC (TCD), the UDDP lab (ISRZ), and the BAU lab (UB), where participants moved from passive involvement to more active shaping of the lab's direction. These developments, however, reflect early steps toward autonomy rather than conclusive shifts in attitudes.

The absence of explicit declarations of attitudinal change underscores the limits of short-term interventions in cultivating deep internal transformation. Changes in how young people perceive their social roles, responsibilities, and power to enact change are slow processes that unfold over time. The compressed timelines and limited continuity of many labs presented structural obstacles to this kind of development. For example, in CrossCare

(TCD) and Vapor Molí Institute (UB), institutional constraints and time limitation made it difficult to sustain student initiative, leading some proposals to be discarded before deeper reflections could emerge. These examples reveal the challenge of balancing facilitators' aspirations with participants' readiness and the time needed for profound change to unfold.

Nonetheless, it is worth noticing that in a few settings, there were signs of a shift in disposition from product-oriented thinking to a more process-focused understanding of change. In the UDDP lab (ISRZ) and in the BAU lab (UB), participants began by seeking tangible outcomes but gradually came to appreciate the value of dialogue, experimentation, and uncertainty. In BAU (UB), this awareness culminated in students advising future participants to "trust the process."

Overall, while promising openings emerged, the findings suggest that fostering meaningful change in relation to civic agency and social responsibility requires longer-term engagement, repeated exposure to democratic practices, and safe environments where reflection and agency can unfold gradually. Without sufficient time such transformations run the risk of remaining aspirational.

5.5 Reflecting on Methodological Choices

In its design, the CCLAB is grounded in methodological diversity as a key resource for fostering youth participation and offering tools to analyse phenomena from alternative perspectives. However, a more systematic evaluation of the different methodological approaches was needed. This section presents key insights linked to the impact of using specific methods to promote democratic engagement in youth, drawing on data collected from diverse educational settings across the project. Specifically, we will explore five methodological axes that characterize the CCLAB:

- The use of art-based methods.
- The implementation of participatory research methodologies.
- The use of dynamics based on debate and dialogue.
- The application of situated strategies aimed at connecting with "out-of-institution" spaces.

- The use of methods that engage with different temporalities.

Finally, we will conclude the section with some final considerations regarding the specific challenges of the CCLAB's methodological approach.

5.5.1 Art-Based Methods

One of the central pillars of the CCLAB is the use of artistic and creative strategies aimed at reflection, creativity, imagination, confidence in sharing ideas and meaningful collaboration among the students. Due to the multimodal nature of this model, methodological experiences have been grouped in three areas: Visual art methods, Performative strategies, Design based practices.

5.5.1.1 Visual Art-Based Methods

These methodologies encompass a wide variety of practices and are grounded in a robust body of literature demonstrating the transformative potential of the arts (e.g., Barone & Eisner, 2012; Greene, 1995; Leavy, 2015; Lee, 2025). For the purpose of this analysis, we will place a specific emphasis on techniques based on photovoice, memes and zine making, drawing, modelling, collage, photography, and video.

The photovoice method was used in UDDP (ISRZ) and UDNZ (ISRZ) where, through photography, students explored social issues from their own perspectives, identifying and making problems visible, which promoted critical analysis and helped to strengthen bonds within the group. In the case of UDDP (ISRZ), students were asked to find or take photographs of objects, people and situations that, for them, represented mental health in the educational context and wrote some with brief reflections on what they represented for them. The photographs were then discussed in open dialogue. The oral contributions and the photographs allowed participants to communicate about protective and risk factors for mental health and to share their experiences, both positive and negative, with mental health in education.

At UDNZ (ISRZ) this method was used as a tool to make students reflect, identify and analyse gender inequality. Students were asked to look for or take pictures of objects, people or situations that represent how life and education have changed over the last decades focusing on the personal, family and societal levels. Students were then divided into smaller

groups and tasked with discussing the selected images to share their views and understanding of gender inequalities in the past and today. At the end, the students expressed that the photovoice activity significantly strengthened their connections with each other and provided them with a clearer understanding of gender inequality by presenting tangible real-life examples through photographs. This experience helped them to become more conscious of their daily environment, to reflect and investigate what they saw and experienced on a daily basis.

The method of creating memes was also effective in engaging young people to express their frustrations through humour, making visible their understanding of and relationship to social issues. This was the case in the CrossCare lab (TCD), where students were encouraged to choose a climate change issue they would like to communicate to politicians and to use satire to highlight their concerns. Participants expressed their vision and awareness of power relations and the role of governments and big business in the fight against the climate crisis. First, students organised themselves into groups to discuss specific aspects of climate change in their locality or everyday life that they would like to highlight. Then, they were then given access to a free meme template platform and asked to create some memes based on their topic. One participant used the meme "Kid Named Finger" to satirically express the feeling of burden and the idea of how adults shift the responsibility for climate action onto younger generations, who in turn feel that this immense task "falls on their shoulders". Nonetheless, in general, the educators highlighted that many of the memes created managed to address a general climate action issue or challenge, but it would have been beneficial to have more time to go deeper and work on these memes to link them to more local issues.

Another powerful tool was the creation of zines that condensed the collective learning journey. In UDDP (ISRZ), participants created one around the selected theme: "Mental Health in the Education System". This format allowed students to make problems visible, tell stories or transmit relevant data from their research on mental health. The participants were responsible for defining the content and design of the zine in groups or individually, using fragments of texts, reflections, interviews, drawings or graphics.

Another relevant example can be found in the use of drawing. In the Loutra lab (LATRA) the facilitators invited participants to express thoughts or ideas in relation to social and inclusion issues through this method and incorporated student's artwork into the Animal

Farm adaption. This activity allowed for a visual and collective reflection on how to convey emotions and explore complex ideas, such as fairness and justice through a multimodal format that incidentally granted a way of participations to less eloquent students.

This expressive potential was also shared in the Can Fabra lab (UB), where it became clear that students found it easier to reflect on complex issues through artistic practices than through conversations or debates. In particular, through 3D modelling, using both play dough and the TinkerCad software, participants were invited to transform problematic issues they identified in their daily lives into plasticine monsters. The dynamics helped the students to move from concrete manipulation of the material to understand and reflect on everyday injustice.

Nonetheless, in other cases, such as Vapor Molí (UB) and CrossCare lab (TCD) activities such as collage making were perceived as too abstract by participants. Specifically, in Vapor Molí (UB) the proposal to create a three-dimensional collage of their research proposal turned out to be too abstract and did not achieve the objective of helping students in defining their project. Similarly, in CrossCare (TCD), when participants were invited to use the collage to reflect on their relation with the local river, many of them expressed that they did not understand the purpose of this activity commenting: 'We didn't really know what we were meant to do', 'we didn't really do anything except cut up paper and then glue it to a page'; 'it didn't really feel that useful'; 'For me personally, I was just looking through my scene and then anything I thought, 'Oh, that's pretty' I just stuck it on' (TCD, CrossCare Focus Group).

Except for these two specific cases, visual methods were well received by participants. Students highlighted how these approaches allowed them to become more engaged with the proposal and appreciated being able to break out of the usual formats and express themselves in a different way. Several educators also stressed the potential for integrating these methodologies into future school projects, even if some of them felt that they lacked sufficient artistic knowledge to do so effectively. Finally, researchers observed how these creative approaches allowed students to view social phenomena from new and diverse perspectives, contributed to enhancing participation by making the research activities more accessible and offered valuable insights into how young people conceptualise the phenomenon under analysis. It follows that creative inputs were used not only to express themselves, but as a cognitive tool that allowed participants to understand complex issues from multiple angles and explore other forms of deliberation beyond verbal language.

5.5.1.2 Performative Methods

During the development of the labs, performative strategies emerged as relevant methodological approaches to address their specific goals. For the purpose of this analysis, we will place a specific emphasis on techniques based on physical games, role play and theatrical activities across different labs.

In UDNZ (ISRZ), the implementation of these strategies facilitated the exploration of the notion of educational inequality. One of the methods used was the “Walking Debate (attitudes thermometer), which allowed participants to express their opinions and learn about the opinions of their peers in a safe and participatory environment. The exercise consisted of drawing a line on the floor representing a scale of positioning, from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree”. Participants were read different statements related to educational inequalities, such as: ‘Students in vocational training programmes do not have the same opportunities to access university’. After listening to each statement, students were asked to place themselves in the position on the line that reflected their degree of agreement or disagreement. They were then asked to argue their position. At the end of the exchange of ideas, they were given the opportunity to change places if their opinion had changed as a result of the discussion.

This physical positioning activity allowed participants to observe the diversity of opinions on the same issue, and to understand that positions are not simply a matter of agreeing or disagreeing, but are part of a much broader spectrum. The exercise helped students develop a deeper and more complex understanding of educational inequality. Educators concluded that, through this activity, students had the opportunity to build critical knowledge of the world, to exercise openness to other beliefs or views, and to practice critical self-reflection.

In other cases, role-playing was employed to support participants embodying different characters and emotions or explore other perspectives, allowing them to understand and be affected by the issues at hand. A striking example of this occurred at CrossCare lab (TCD). During the activity, cards with different characters were distributed to the participants, who were asked to identify a physical trait that would help them to get into the assigned role. Once the character was adopted, the educators introduced various discussions that led to the creation of stories and conversations set in imaginary scenarios of the past. At the end, the group came together for a shared reflection. In this case, through

the embodiment of different characters, participants explored the historical and relational layers associated with water availability in Dublin, thus transforming abstract concepts into tangible, situated and meaningful experiences. The researchers highlighted that the dynamic generated a particularly revealing moment, as it led to a deeper understanding of the implications and interconnections of the phenomena addressed and their historical dimensions. This experience aroused the curiosity and interest of the group. One young person pointed out that, although the character she inhabited was very different from her, the exercise of defending her point of view allowed her to understand other ways of thinking.

In Can Fabra (UB), the dynamics of the Image Theatre was used as a methodological tool to give meaning and structure to the information previously collected by the participants in their field diaries. In the previous session, they had been asked to observe and collect concrete examples of problems linked to social indifference. During the new session, each participant chose a scene from her diary and using the bodies of her peers, without speaking, they represented the selected scene as if they were sculptors, creating a static image (Figure 5). The other members of the group had to interpret and guess what was being represented. Afterwards, the scenes were analysed collectively through questions such as: What do these scenes tell us? What do they have in common? How do they relate to each other? What are the consequences? The key ideas that emerged from this analysis were hand-drawn on a conceptual map on kraft paper. Finally, pairs were formed. Each pair selected a specific focus from the map to explore in more depth.

Figure 5. *Theatre of the Oppressed Dynamic (UB – Can Fabra)*

During the CCLABs, performative strategies did not only involve directed enactment but also included artistic fruition. A remarkable example is represented by the Loutra lab (LATRA), where they adapted the play of George Orwell's novel *Animal Farm* to include interactive elements that allowed students to vote on characters' decisions. This structure fostered debate among children who used the play as a mirror for reflecting on tensions and injustice in their situated context. Similarly, participants from UDNZ (ISRZ) attended the play *Shoe Tongue*, which tells the story of a young Croatian footballer transferred to a German club, exploring dehumanisation in elite sport through the prism of success, pressure and emotional isolation. According to the researchers, the play resonated with the themes of the lab, addressing gender roles within this environment by offering a critical look at the tensions between traditional versus contemporary gender models. Participants stated that the play "inspired them a lot" (ISRZ-UDNZ, Focus Group) and helped them understand the interconnectedness between different social roles that shape people's lives in ways that can seem frustrating, confusing or contradictory. This experience reaffirmed the role of art as a means of questioning social structures, encouraging reflection and challenging perspectives by influencing the way people perceive their social reality.

To sum up, during the development of the labs, performative strategies succeeded in provoking moments for critical reflection, emotional expression and exploration or active participation. Through these practices that bring attention back to the body, participants were able to explore the chosen themes from a dimension that differs from the school routine, promoting deep understanding and connection. Moreover, in several labs, they offered the embodied opportunity to inhabit other points of view and to generate emotional links between the participants and the social issues addressed through emerging affects.

Finally, another highlight was the involvement of learners who are not usually very participatory. One educator (TCD) highlighted the involvement of a pupil known for his general disinterest, who was motivated and active during the performative dynamics. These anecdotes illustrate the potential of artistic strategies to include those who are often left out in more conventional pedagogical formats.

5.5.1.3 Design-Based Methods

Design-based methodologies played a crucial role in materialising ideas, exploring concrete solutions, and facilitating shared decision-making. Within the CCLABs, a wide

range of design-based techniques were employed, including visual mapping, scenario envisioning, prototyping, and participatory design.

On the other hand, during the Envision phase of the CCLAB methodology, the use of design methods focused on supporting students in imagining alternatives and desirable futures, drawing on methodological frameworks such as design futuring and speculative design (e.g., Dunne & Raby, 2013; Hardy, 2019; Howell et al., 2021; Kozubaev et al., 2020; Maxwell et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2021). In the UDDP (ISRZ) labs, groups imagined optimistic, pessimistic and realistic futures about issues such as educational inequalities, using visual materials to construct narratives and propose action plans. This method supported critical analysis of current social and educational trends, promoting collective reflection on possible courses of action and strengthening their prospective capacity.

On the other hand, in the Act phase, techniques based on rapid prototyping were implemented in several CCLABs. Through this approach, students were invited to use accessible materials to transform their ideas, developed from previous research processes, into tangible and contextualised proposals. A prominent example took place at the Vapor Moli lab (UB), where a group designed and built a prototype of a bin lid out of cardboard, motivated by an everyday problem: waste blowing in the wind around their school. The process, which included taking measurements, designing, building and testing the prototype in the public space, awakened in the students a strong sense of capability and agency (Figure 6). Similarly, at BAU (UB), the lab led to the creation of artistic devices linked to the theme of affective responsibility. The creations included a handbook for families, a collaborative website, and a photographic installation of maps to identify community spaces.

Figure 6. *Prototype Design (UB – Can Fabra)*

In several cases, participatory design approaches were integrated into rapid prototyping to ensure the co-creation of outcomes and foster a stronger sense of ownership. A notable example is the Corderius College lab (WAAG), where students collaboratively designed a costume representing their individual and collective identities. This process involved negotiation, collaboration, and shared decision-making, highlighting the social and relational aspects of democratic practice. The experience of jointly designing and prototyping not only fostered creativity and group cohesion but also allowed participants to embody and critically engage with the complexities and tensions of democratic participation.

Overall, the use of design-based methodologies within the CCLABs not only enabled the generation of concrete ideas and solutions but also enhanced young people's capacity to collaborate creatively and engage in collective decision-making.

5.5.2 Use of Participatory Research Methods

One of the central goals of the CCLAB approach was to engage young people in actively researching specific eco-social issues. The framing and implementation of research activities varied across the different labs, with each site adopting distinct techniques suited to their context and objectives. These included methods such as field diaries, social media ethnography, field visit, interviews and desk research, among others.

At Can Fabra (UB), participants were invited to keep a field diary for one week, documenting scenes and situations related to their chosen topic: social indifference. This exercise encouraged them to observe their everyday environments with a more critical lens, helping them to identify the absence of democratic and caring practices in their immediate surroundings. By becoming ethnographers of their daily lives, participants developed greater awareness of subtle yet significant social dynamics. They realized how indifference to others' discomfort operates across everyday spaces, like the schoolyard or public transport, sparking a debate on how "wrongdoing" can stem not from direct action, but from failing to pay attention to what others are experiencing.

In Kastelli (OULU) they involved students as co-researchers through an approach based on social media ethnography. Specifically, they asked students to collect data, in the form of screenshots, around the question "What bothers you regarding social media?". After this

collection phase, students were involved in collective thematic analysis. In small groups, students worked with the collected screenshots to group them into categories and define key themes and central issues. Through this process, which combined individual data collection with collective analysis, discussion and reflection, students manage to gradually assume a more critical perspective in their ways of looking at social media.

Field visits also proved successful strategies for involving students in researching specific issues. For instance, in the DYFC lab (TCD), students were involved in a creative mapping exercise and a field visit. During the first exercise, researchers invited students to examine their local environments, pinpointing areas where infrastructure hindered pedestrian and cycling mobility. Through discussions and creative mapping, they identified challenges (e.g., poor bike lanes, unsafe crossings, and limited green spaces.) The task triggered a relevant understanding: reimagining the city wasn't just about large-scale futuristic ideas but also about practical, small-scale interventions that could have a significant impact. During the second visit, the participants went on a "biodiversity walk" through Trinity College Dublin, guided by sustainability experts. They explored the ecological significance of urban green spaces, considering how nature could be integrated into the city's landscape and considered some of the challenges facing Dublin city specifically in the face of climate change. The value of engaging directly with experts and seeing real-life examples became evident when, in a later activity, students chose to create digital 'pets', with one group selecting a pine marten, a native species, highlighting how eco-social themes had clearly resonated.

Similarly, at Vapor Moli (UB), one of the groups decided to focus their research on security in the underground transportation system. The group, accompanied by one of the facilitators, visited a metro station near the school to take photographs, count the number of surveillance cameras, evaluate their distribution, check the functioning of the emergency buttons and how many security agents were in the space. This fieldwork helped to reinforce the relevance of their research by highlighting the scarce and ineffective presence of security measures. The activity not only broadened their understanding of the problem but also increased their motivation as they realised that their project responded to a concrete need, observed and felt first-hand.

The field visit methodology was reinforced by interviews with experts in the UDDP lab (ISRZ) where the visit to the University Counselling Centre was described by participants as "the

most impactful part of the process” to better understand mental health and education. During the visit, students, educators and researchers learned first-hand about the work of the centre’s psychologists, who shared their experience in accompanying students as counsellors. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions and fill in a psychological questionnaire related to mental health and received individual feedback on their results. They were also introduced to tools such as associative cards, designed to recognise signs of distress in oneself or others. This experience allowed them to connect in a personal way with the research topic.

Another participatory method that facilitated active involvement in researching challenges was the “Archive of Voices”. At HTL Spengergasse (AE) the process involved conducting multiple interviews that allowed participants to delve into current political issues with people they met randomly on the street. One group spoke with a university student who shared her stress in trying to balance academic demands with personal responsibilities. This conversation shed light on the mental health issues faced by young people and sparked critical discussion among the group about the lack of adequate support systems in educational institutions. In UDNZ (ISRZ), participants interviewed a woman working in a mechanic’s workshop, who shared her daily experiences of sexism in the work environment. Her experiences resonated with the students, leading to a deep reflection on gender inequality in professional environments and how social norms reinforce these biases. The experience reinforced the value of active listening as a participatory research tool and demonstrated how direct contact with diverse voices can enrich understanding of social phenomena, encouraging deeper discussions on how structural inequalities affect people’s lives and well-being.

In contrast, desk research was found by partners to be insufficient to activate imagination or critical thinking or to foster student ownership of the process. For instance, in the Vapor Moli lab (UB), the students who only engaged in desk research by looking for information regarding their topic on the internet, showed a lower engagement and motivation in the process and in the ideation phase. In UDDP (ISRZ), a method that included reading about articles related to mental health did not encourage positive engagement in participants.

To sum up, the CCLABs offer positive evidence of the relevance of engaging students as active participants in empirical research processes. The empirical approaches applied to involve young people in investigating real-world eco-social issues offered students

opportunities to connect with their surroundings, hear other voices, and reflect deeply on the complexities of the issues they explored. This finding reinforces the value of participatory and student-led empirical work, stressing the importance of researching not as a way of collecting information but as an empirical work that allows shaping understanding and building relationships.

5.5.3 Use of Debate and Dialogue-Based Methods

As part of the CCLAB's participatory methodology, various dialogue and debate-based techniques were implemented to foster participants' openness to diverse worldviews, critical reflection, and collaborative inquiry. These methods aimed to encourage young people to articulate, question, and rethink their perspectives in a respectful way, hence supporting their deliberation skills. To scaffold these competencies, facilitators used a wide range of dialogic tools, including performative debates, structured debates or group discussions through visual cartographies (Figure 7). These modalities combined verbal and non-verbal expressions of opinions.

Figure 7. Visual Cartography (AE – Open Lab)

In the case of Vapor Molí and Can Fabra (UB), visual cartographies were used to identify the theme of the laboratory in a participatory way. On a piece of kraft paper on the floor, participants wrote their answers to the question “What are you fed up with?” on sticky notes and stuck them to the paper. After placing their post-it, each participant explained precisely what they meant by the content they had added to the post-it, as well as the reasoning behind their choices. These conversations became moments of collective reflection, where

participants debated whether others shared similar concerns or frustrations. They then placed their notes and grouped them by thematic affinity. Together with the researchers, they collectively named the resulting groups. Each participant marked with a star the topics they were most interested in. Finally, the pros and cons of the most voted topics were discussed, and the focus of the lab was agreed upon (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Participants Writing (UB – BAU)

Another example was the performative walking debate implemented at both UDNZ (ISRZ) lab and at DYFC (TCD) lab. Participants physically positioned themselves along a line drawn on the floor to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with provocative statements. After each statement and positioning, a discussion took place in which participants explained the reasons for their positioning in the line. The educators acted as mediators, encouraging all students to express their opinions freely and respectfully. This embodied practice stimulated dialogue by inviting participants to justify their positioning, leading to reflective conversations. This approach was similar to another approach taken by Center Rog (KI), through the technique of the “row of opinions”. As in the “walking debate”, students were asked to position themselves based on their opinion around specific statements related to technology and society. After this initial positioning, they were invited to discuss between them their opinion. This method allowed them to explore more nuanced approaches in their views and understandings.

Another variation of this approach was used in UDDP (ISRZ), through the “Walk of privilege” activity in which participants were invited to reflect on the role of society in the reproduction of inequalities. The participants were divided into two groups; one group was in the role of

an observer and in the other group each participant was assigned a different role. The facilitators posed a series of questions from the perspective of the assigned roles. For each affirmative answer to the questions posed, they had to step forward. If the answer was no, they remained in their place. The second group observed attentively without knowing the other group's assigned role. At the end of the series of questions, the observers tried to deduce which identity each role represented, based on their relative position. This led to a guided discussion space to share impressions, observations and reflections on structural inequality.

Structured debate also supported shifts in perspective, deepened critical thinking and students' engagement. For instance, at Corderius College (WAAG) the appearance of a statement about racism on the interactive whiteboard generated absolute silence in the classroom whereas the subsequent projection of an image representative of the Black Lives Matter movement initiated a conversation about the protest. The facilitator proposed the organisation of a "debate" with students from another academic discipline in order to continue the discussion, and a total of fifteen of the twenty-seven students expressed their interest in participating. This demonstrated the persistence of their curiosity and interest, even beyond the end of the initial workshop, as well as the importance of scaffolding and the power of well-chosen prompts and cues in fostering debate amongst youth.

A creative approach to debate was proposed by Loutra (LATRA). In this lab, researchers employed a creative and art-based approach to foster debate among youth. Aligned with Boal's Theatre of the Oppressed technique, this lab adapted George Orwell's novel "Animal Farm" to include interactive elements that allowed students to vote on characters' decisions. This structure fostered debate among children who used the play as a mirror for reflecting on tensions and injustice in their situated context. Furthermore, this approach allowed them to connect what happens in the play with what happens in their lives and better understand the tensions related to fairness and inclusion.

In the same vein, the guided tour of the Ars Electronica centre at OpenLab (AE) offered participants an immersive and interactive experience focused on topics such as artificial intelligence, robotics, the future of food, materials and music. Participants explored the exhibition in a collaborative and active way, generating speculative questions. The sections on AI and food provoked particularly rich discussions, with imaginative scenarios such as: "What if the earth were edible?" or "How would our artistic experience change if music were

composed by robots?” The activity encouraged speculative thinking, reinforcing the group's capacity to imagine alternatives to the present through collective dynamics of discussion, active listening and the construction of shared ideas.

Despite the successes, several cases also revealed the limitations and challenges of this approach. In the Can Fabra lab (UB), participants showed a certain resistance toward fully engaging with debate and critical reflection, explicitly stating that they prefer “doing” rather than thinking. Similarly, in the WAAG lab, researchers also reported a limited participation into deeper discussion, due to the perceived lack of a safe space for dialogue.

In summary, the discussions and dialogic practices allowed young people to explore complex social issues, such as the refugee crisis, social inclusion or democratic values, leading to a more holistic understanding and deeper reflection on social challenges that manifest themselves both globally and locally. Questions addressing dilemmas linked to democratic principles often triggered discussions that concluded with the need for a more nuanced formulation or a broader context to form an informed opinion.

The diversity of formats, from performative debates to structured discussions and visual mappings, gave rise to different forms of expression and interpretation, accommodating both verbal and embodied forms of knowledge (Figure 9). However, specific challenges were also encountered, such as resistance to critical reflection or the perception of an insecure space for dialogue, reminding us that these practices cannot be taken for granted.

Figure 9. *Final Activity. Podcast Recording (AE – Open Lab)*

5.5.4 Strategies to Connect with "Out-Of-Institution"

As part of the CCLAB methodology, each partner explored specific strategies to engage young people in initiatives beyond the school context. These community-based approaches aimed to connect students with real-world actors and support their willingness to act in their local contexts. Several labs illustrate the transformative effect of this approach.

For instance, at UDDP (ISRZ), where participants focused on exploring mental health, their visit to the University of Zagreb's Student Counselling Centre provided opportunities to engage with professionals, explore self-assessment tools, and reflect on emotional wellbeing from both personal and social perspectives. This direct contact facilitated a more nuanced understanding of the individual and social factors that impact on emotional wellbeing. Furthermore, this visit was described by participants as 'the most impactful part of the process' of raising awareness about emotional health.

Another example can be observed in the collaboration with professionals at Openlab (AE), where the intervention of a radio producer raised enthusiasm and reinforced participation. The same happened in UDNZ (ISRZ) where participants carried out interviews with two professionals: a female sports coach and a male pre-school caregiver. The discussion focused on their experiences, challenges, advantages and obstacles of working in areas outside conventional gender roles. The speakers shared both positive and negative experiences, providing participants with valuable insight and a deeper understanding of the topic explored in the lab.

Similarly, in the CrossCare (TCD) lab, the walking activity in the local area facilitated an emotional connection to the issue of climate change and supported more concrete ideas for taking action: planting different types of plants close to the asphalt and applying the botanical knowledge previously acquired. This strategy increased the motivation of the group by making the local effects of global issues more accessible and visible, and fostered a greater sense of agency and care for their environment among the young people.

However, connecting the school with the local context also faced some challenges. As an example, at Vapor Molí (UB), one group focused on safety in the subway system, aiming to develop anti-gender violence software for a mobile app. As part of their research, the group went out to explore a metro station near the school. This outing further reinforced the

relevance of their proposal, as they saw for themselves the limited and ineffective security in the metro environment. However, despite the relevance of the issue, the thematic freedom offered by the lab made the implementation of possible solutions difficult, as the scale of the problem exceeded the resources and means available, making it an unfeasible action. This case exemplifies a frequent situation in which, despite the interest and involvement of the group, the action did not materialise due to the magnitude of the proposal or logistical limitations.

Overall, the integration of activities to connect with the local context contributed to student engagement, critical reflection, and a stronger sense of purpose. Participants consistently expressed a desire for more external visits, real-life collaborations, and outdoor workshops. The teaching staff also expressed an expectation of greater community involvement and the need for the lab design to incorporate a greater number of activities developed outside the institutional environment, facilitating the connection with diverse external scenarios that strengthen the students' sense of agency and the real impact of their projects.

Anchoring activities in local realities enhanced students' connection to the issues and strengthened their sense of agency. Moreover, collaboration with external professionals provided alternative perspectives making the learning process more dynamic and memorable. In most labs, contact with the outside world was a catalyst for transforming ideas into action and a key source of motivation that helped overcome initial resistance to participation.

Nonetheless, one of the most latent frictions in the development of the CCLAB model has been rooting the labs locally in a meaningful way. The time constraints imposed by the institutional rhythm and calendars make it difficult for the young people to take the necessary time to identify and carry out the needed networking to meaningfully address a topic that is relevant to the local context to collectively produce some transformation. Therefore, not all labs managed to create meaningful connections outside the institution.

5.5.5 Use of Different Temporal Dimensions

An effective methodological strategy that emerged from the cross-cutting analysis of the labs was the integration of multiple temporal dimensions—past, present, and future—to deepen critical understanding of complex phenomena and enhance the capacity to imagine alternative realities.

A significant example of this happened in TCD where the CCLAB was integrated into a pre-existing programme called “Design Your Future City” with a focus on sustainability. In this lab, the students analysed the evolution of Dublin over the years in relation to urban planning. This gave them the opportunity to observe change over time, which, according to the educators, influenced their final design proposals.

Another relevant example was at UDDP (ISRZ), where facilitators invited students to develop speculative thinking by creating optimistic, pessimistic and realistic future scenarios as part of the work on educational inequalities and mental health. Using a variety of materials such as photographs, newspaper clippings, collage paper, markers and play dough, each group visualised their ideas in a creative way. This activity promoted participants’ autonomy, reinforcing the idea that the future is not predetermined and provided opportunities to explore issues from a critical and temporal perspective, generating meaningful discussions about change, responsibility and action.

At Open Lab (AE), an activity took place around the exhibition Future, which provided a space for debate on how futures have been imagined over time and the implications of these representations. Through artworks produced between 1906 and 2024, participants explored different artistic visions of the future. They were asked to identify what artists thought about the future, what problems they perceived in their historical context and how they projected its possible transformation. During the reflection, discussions emerged about which visions of the future had been realised and how these demonstrated that the future can be changed. This highlighted the role of speculative thinking as a generator of agency. At the same time, some participants critically questioned the dominant approaches represented in the exhibition, pointing out that many of the examples responded to “very white” perspectives, which opened an important space for debate about who has the right to imagine the future. In this sense, the exhibition functioned as a catalyst for activating critical and speculative thinking practices.

To sum up, this approach fostered moments of reflection. Facilitators underlined the importance of discussing issues in relation to temporalities. In the phases of Question & Analyse it enabled participants to talk about the past and the present, generating a genuine interest in learning more about historical processes and their current implications. In the ‘Envision’ stage it enabled participants to explore futures, suggesting that the future is undefined and susceptible to change.

5.5.6 Strengths and Issues with Methods

The cross-cutting analysis revealed several specific strengths of the CCLAB model, while also bringing to light some relevant tensions that merit further reflection.

Among the most significant strengths, beyond those already mentioned, was the democratic structure of the sessions. Students actively participated in making decisions with visible consequences within the lab, such as choosing topics, drawing connections between issues, and defining criteria for the different phases. This tangible involvement helped questioning traditional hierarchies, promoting more horizontal educator-participant relationships. Participants repeatedly emphasised how the participatory design of the sessions differed from conventional classes, making them feel part of the process.

Another key strength was the implementation of a wide variety of methods, which sustained engagement across diverse groups with varying interests, abilities, and ages. The multiplicity of formats (e.g., art and design based, performative, written, etc.) provided inclusive pathways for participation, particularly benefiting those less comfortable with public speaking. As a result, even participants who were less active initially found meaningful ways to contribute since multimodal forms of participation enabled different forms of expression. The possibility to choose and take responsibility for specific tasks within group work further reinforced the inclusivity of these approaches. Furthermore, in contexts such as Loutra (LATRA) and OpenLab (AE), the specific attention to linguistic and cultural diversity enhanced peer collaboration and gradually shifted power dynamics towards more democratic relationships.

On the other hand, however, the cross-cutting analysis also revealed various methodological tensions that affected both the participants' understanding of the proposal and their involvement in the project. These specific challenges subsequently informed the iteration of the design of the model. The identified challenges were:

- **Temporal constraints:** As in PAR Cycle 1, one of the most frequently reported challenges was the limited time allocated for the labs. Students, educators, and researchers consistently noted that the timeframe was insufficient to support deeper reflection, genuine collaboration, or lasting change. Participants often struggled to move through the full lab, from problem identification to action design and implementation, within the schedule. This time pressure led to superficial

engagement in some cases, and in others, it generated frustration or fatigue. Educators and facilitators also acknowledged that the ambitions of the model, encouraging democratic agency, fostering collective action, and producing socially relevant outputs, were difficult to achieve within such short windows. Yet these temporal constraints often lay outside the control of the researchers, given the need to adapt the activities to the rigid schedules of schools or institutional partners.

Revitalising the relationship between youth and democracy, as the model aspires to do, demands slow and sustained rhythms that allow for trust-building, and time for reflecting and revisiting ideas. However, the model had to fit into tight schedules that do not allow to fully explore these crucial moments. This tension between institutional rhythms and participatory methodologies points to a systemic issue that requires rethink collaboration with educational institutions if more impactful outcomes are to be achieved.

- **Institutional frameworks:** Again, as in PAR Cycle 1, the institutional environments in which the labs were embedded also presented significant methodological tensions. When implemented within formal school contexts, the participatory ethos of the CCLAB model often clashed with traditional school structures and expectations. For example, in Vapor Molí (UB) and Norssi (OULU), students framed the labs as curricular tasks rather than opportunities for creative, autonomous exploration. Similarly, in Ars Electronica labs, although the pre-established podcast format was appreciated for its accessibility, it did not resonate with all participants—particularly those with a background in visual arts, who felt that their strengths and interests were not fully activated. Moreover, a friction was observed between the flexible, exploratory nature of the CCLAB methodology and the more rigid pedagogical styles of some teaching staff. Teachers accustomed to structured, teacher-led classrooms encountered difficulties in adapting to a model that embraced openness, co-creation, and uncertainty. This pedagogical dissonance led to moments of confusion, hesitation, and even resistance, both for educators and students.
- **Spatial constraints:** Closely related to the previous issue, there were a number of spatial limitations that affected the quality of the participants' experience. In several labs, including OpenLab (AE), Can Fabra (UB), and Vapor Molí (UB), participants reported challenges stemming from the physical settings of the activities. Ambient

noise, lack of dedicated space, and general discomfort were frequently mentioned as obstacles to concentration and open dialogue. In some cases, the use of regular classrooms as the site of the labs blurred the boundaries between the experimental and the conventional. This led participants to perceive the lab as “just another school task,” thus weakening their sense of ownership and reducing their intrinsic motivation. The spatial context, far from being a neutral backdrop, shaped the atmosphere of the labs and influenced how students engaged with the process. Future iterations of the model must consider the importance of creating spaces that invite openness, collaboration, and imagination.

- **The tension between freedom and guidance:** One relevant tension that emerged across the CCLAB experiences was the delicate balance between fostering autonomy and providing sufficient structure. Central to the CCLAB model was the intention to empower young people as active agents of change, encouraging them to take ownership of their learning and research processes. However, in several cases this commitment to autonomy risked leaving participants unsure of how to proceed and, at times, disengaged. Many participants expressed confusion in the absence of clear instructions. Coming from school environments where they are generally told what to do and how to do it, the open-ended nature of CCLAB activities was perceived by some as overly abstract or ambiguous. This was particularly evident in exercises that demanded critical reflection or imaginative efforts. In BAU (UB), for instance, a student openly reflected that she would have welcomed more guidance on how to approach research tasks. Such moments illustrate that while freedom can be liberating, it can also be paralyzing. This tension was also felt by the educational teams, who, in some cases, faced significant challenges in maintaining group engagement, especially when participants struggled to grasp the purpose or process of an activity.
- **Lack of Clarity in Communication:** Another recurring difficulty was the lack of clarity in the communication of the objectives of each session by researchers. Some participants expressed confusion about what was expected of them. In several labs the disconnection between proposed activities and the lack of an explicit narrative linking them together made it difficult to understand the overall purpose of the lab. Students pointed out that in some cases they would have found it more useful if the common thread between the different sessions had been made more evident. These

perceptions point to the need to explain more explicitly the purpose of each activity, or to be clearer from the outset about the purpose of each activity before proposing it, as well as its link with the general framework of the lab. One of the recommendations most often repeated by the participants was precisely that of 'explaining why we are doing things' from the beginning of each session, so that the expectations from both sides, participants and dynamisers can be aligned. This is intensified by the lack of time that characterised many of the labs. The limited timeframe not only restricted the possibility of building trusting relationships but also hindered the opportunity to better navigate between freedom and guidance.

- **The tensions between doing and thinking:** Although the CCLAB model explicitly aimed to embed reflection throughout the entire process, in practice, many students still perceived a divide between action and reflection. Activities requiring deeper cognitive engagement were often experienced as disconnected or overly abstract, which sometimes led to disengagement. In contrast, more hands-on tasks, especially those rooted in participants' everyday experiences, ended to foster greater interest and involvement. These findings underscore the challenge of ensuring that doing and thinking are not only conceptually integrated but also perceived as such by participants, pointing to the need for more seamless design strategies in future interventions
- **Tension between process and product:** Although the CCLAB model did not explicitly require the production of a concrete, physical outcome, the expectation of delivering a final product often became an implicit goal. This pressure generated a tension between dedicating time to the process itself and steering it toward a tangible result. Within this tension, several issues emerged. On one hand, having a visible outcome can serve as a strong motivator for students, offering a sense of achievement and closure. On the other hand, the desire to produce something concrete often came at the expense of reflection, slowing down, and embracing uncertainty. In some labs it led to an unintended slide into a logic of productivism, where the value of the process was overshadowed by the urgency to deliver a final product. These dynamics call for a careful reflection around the goals of the model and the balance between process-oriented learning and expectations of productivity.

5.6 Evaluation of the Competences Framework

To evaluate the learning objectives and the competence model presented in Section 4.1.1, we carried out a triangulation process combining the feedback from consortium partners with the insights gathered through the validation protocol applied with both educators and young participants involved in PAR cycles 1 and 2.

From the partners' perspective, the definition of competences proved useful in clarifying the objectives of each lab and aligning the methodological design of the activities. However, some partners also noted that the interpretation of certain competences occasionally led to conceptual overlaps. This was particularly evident in the report of researchers' diaries, where critical incidents often emerged at the intersection of multiple competences, making it difficult to attribute them to a single category (For instance, some of the critical incidents that emerged during the debates could be interpreted as fitting both the 'Openness to other beliefs, worldviews and practices' competence and the 'Democratic disposition' competence. This overlap made it challenging to clearly distinguish between the two, as the situations often involved elements of both intercultural sensitivity and democratic engagement). On the other hand, in terms of carrying out the cross-cutting analysis of the different labs, structuring the reporting format around competences allowed for a more precise observation of students' lived experiences, perceptions, and voices. Furthermore, it also helped in identifying and attending to subtle signs of learning and engagement that occurred in each lab.

From the perspective of the teachers who participated in the co-definition of key competences for each Critical ChangeLab, similar reflections were also collected. While they appreciated the clarity the competence framework brought to the planning process, they also pointed out recurring overlaps between certain categories. For example, *Openness to Other Beliefs* was often perceived as part of *Democratic Disposition*, and *Research Competence* was seen as closely linked to *Transformative Agency*. Likewise, the distinction between *Imaginative* and *Creative Competence* was not always clear. Despite these challenges, educators were able to identify and prioritise competences that best responded to the specific context and needs of their student groups. In most cases, the competences selected as most relevant included *Knowledge and Critical Understanding of the World*, *Openness to Other Beliefs, Worldviews and Practices*, and *Transformative Agency and Democratic Disposition*. For instance, in the Loutra lab (LATRA), teachers emphasised

the importance of fostering these competences, given the pressing need to promote inclusion and active citizenship in the complex social context of Lesvos. Similarly, educators from UDNZ (ISRZ) and Can Fabra (UB) placed particular emphasis on *Transformative Agency*, noting that students often express a desire to change things that concern them but lack the tools or opportunities to act. They highlighted the importance of enabling students to develop projects that go beyond classroom exercises, actions that engage with their environment and have a tangible impact, rather than remaining speculative or symbolic.

Finally, for the perspective of youth participants, the process of co-defining competences with them revealed certain challenges. Although efforts were made to simplify the descriptions and translate them into local languages, many students found the activity abstract and difficult to relate to. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the competences most frequently selected by young people were those related to *Creative and Imaginative Capacities*, as well as *Critical Understanding of the World*.

In conclusion, the competence model contributed to greater methodological and evaluative clarity and facilitated more coherent decision-making processes between researchers and educators. However, the findings also point to the need for a revision of the model to make it more operational and to reduce conceptual overlaps, ensuring that it remains both meaningful and accessible to all participants.

6. Second Redesign Iteration: Areas of Improvements for PAR Cycle 3

The second implementation and evaluation process provided an opportunity to address several issues identified during the first iteration (see Section 4). At the same time, it allowed to both confirm and deepen the insights previously gathered. These findings were shared with the consortium to inform the design improvements of the third PAR cycle. As a result, the remarks focused on the following aspects:

- Revision of the competence model.
- Stronger integration of youth's voices, experiences, and ways of doing into the model.
- Strengthening the methodological structure of the CCLAB model.

The following sections detail each of these aspects.

6.1 Revising the Competence Model

In the first PAR cycle, the need to build a shared understanding of learning and expected learning outcomes was identified as central. To this end a set of learning goals and a competence model was defined. In the second PAR cycle, the competence model proved valuable in enhancing both methodological and evaluative clarity, as it facilitated more coherent decision-making processes among researchers and educators. Its use in planning and evaluation also enabled a more comprehensive approach to observing learning processes within the CCLAB and to tracking relevant changes in participants' learning.

However, the evaluation of the competence model with researchers, educators, and youth also highlighted important limitations. In particular, the model required revision to become more operational and to reduce conceptual overlaps.

Building on this need, a review of the competence framework was carried out. Specifically, the number of competences was reduced to four, clustering together those that showed significant conceptual intersections. The competences prioritised were:

- Critical understanding of the world
- Imaginative and creative
- Transformative agency
- Democratic disposition

Table 14 presents the details of each competence and its sub-dimensions. This modification was also reflected in the design of the researchers' diaries.

Table 14. Revised version of the Competence Model

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
<p>Critical Understanding of the World Competence. This competence involves critically analysing and investigating eco-social issues by identifying tensions, conflicts, and historical influences. It emphasises recognising interconnected challenges, questioning power structures, and addressing inequalities. Additionally, it includes formulating research questions, understanding diverse research methods, and applying participatory tools to drive meaningful change.</p>	<p>Conflict Recognition Competence. Ability to identify conflicts and contradictions in everyday life.</p>
	<p>Critical Assessment Competence. Ability to critically assess the implications of defined phenomena on their everyday experiences and those of their community.</p>
	<p>Historical Analysis Competence. Ability to investigate and understand the historical trajectories that have shaped current situations and issues, linking past events to present conditions.</p>
	<p>Systems Thinking Competence. Capability to recognise and analyse the complex network of interrelated conflicts and contradictions, understanding the interconnected nature of eco-social phenomena.</p>
	<p>Critical Power Analysis Competence. Ability to identify and critically understand and challenge power relations and sources of inequalities within specific phenomena.</p>
	<p>Research Question Formulation Competence. Ability to identify, articulate, and formulate</p>

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
	<p>research questions that are relevant and responsive to community needs and interests.</p> <p>Research Approaches Competence. Understanding of various research approaches and methods, demonstrating the ability to select appropriate strategies for investigating and understanding specific topics.</p> <p>Participatory Research Methods Competence. Proficiency in applying and experimenting with participatory research tools, such as community mapping, photovoice, and participatory workshops, etc. to actively engage communities in the research process.</p>
<p>Imaginative and Creative Competence. This competence centres on envisioning alternatives beyond existing paradigms by questioning assumptions, exploring unconventional possibilities, and engaging with the creative and political potential of "What if?" scenarios. It fosters the ability to imagine alternative futures that transcend current limitations. Additionally, it emphasises using artistic and creative resources to expose tensions, highlight issues, and enhance participation in deliberative processes. By challenging conventional thinking, generating innovative ideas.</p>	<p>Creative and Critical Inquiry Competence. Ability to explore the political and creative potential of "What if?" questions, using them as tools to imagine alternative scenarios.</p> <p>Futures Imagination Competence. Skill in imagining possible worlds and futures beyond current constraints, demonstrating the ability to think creatively about alternatives to the present.</p> <p>Challenging Existing Paradigms Competence. Proficiency in questioning assumptions and accepted norms and thinking about unestablished and unconventional possibilities, fostering critical thinking, innovation, and the ability to disrupt conventional perspectives.</p> <p>Creative Inquiry of Social Issues. Ability to use creative and artistic resources to investigate, highlight, and make visible tensions, issues, and contradictions in various contexts.</p> <p>Creative approaches for Inclusive Engagement. Skill in employing creative and artistic approaches to make participation and</p>

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
	deliberative processes more accessible, inclusive, and engaging for diverse groups.
	<p>Creative Facilitation for Collective Decision-Making. Capacity to utilise creative methods to facilitate collective decision-making and fostering collaboration.</p>
	<p>Challenging Norms Through Creative Approaches. Capacity in using artistic and creative resources to challenge existing thinking habits and generate novel ideas</p>
	<p>Creative Facilitation for Community Engagement. Ability to use creative and artistic practices to facilitate socially engaged initiatives, encouraging community involvement and dialogue.</p>
	<p>Creative Facilitation for Local transformation. Ability to apply creative and artistic resources to support and drive transformative processes within local contexts.</p>
<p>Transformative Agency Competence. This competence focuses on the ability to model new solutions and bring ideas for real life change. It involves skills in identifying and articulating clear pathways for justice-oriented change and planning actions to achieve these goals. It includes selecting the most appropriate tools, methods, and resources for effective implementation, adopting a proactive approach, and taking practical steps. Additionally, it emphasises the importance of identifying, fostering, and maintaining collaborations with key stakeholders to work toward shared objectives.</p>	<p>Change Pathway Identification Competence. Ability to identify and articulate clear pathways and planning actions for bringing about justice-oriented change within various contexts</p>
	<p>Resources and Method Selection Competence. Ability to identify and select the most appropriate tools, methods, and resources to effectively achieve proposed goals.</p>
	<p>Action Initiation Competence. Ability to have a proactive approach and take practical actions that drive meaningful change.</p>
	<p>Collaborative Networking Competence. Capacity to identify, seek, foster, and maintain collaboration with other stakeholders to work towards shared goals and collective actions.</p>

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
<p>Democratic Disposition Competence. This competence encompasses the attitudes and skills necessary to foster democratic practices and engage in political participation. It involves experiencing, reflecting on, and critically navigating the complexities of democracy while cultivating essential democratic values. Key aspects include recognising and assessing democratic principles in practice, advocating for their reinforcement, and implementing strategies to strengthen engagement. It also emphasises openness to diverse perspectives, curiosity about different worldviews, and a commitment to listening to marginalised voices. This competence requires the ability to identify biases, adopt multiple viewpoints, and remain flexible in revising one’s perspectives based on new insights.</p>	<p>Democratic Reflection Competence: Ability to experience, reflect on, and critically engage with the complexities of democratic practices, understanding the challenges involved.</p>
	<p>Democratic Attitude Competence: Capacity to cultivate attitudes essential to democracy, such as collective decision making, active participation, mutual respect, inclusivity, and collaboration.</p>
	<p>Democratic Awareness Competence: Proficiency in recognizing and assessing the presence or absence of democratic practices and values within various contexts</p>
	<p>Democratic Advocacy Competence: Ability to advocate and use practical strategies to promote and reinforce democratic practices in various contexts.</p>
	<p>Bias Identification Competence: Skill in identifying and recognizing biases within various worldviews, including anthropocentrism, eurocentrism, colonialism, and other dominant perspectives.</p>
	<p>Perspective-Taking Competence: Ability to understand, reflect on, appreciate and inhabit multiple, potentially contradictory perspectives and worldviews related to a topic, demonstrating an understanding of diverse viewpoints on a given topic.</p>
	<p>Marginalized Voices Inclusion Competence: Commitment to actively seeking, listening to, and integrating voices that have been marginalized to build a more inclusive understanding of issues.</p>
<p>Adaptive Perspective Competence: Openness and flexibility to change one’s perspectives and</p>	

Competence	Competence Sub-Dimensions
	opinions based on new information, understanding, and dialogues with others, demonstrating a willingness to adapt and grow.

6.2 Integrating of Youth’s Voices, Experiences, and Ways of Doing into the Model

The second PAR cycle confirmed initial findings regarding youth perspectives and allowed for a deeper understanding of how young people perceive eco-social phenomena, democracy, and their own agency. This understanding is essential to more consistently integrate their voices, experiences, and ways of doing into the design of the model. The following issues emerged as particularly relevant:

- Participants expressed a strong preference for addressing issues that directly affect their everyday lives (e.g., family, school, community), rather than abstract global challenges.
- Many participants struggled to understand systemic interconnections, often focusing on individualistic perspectives without fully grasping the complex, interrelated nature of social and ecological issues.
- There was a clear preference for hands-on and practical activities, while motivation for deliberation and reflection remained relatively low.
- Artistic and creative methods were especially well received, offering alternative modes of expression beyond traditional academic formats.
- Activities connected to contexts outside the institution were particularly meaningful in fostering students’ engagement and sense of purpose.
- As already noted in PAR Cycle 1, students’ sense of agency remains weak: they often feel their voices are undervalued by adults and perceive themselves as peripheral actors in processes of social change.

- Participants showed limited capacity to imagine alternative futures, highlighting the need for educational strategies that foster future-oriented thinking.
- In both the first and second PAR cycles, initial signals indicated that gender, migration background, and socio-economic conditions play a role in shaping children's participation.

In response to these findings, the third phase of the project placed emphasis on the following directions:

- Implementing strategies that recognise the importance of young people's situated experiences.
- Developing approaches to help move from individualistic perspectives toward shared and systemic understandings.
- Placing stronger emphasis on experiential and creative methods as a way to sustain engagement, bridge the gap between theory and practice, and concretise abstract concepts.
- Exploring more targeted and supportive strategies to facilitate the imagining of alternative futures.
- Paying closer attention in the evaluation to youth involvement, not only in terms of participation but also regarding the quality, intensity, and forms of engagement throughout the process.
- Placing a greater emphasis on exploring how intersectional dimensions influence the opportunities, challenges, and forms of engagement experienced by participants.

6.3 Strengthening the Methodological Structure of the CCLAB Model

In terms of the model's sustainability, a clear need emerged for a more defined methodological structure to facilitate meaningful and reliable implementation by educators. This requires framing the model in a way that balances flexibility and adaptability to diverse

contexts with the provision of clearer, practical guidelines that enable teachers to enact it autonomously. Concretely, the reconfiguration involves integrating the different methods into the model's architecture so that pedagogical choices, implementation procedures, relational dynamics, and the tensions, challenges, and opportunities that surface in each phase are made explicit and navigable for practitioners.

7. Evaluation of PAR Cycle 3

7.1 Description of the Labs and KPIs

A total of **21** Critical ChangeLabs were implemented during PAR Cycle 3 across eleven countries (summarized in Table 15): Finland (OULU), Spain (UB), Ireland (TCD), the Netherlands (WAAG), Austria (AE), Slovenia (KI), France (EUROALTER), Italy (EUROALTER), Greece (LATRA), and Croatia (ISRZ). In total **526** young people participated in the labs (Table 16).

Table 15. Overview of PAR Cycle 3 Labs

Partner	Lab	Location	N. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
Trinity College Dublin	Coláiste Bríde Secondary School	Dublin, Ireland	10	Social injustice and future visions of the community	24 female participants ages between 15 and 16 years old.
Trinity College Dublin	Design Your Future City	Dublin, Ireland	5	The Future of Dublin	19 participants (12 female and 7 male) ages between 16 and 16 years old.
Trinity College Dublin	Design Your Future Fingal	Dublin, Ireland	5	Designing Futures	16 participants (4 male, 12 female), aged 15 and 16 years old.
Trinity College Dublin	Treoraigh do Thodchaí	Galway, Ireland	5	The Future of their Area	20 white Irish-speaking participants aged 15–17 (gender not informed)
University of Oulu	AI Ambassadors	Oulu, Finland	10	AI in decision making	20 participants (11 female, 9 male), ages between 15–17-year-old; 9 from immigrant background.

Partner	Lab	Location	N. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
University of Oulu	Auta Lasta	Oulu, Finland	1	Making activist jewellery	4 participants (3 female and 1 male), ages 16 to 18.
European Alternatives	YOLK - Palermo	Palermo	2	Gender stereotypes	10 participants ages between 11 and 13 (gender not informed) .
European Alternatives	Lycée Michel Ange	Villeneuve La Garenne, France	3	Artificial intelligence	18 participants aged 17 and 18 years old (gender not informed).
European Alternatives	Pablo Neruda - Pierrefitte	Pierrefitte, France	5	Artificial intelligence	22 participants aged 14 and 15 years old (gender not informed).
LATRA	Mytilene and Kalloni Elementary School	Lesvos, Greece	13	Justice and Inclusion	160 children:11-year-old participants (gender not informed).
Institute for Social Research	UDDP	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Food waste	10 female participants between 15 and 18 years old.
Institute for Social Research	UDNZ	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Substance use and addiction (focus on marijuana use)	11 participants: gender-diverse, ages between 15 and 18 years old.
Institute for Social Research	UDMJ	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Mental Health, self perception and expectations of others	13 female participants between 15 and 18 years old.
Ars Electronica	Europaschule Linz	Linz, Austria	4	Conflict resolution	22 participants (14 male, 8 female)

Partner	Lab	Location	N. of Sessions	Topic	Participant Demographics
				strategies in the classroom	ages between 14 and 15 years old.
Ars Electronica	Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner	Traun, Upper Austria	2	Envisioning Futures	17 participants (15 male, 2 female) ages between 17 and 18 years old.
Ars Electronica	Verein Saum	Perg/Linz surroundings, Upper Austria	4	The Future of Work	16 participants (14 male, 2 female) ages between 16 and 18 years old.
Kersnikova	DemoBot- Skupna Točka – Medgeneracijski center	Ljubljana, Slovenia	8	Democracy and how technology plays a part in it.	34 participants (22 male, 12 female), ages ranged between 11 and 15 years old.
Waag Futurelab	Don Bosco	Volendam, Netherlands	4	Disinformation and democracy	16 female participants, aged 14 and 15.
Waag Futurelab	Damstede Lyceum	Amsterdam Noord, Netherlands	3	Disinformation and democracy	17 participants (10 male, 7 female) ages 14 and 15 years old.
University of Barcelona	Pineda High School Institute	Pineda de Mar, Barcelona, Spain	6	Democracy and digital technologies	16 participants (3 female and 13 male) aged 16 and 17 years old.
University of Barcelona	Trinitat Nova, Group T	Barcelona, Spain	5	Injustices within educational centers	20 students (10 female and 10 male) ages between 15 and 16 years old.
University of Barcelona	Trinitat Nova, Group N	Barcelona, Spain	5	Injustices within educational centers	20 students (12 female and 8 male) ages between 15 and 16 years old.

Table 16. *Participants in PAR Cycle 3*

	Finland	Spain	Ireland	The Netherlands	Austria	Slovenia	France	Greece	Croatia	Total
Young people	24	59	80	40	53	36	40	160	34	526
Educators	4	4	20	8	8	4	4	10	2	64
CCLAB team members	6	4	4	3	2	2	5	3	7	36
Others^A	5	1	2	0	3	2	3	3	4	23

Note: ^AOthers include institutional and NGO representatives, as well as other pedagogical agents.

Additionally, **8** external labs were coordinated by Tactical Tech and carried out at the following locations: Dedal Art School (Varna, Bulgaria), Liceul Teoretic de Informatică “Grigore Moisil” (Iași, Romania), Center for Teacher Education, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade (Belgrade, Serbia), Dijital Esenlik at Hisar Schools (Istanbul, Turkey), Televele Media Education Association at Bethlen Gábor Általános Iskola és Gimnázium (Budapest, Hungary), First Lab at FEZ Berlin at Sartre Gymnasium (Berlin, Germany), Second Lab at FEZ Berlin at Sartre Gymnasium (Berlin, Germany) and Criar Cidade at Associação de Moradores do Bairro Horizonte (Portugal). These external labs are not included in this report due to the absence of detailed evaluation data.

Since the detailed description of each lab has already been reported in the Deliverable 2.1, the following section only provides general descriptions of the internal labs conducted to contextualise the evaluation process.

LAB #1 (TCD - Coláiste Bríde): This lab took place at Coláiste Bríde, an all-girls secondary school in Clondalkin, a socioeconomically disadvantaged suburb of Dublin. Participants included 24 female students aged 15 and 16 from mixed ethnic backgrounds. Initially, the focus was on poverty, but after the first session, the topic shifted to social injustice more broadly, to avoid excessive negativity about the local area while highlighting community achievements. The adjustment aimed to balance critique with empowerment, ensuring the

lab remained constructive and celebratory of resilience. The lab lasted **10** sessions and prioritized youth perspectives while navigating sensitive local realities.

LAB #2 (TCD - DYFC): The Design Your Future City (DYFC) programme, run by the Academy of the Near Future, engaged 19 transition-year students in a weeklong non-formal initiative exploring Dublin's future (technology, sustainability, community). Five 6-hour sessions fostered youth agency, with participants reporting increased confidence in their voices and ideas. Stakeholders like Smart Dublin, Dublin City Council, CONNECT, and Trinity Sustainability sponsored and led workshops. The voluntary, experiential format emphasised practical impact, with students feeling their proposals were valued. The programme successfully blended youth empowerment with real-world civic engagement.

LAB #3 (TCD - DYFF): The Academy of the Near Future, in partnership with Fingal County Council, hosted a weeklong youth programme Design Your Future Fingan (DYFF) at Balbriggan Library and The Lark Theatre, engaging 16 participants aged 15–16 from North Dublin's Fingal region. Through five intensive six-hour sessions focused on speculative future design, the programme highlighted the transformative role of facilitation style in fostering youth agency. While students gained confidence in ideation, feedback revealed challenges in aligning their speculative proposals with the council's budgetary and policy constraints, underscoring the need to recalibrate stakeholder expectations for future iterations. The experience illuminated both the potential of youth-led design and the complexities of institutional collaboration.

LAB #4 (TCD): Treoraigh do Thodchaí, a phrase that means "steer your future" in Irish, was a lab held in Spidéal, Connemara, involving 20 white Irish-speaking participants aged 15–17. Partners included the Academy of the Near Future, and Gael Linn, an organization promoting Irish language and culture. Conducted entirely in Irish, the lab aimed to normalize learning about sustainability, technology, and futures thinking through the participants' everyday language, Irish. Activities emphasized cultural heritage and Irish traditional arts. Youth prototyped innovations addressing personal challenges like mental and physical health, with one project exploring technology to promote everyday use of Irish across Ireland.²

² Due to the absence of researcher observations, this lab was not considered for the PAR Cycle 3 evaluation process.

LAB #5 (OULU – AI Ambassadors): The University of Oulu’s AI Ambassadors programme, led by the INTERACT research team, engaged 20 participants with an age ranging between 15 and 17 years old, in a two-week lab on AI and Decision-Making. Organised with Oulu Municipality and partners like FabLab Oulu and child welfare groups, the project blended debates, design tasks, and media creation to connect AI to daily life. While the safe space fostered open dialogue, participants’ reactions varied: some embraced self-management confidently, others felt unsettled by the autonomy. The mix of structured guidance and creative freedom proved effective for engagement, though adaptability to different comfort levels remained a learning point.

LAB #6 (OULU – Auta Lasta): On May 26, 2025, a two-hour lab was held at Auta Lasta foster home in Oulu, Finland, engaging four participants: 3 girls, 1 boy, ages between 16 and 18. Collaborators from the University of Oulu and Fab Lab Oulu brought a mobile digital fabrication workshop to the participants’ familiar space, fostering trust. While the research team set the framework, content was youth-directed, allowing complete creative freedom. The familiar environment enhanced engagement, and digital fabrication served as both an expressive and therapeutic tool. Though the session was impactful, future iterations could deepen reflection with structured group discussions given more time.

LAB #7 (EUROALTER – YOLK): At YOLK, a non-profit association in Palermo, Italy, 10 middle school students, age range between 11 and 13 from the working-class neighbourhood of Via Montalbo, participated in a lab on gender stereotypes. The lab was introduced during a regular circle dialogue session and was met with enthusiasm. The students had already been involved in YOLK’s after-school programme, which includes sports, group discussions on local issues, and academic support aimed at preventing school dropout. The lab built on this structure, fostering reflection and engagement through a trusted, participatory environment.

LAB #8 (EUROALTER – Lycée Michel Ange): At Lycée Michel Ange in Villeneuve-la-Garenne, a working-class suburb of Paris, 18 students aged 17 and 18 participated in a two-session CCLAB focused on the use of artificial intelligence in daily and school life. The topic was pre-defined in agreement with the teacher, reflecting concerns about how AI is reshaping learning processes. The first session was held at European Alternatives’ headquarters in Paris, and another one the second at the school. The area’s social inequalities provided a relevant backdrop for discussing technological change and education.

LAB #9 (EUROALTER – Pablo Neruda): At Pablo Neruda Middle School in Pierrefitte-sur-Seine, a lab was held with 24 students aged between 15 and 16 in a REP+ school, serving a socially and economically disadvantaged community. The topic of the lab, AI, was chosen previously by facilitators due to time constraints. Conducted over five two-hour sessions, it was implemented in partnership with Citoyenneté Jeunesse, a popular education association promoting critical thinking through arts and culture among youth in Seine-Saint-Denis and Île-de-France.

LAB #10 (LATRA – Mytilene and Kalloni): This lab was conducted in two rural elementary schools (Mytilene and Kalloni) and engaged children aged 9 to 12 from low-income backgrounds, including refugees (15%) and unaccompanied minors (5%). It focused on Justice and Inclusion, and the theme was selected based on PAR Cycle 2 evaluations and stakeholder input. Researchers employed creative workshops and a child-adapted Animal Farm performance to explore these topics. The remote geographic location and socio-economic context shaped the participants' perspectives. The intervention aimed to address systemic inequities while centring youth voices through participatory arts-based methods.

LAB #11 (ISRZ – UDDP): At the Dora Pejačević student dormitory in Zagreb (UDDP), nine girls aged between 15 and 18 participated in a lab focused on food waste. The theme emerged from the participants' own interests and aimed to address food waste across the entire supply chain, from production to consumption. Meetings were held informally after dinner. While the institution had taken part in a previous PAR cycle, most participants were new. The initiative was facilitated through collaboration with dormitory educators and staff familiar with the programme.

LAB # 12 (ISRZ – UDNZ): At the Novi Zagreb student residence (UDNZ), 10 upper secondary students (mixed gender and aged between 15 and 18 from various Croatian regions) participated in a lab focused on substance addiction, specifically marijuana use. Participants, enrolled in different vocational and academic programmes, live in the dormitory while studying in Zagreb. Most had taken part in the previous PAR cycle. The topic was chosen collectively during the first session. Meetings were informal and held after dinner. The activity was promoted internally by dormitory educators, who had previously collaborated with the research team.

LAB # 13 (ISRZ – UDMJ): At the Marija Jambrišak student dormitory (UDMJ), 13 female high school students (mostly aged 15 and 16), participated in a lab focused on mental health,

specifically self-perception and other people's expectations. The topic was democratically chosen by the group. Participants expressed strong interest in developing all competences, particularly critical understanding of the world and imaginative thinking, which they saw as essential for meaningful change. While democratic competences and transformative agency were also valued, students felt these could not be developed without first strengthening critical and creative capacities.

LAB #14 (AE - Europaschule): At Europaschule Linz, a lab was integrated into the formal curriculum for 22 students aged 14 and 15 over three sessions. The focus was on improving conflict management, in response to the teacher's concerns about classroom disruptions, difficulties in self-regulation, and gender imbalances in participation. The workshop aimed to support more equitable dialogue and culminated in the co-creation of a Classroom Agreement, signed by students and teachers, with the option to present it to the Student Parliament to influence school-wide norms.

LAB #15 (AE - Schulungszentrum): At Schulungszentrum, a non-formal education centre for unemployed youth, 17 participants with ages between 14 and 18 took part in a two-session lab focused on "Envisioning Futures.". The goal was to foster imaginative and critical thinking. Staff noted that many students struggle to see beyond their individual circumstances or recognise their agency in shaping their futures. The lab aimed to strengthen critical engagement, particularly in how youth consume and interpret media and the world around them.

LAB #16 (AE - Verein Saum): At Verein Saum, a programme for unemployed youth in Upper Austria, 16 participants, ages between 16 and 18, engaged in a four-session lab on "The Future of Work." Introduced via Ars Electronica's partnership with the Austrian Public Employment Service, this was the first collaboration with the organisation. The lab focused on building creative and imaginative skills in participants facing mental health and socioeconomic challenges. This was in response to educators' concerns that these participants struggled to envision long-term futures and recognise their own capacity to create change, particularly in the post-pandemic context.

LAB #17 (KI - Skupna Točka): At Skupna Točka – Medgeneracijski center, a non-formal after-school programme run by the Zveza Anite Ogulin humanitarian organization, 36 children aged between 12 and 14 participated in "DemoBot", an eight-session lab on "Democracy and technology". The group, who had diverse economic and national

backgrounds, was one-third female. Initially intended to develop a chatbot, the project shifted toward building a game console based on participants' interests. This flexible, participant-driven approach significantly boosted engagement and highlighted the importance of adapting to children's needs in educational design.

LAB #18 (WAAG - Damstede Lyceum): This lab took place at Damstede Lyceum in Amsterdam Noord, a socioeconomically disadvantaged area. Seventeen students aged 14 and 15 from diverse ethnic and subcultural backgrounds participated in three two-hour sessions on game design addressing disinformation's threat to democracy. The project involved key stakeholders such as UNESCO (contributing media literacy expertise), a philosophy professor from Corderius College, a Media and Technology student, and an Arts and Design teacher, who co-developed materials and observed the process. The mix of institutional support and youth creativity fostered engagement, though the complex theme required careful facilitation to bridge abstract concepts with students' lived experiences in a challenged community.

LAB #19 (WAAG - Don Bosco): This lab was conducted at Don Bosco School in Volendam with 16 girls aged 14 and 15 from a social studies class. As in the Damstede Lyceum, students also explored the topic "Disinformation and its impact on democracy," throughout four sessions. The lab's theme was chosen by their teacher to enhance media literacy. UNESCO also contributed media education expertise, while a Corderius College philosophy professor helped develop the curriculum. A Media and Technology student also participated as an observer. The project successfully combined institutional knowledge with student perspectives, though the gender homogeneity and predetermined topic presented both unique opportunities and limitations for participatory engagement.

LAB #20 (UB - Pineda): The lab in Pineda de Mar Institute was developed within the framework of an optional course on Citizenship, Politics, and Law, with a group of 16 students between the ages of 16 and 17. The main objective was to explore, together with the young people, the relationships between digital technology and democracy. This topic was chosen by the course teacher. Students focused more on digital tech's personal effects than societal impacts. The curriculum-mandated topic felt imposed, lowering their motivation and engagement in the project.

LAB #21 (UB - Trinitat Nova T): The lab at Trinitat Nova Middle School focused on "Injustices in the school context," aligning with the History curriculum on "Democracy and Modern

World” unit, a content the teacher had expressly added to the official syllabus. Technological themes were deprioritised to emphasise youth expression and democratic values. Group T exhibited a creative and chaotic energy yet had the ability to work well together. The process provided participants a space to vent frustrations about perceived injustices in their immediate environment.

LAB #22 (UB - Trinitat Nova N): As in the previous lab at Trinitat Nova Middle School, Group N also worked with the topic of “Injustices in the School Context”. The history teacher taught both groups but was also in charge of tutoring Group N. During a previous interview he shared an underlying school harassment situation that affected this group specifically. This persistent bullying issue undermined group cohesion, leaving one student isolated. Despite calm appearances, collective emotional intelligence gaps prevented constructive conflict resolution or collaborative problem-solving throughout the lab.³

7.2 Evaluation Approach, Methods, and Instruments

To evaluate the implementation of the model across different partner contexts, a cross-cutting analysis was conducted based on the materials submitted by each partner. These materials included: researchers’ diaries; reports from focus groups with young people, and reports from interviews with teachers. A total of 21 labs were included in the analysis, excluding the Treoraigh do Thodchaí lab (TCD) due to absence of evaluation information.

This final stage of evaluation served a dual purpose. On the one hand, it had a formative aim: to contribute to the iterative refinement of the CCLAB model by generating insights that can inform its redesign and adaptation to new contexts. In this sense, it sought to produce actionable knowledge for practitioners engaged in participatory processes, offering them flexible yet grounded frameworks to guide their practice. On the other hand, it pursued a critical and reflective aim: to examine our practices within the labs, uncovering tensions and challenges that emerged along the way. To this end, the evaluation focused on the following key dimensions.

³ Due to the qualitative differences between the groups T and N, the Trinitat Nova CCLAB is analyzed as two different labs. It is worth noting that Deliverable 2.2 reports it as a single lab.

1. **Implementation of the model:** Examining how the different phases were enacted across partner institutions, with particular attention to:
 - **Key pedagogical moments:** understood as critical junctures in the process that highlight essential aspects of learning and its goals.
 - **Strategies:** the overarching approaches employed in key pedagogical moments to achieve specific educational objectives.
 - **Methods:** concrete techniques used to support learning goals connected to the broader strategies.
 - **Strengths and opportunities:** the observed benefits and potential generated by particular strategies and methods.
 - **Challenges:** the tensions, difficulties, and issues encountered by facilitators and researchers throughout the process.

2. **Broader pedagogical reflections:** Analysing cross-cutting insights that emerged during implementation, with the aim of assessing the coherence, adaptability, and long-term viability of the model across diverse educational contexts and examining how structural factors—such as gender, migration background, or socioeconomic status—shaped young people’s experiences, with the aim of identifying inequities in participation and reflecting on ways to address them.

7.3 Outcomes of Cross-Cutting Analysis of the PAR Cycle 3

Four researchers conducted the analysis combining a thematic approach using Atlas.ti software with a shared analytical grid aimed at tracing transversal patterns across labs as well as contextual specificities. The following sections present the key findings that emerged.

7.3.1 Question & Analyse Phase

This section explores how the different project partners implemented the Question & Analyse phase within their respective labs. In the original model, this phase is designed to help participants identify the issues generating conflict and contradictions in their everyday lives, while fostering critical thinking. It involves developing a systemic understanding of the

topic, analysing the current democratic dynamics and their historical evolution, and deconstructing preconceptions about democracy by exploring the issue from multiple perspectives. This phase emphasises the co-construction of knowledge, the recognition of tensions within democratic systems, and the questioning of dominant assumptions and norms. It also encourages engagement with diverse voices and contexts in order to critically examine power relations and socio-political inequalities.

7.3.1.1 Defining the Theme of the CCLAB

Defining the theme of a lab constitutes one of the most relevant and sensitive moments in the process. This section presents the diverse strategies adopted by consortium partners to define the themes of their CCLABs, shedding light on the tensions and possibilities that emerge when trying to balance institutional demands with the agency of young participants.

- 1. Theme predefined by educators or researchers:** In some circumstances, the theme was predefined by educators or researchers before the participants joined the process. This was often the case in labs embedded in formal educational settings, where curricular frameworks or institutional objectives required the process to be aligned with certain themes. For instance, in the AI Ambassador programme developed at the University of Oulu, the theme of “Artificial Intelligence and Decision-Making” was introduced from the outset by the research team. A similar dynamic was observed in the Pineda lab (UB), where the theme “Democracy and Digital Technologies” was selected by the teaching staff. In other institutions, such as Europaschule Linz (AE), Lyceé Michel Ange (EUROALTER), Skupna točka (KI), Damstede Lyceum (WAAG) and Don Bosco (WAAG), the themes— “Conflict Resolution in the Classroom”, “AI” and “Disinformation and its Impact on Democracy”—were also defined in advance.
- 2. Broad theme co-shaped with participants:** Other partners adopted a more flexible approach by introducing a broad or general theme that served as a starting point but was then collectively reinterpreted and redefined with the participants. This strategy offered a middle ground between structure and openness. In the DYFC programme developed by TCD, the cycle began with a general focus on “The Future of Dublin” which was later explored and specified by the students through a participatory design process. Similarly, in Coláiste Bríde lab (TCD), the research

process began with a proposed focus on poverty. However, after initial discussions, the team decided to shift the emphasis toward celebrating local achievements, in order to avoid reinforcing deficit-based narratives about the local neighbourhood. In Trinitat Nova T/N labs (UB) and in the Mytilene and Kalloni labs (LATRA), the theme of “Social Injustice” was introduced as a general frame, with participants encouraged to explore how this issue intersected with their realities. A similar strategy was adopted in Schulungszentrum (AE), where the theme “Envisioning Futures” was progressively shaped by the group, and in Verein Saum (AE), where participants explored the idea of “The Future of Work” from their own situated perspectives. To this end, In Schulungszentrum and Verein Saum (AE), a dynamic called Frustration Mapping was used to collect reflections on everyday concerns and future visions. Participants responded anonymously to open-ended prompts through the Mentimeter platform. In Verein Saum, this approach surfaced meaningful themes such as loneliness, independence, financial insecurity, and work, fostering a high level of participation and openness. However, in Schulungszentrum, the same method had mixed results: although using mobile phones initially captured students’ attention, it quickly became a source of distraction. Responses were often superficial or disengaged, and the activity ultimately failed to create a strong connection with the group, or the level of reflection anticipated.

- 3. Fully defined by participants:** Finally, a third group of experiences opted for a fully youth-led approach to theme definition, giving participants complete autonomy to decide what issues they wanted to investigate. This was the case of the CCLABs conducted by ISRZ, where topics such as food waste, mental health, and drug addiction emerged organically from group discussions. These themes were not introduced or suggested by the facilitators but arose from the participants’ lived experiences and concerns. A similar approach was observed in the Auta Lasta lab (OULU), where participants were encouraged to focus the lab entirely on their own interests.

To support the definition process of the lab’s theme with participants, different methodological approaches were employed. These involved the use of affective prompts and creative dynamics aimed at surfacing the participants’ concerns, frustrations, fears, and hopes.

For instance, In the UDDP and UDMJ labs (ISRZ), the first session centered on a brainstorming activity in which educators asked participants to reflect on the struggles and challenges they face in different areas of life, school, the dormitory, their city, and personal experiences. This initial exploration generated a wide range of topics. In the second session, participants engaged in an idea-mapping process. Divided into small groups, they were asked to identify and prioritize three topics of greatest interest. After presenting their selections, the full group engaged in a step-by-step narrowing process, eliminating some ideas, discussing others, and ultimately voting to select one final theme to guide their inquiry.

In the Auta Lasta lab (OULU), the conversation around theme selection began with a single, affective prompt: “What topic matters to you and do you want to make visible?” This open question sparked dialogue on various personal and social issues. These themes were then translated into short slogans and developed into visual messages through the design of activist jewellery and keychains.

In the UDNZ (ISRZ) lab, instead, a more structured dynamic was implemented to help define the theme. A set of pre-formulated topics was printed and displayed visually. The facilitator introduced each one and encouraged students to share comments or propose alternatives. Participants then used post-it notes to identify the issues they found most relevant, creating a collective map of concerns. Through group discussion, they narrowed the list down to three priority topics, followed by a final round of voting to select the theme that would guide the next phase.

7.3.1.1.1 Theme Definition and Participant Engagement

Creating a safe space is the essential key starting point in a CCLAB process. It lays the foundation for steering the lab towards co-defining a theme together—a step that is not only necessary but also a key methodological and strategic challenge, especially when the intention is to place young people’s voices at the centre of the process. The motivations behind how the theme is chosen can vary significantly, depending on the institutional context, time constraints, and the balance of power between facilitators and participants. These structural and temporal conditions often shape the degree of autonomy participants can exercise, as well as the relevance of the themes explored.

In this sense, different approaches to theme definition can impact differently the engagement, level of emotional investment, sense of ownership, and perceived relevance

among young participants. These effects become especially visible when comparing labs that illustrate varying degrees of thematic autonomy and different contextual conditions.

In the case of ISRZ, the third PAR cycle represented a turning point. For the first time, students were granted full autonomy to define the topic they wished to explore. No themes were proposed in advance; instead, participants were encouraged to identify issues that felt both personally meaningful and socially relevant. According to the research team, this shift led to a highly significant process: deeper engagement, more open dialogue, and a stronger sense of agency were observed. The participants selected topics such as food waste, mental health, and drug addiction, issues they believed they could address through collective action, thus reinforcing the connection between research and transformative practice.

In contrast, a clear tension emerged in the Pineda lab (UB), where the theme —*Democracy and Digital Technologies*— was predefined by the teaching team. Researchers reported that this was the only lab carried out by the institution in which the topic had been decided in advance, and as a result, several students struggled to relate to it. The lack of space for thematic negotiation weakened their sense of ownership and, in some cases, reduced their level of engagement. While this approach allowed for thematic coherence and alignment with institutional or project-level goals, it also introduced certain limitations regarding the participants' ability to shape the process from their own perspectives and lived experiences.

A similar situation arose in the Pablo Neruda lab (EUROALTER), where students showed fluctuating interest in the proposed theme of artificial intelligence. In this context, students explicitly expressed that they would have liked to have a say in choosing the topic for discussion during the lab. This comment also resonated with the schoolteacher involved, who reflected that student engagement might have been greater had they been able to choose the topic themselves. Although participants' understanding of the subject improved slightly, she noted that more time would have been needed to explore it in depth and make it truly meaningful to them. Likewise, in the Europaschule Linz lab (AE), the teacher initially chose to focus the lab on Conflict Resolution Within the Classroom. While some of the proposed dynamics worked positively, the attempt to delegate aspects of classroom management to the students clashed with their expectations and the prevailing hierarchical structure of the school environment. This tension prompted a reconsideration of the thematic focus, resulting in significantly higher student engagement. Subsequently,

the lab was redirected to explore the role of school management in conflict resolution, allowing students to critically examine institutional dynamics from a broader perspective.

Another illustrative example is that of Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), where the facilitators proposed the topic *Designing Games about Disinformation and its Impact on Democracy*. At the outset, the researcher noted a marked difference in engagement levels across student groups. While roughly half of the students were motivated and actively participated, the other half responded with disruptive behaviour and absurd comments intended to mock the facilitators. However, as the workshops progressed, the dynamics began to shift. The proposed activities gradually generated greater involvement, and students later reported having enjoyed the experience, describing the game design process as “special” and expressing surprise that research could be both meaningful and fun. A comparable trajectory unfolded in the Don Bosco lab (WAAG), where students initially responded to the proposed themes with reservation and emotional distance. Over time, their involvement improved, although the process had to be heavily scaffolded by facilitators, and a full sense of ownership never fully materialised.

A different scenario can be observed in the AI Ambassador (OULU) and in the DYFF (TCD) labs. In these cases, even if the theme was proposed in advance by the team, participants had voluntarily enrolled in the program, fully aware of its thematic focus. This prior knowledge and self-selection appeared to foster stronger engagement. On such occasions, although the themes were not co-created, the fact that participants had opted in with a clear understanding of the labs’ objectives facilitated meaningful involvement.

7.3.1.1.2 Defining the Theme of the CCLAB: Opportunities and Challenges

The question of who defines the theme of a lab within institutional settings is important. Resistance to granting young people full autonomy in defining the research theme often stems from two main sources. On one hand, PAR projects are frequently embedded in institutional environments, such as schools, where curricular demands and time constraints impose clear boundaries on what can be addressed and how. On the other hand, there is a deeper, more implicit tension related to adult perceptions of youth capacity: allowing students to choose the topic is seen by some educators and researchers as complex, unpredictable, or even risky. These concerns are not only methodological, but also ethical, raising important questions about trust, control, and the role of adult facilitators in participatory processes.

Despite these tensions, the experiences gathered across the CCLABs offer compelling evidence that co-defining research themes with young people is not only feasible, but often highly fruitful, especially when facilitated through carefully designed strategies that enable collective reflection and decision-making. Nonetheless, as the examples of the Damstede Lyceum and Don Bosco (WAAG) labs, pointed out, even in cases where the topic cannot be fully defined a proper scaffolding of the process can help in shifting participants' attitude from initial reluctance toward a stronger compromise.

The considerations point to the fact that there is no single ideal way to define the theme of a lab. Nevertheless, it is crucial to reflect methodologically on this pedagogical choice, as it can play a key role in shaping students' involvement and their subsequent willingness to engage more deeply and actively with the topic.

7.3.1.2 Co-Constructing Knowledge Around the Chosen Topic

Across all labs, regardless of whether the theme was predefined by educators or co-selected by students, the initial stage of the *Question & Analyse* phase was guided by a shared intention: to co-construct knowledge about the topic together with participants, in order to lay the foundations for critical understanding. This shared goal reflects the epistemological stance of the CCLAB model which pursues ways of knowing that move beyond traditional academic approaches and actively seek to collectively construct through dialogue, exploration, and shared inquiry.

In the different contexts, the process of knowledge co-construction pursued different objectives: building a shared and nuanced understanding of the theme; unpacking its complexity and narrowing its focus; assessing how the issue manifests in the participants' everyday lives and identifying the interrelated conflicts, contradictions, and eco-social dynamics embedded within it. Moreover, the process aimed at encouraging participants to explore diverse perspectives, critically reflect on their own assumptions, and eventually reformulate their initial understandings considering new insights.

To meet these objectives, diverse strategies were implemented across the different labs, combining creative methodologies, critical discussions, and experiential practices. These approaches were not only pedagogical tools, but also expressions of an epistemological positioning that values the plurality of ways in which knowledge can be produced. In the following sections, we explore how these epistemic orientations materialized in practice

across the various labs. Through specific examples, we examine how different teams created conditions for co-construction, what methods they used, what the methods enabled and what tensions or challenges they faced. Finally, we will conclude this section by reflecting on the epistemic coherence between the pedagogical framework of the CCLAB model and the ways of knowing enabled.

7.3.1.2.1 Sharing Situated Experiences to Co-Construct Knowledge

Across all the labs analysed in the third round of evaluation, it becomes evident that participants' situated experiences play a central pedagogical role in structuring and planning the sessions. This orientation emerges, on one hand, as a direct response to outcomes from PAR Cycle 2. As highlighted in the previous evaluation, students consistently showed greater interest in topics that intersect with their everyday realities over global challenges perceived as distant or abstract. When young people were invited to engage with topics that connect directly to their identities, environments, and daily lives, their sense of involvement increased, and their agency was strengthened. This premise was clearly embodied in the third PAR cycle, where there is a conscious pedagogical effort to include participants' situated experiences as a legitimate form of knowledge, one that coexists non-hierarchically with other ways of knowing. This implied creating spaces where personal experiences can be shared, discussed, and validated as meaningful contributions to collective sense-making.

From the practices analysed, three specific strategies for leveraging situated experience as a knowledge-building resource can be identified. On the one hand, as described in section 7.3.1.1, personal experiences and concerns were used as starting points to co-define the theme of the lab with participants. On the other hand, situated experiences were directly addressed either to co-construct a shared understanding of the theme or as a means to ground complex or abstract concepts.

Situated Experiences to Build Shared Understanding Around the Topic

One of the foundational moments in every lab is the collective construction of meaning around the theme under exploration. In most of the analysed labs, this process of building a shared understanding does not emerge from abstract definitions or top-down instruction, but rather from the lived, situated experiences of the participants themselves. Across the various

initiatives, we observe how personal narratives, everyday concerns, and embodied knowledge become the starting point for a deeper engagement with complex issues.

At Europaschule Linz (AE), for instance, where the focus was on conflict resolution within the school environment, this approach took shape through the activity “Reflections on School Life”. Students were invited to anonymously respond to prompts such as “What works well at school?” and “What doesn’t work well?”, writing their answers on post-it notes. These reflections were then read aloud and collectively discussed. The anonymity of the format allowed students to speak honestly, while the group discussion helped weave individual insights into a broader understanding of the school’s dynamics, hence allowing to better define the scope of the process.

Similarly, at Pineda (UB), the exploration of digital technologies began with an autobiographical activity: each student created a visual lifeline mapping their relationship with digital tools from childhood to the present. This method opened a space for personal reflection, emotional connection, and collective identification. As participants shared their stories, common concerns surfaced, ranging from device addiction and lack of concentration, to mental health issues such as anxiety and insomnia, and exposure to violent or inappropriate content. The exercise not only helped articulate individual struggles but also revealed shared patterns and systemic challenges to further refine the goals of the lab.

In a similar vein, to explore the issue of injustice, in Trinitat Nova T/N labs (UB), students were asked to write down instances of injustice they had witnessed in school or elsewhere. These contributions were later categorised thematically by researchers, enabling the refining of the focus of their research process.

Situated Experiences to Ground Abstract Concepts

One of the recurring challenges identified during the second PAR cycle was the difficulty many students experienced when trying to engage with abstract or unfamiliar concepts. Issues such as algorithmic bias, democracy, or structural injustice often felt too distant from their immediate realities. In response to this, several labs in the third PAR cycle intentionally turned to students’ situated experiences as an anchor, using personal narratives and concrete examples from their daily lives to build bridges toward conceptual understanding.

A particularly illustrative case is that of Don Bosco (WAAG), where the concept of *filter bubbles* was explored through an activity specifically designed to make the idea tangible and personally relevant. In this activity, students were given a worksheet to map out the brands they follow on social media, the influencers they engage with, the websites they frequent, and the types of advertisements they encounter. On the reverse side, they created a collage that visually represented their personal filter bubble. This creative and introspective exercise laid the groundwork for a group discussion in which students compared their bubbles and reflected collectively on the risks of living in digital echo chambers.

A different yet equally revealing example comes from Mytilene and Kalloni labs (LATRA), where the topic revolved around themes of injustice and democracy. During a classroom dialogue about justice and decision-making, the question: “How are classroom rules decided, and by whom?” leads to a spontaneous exchange that opened a space for reflection among the students, who began to question the extent to which their voices are genuinely considered within school dynamics.

Finally, in Don Bosco (WAAG), Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), Palermo (EUROALTER) and Pablo Neruda (EUROALTER), the lab kick-started by asking students to share their own stories either related to disinformation, gender stereotypes or use of AI. This grounded the discussion in familiarity, making otherwise distant topic more accessible and meaningful.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

These findings underscore the importance of grounding CCLABs in participants’ lived experiences and indicate the need to design learning processes that validate and centre the perspectives and knowledge young people bring from their own lives.

At the same time, this approach reflects an epistemological alignment with the principles of participatory action research, as well as with critical and feminist pedagogies. As bell hooks (2014) argues, transformative pedagogy requires recognising that everyone brings experiential knowledge into the classroom, and that this knowledge can enrich the learning process. She also emphasises that students are more likely to engage when they perceive that the topics addressed directly affect them, and they are more confident in contributing when their lived experience is acknowledged as valid.

While, in most labs using situated experiences as a pedagogical entry point proved highly effective in engaging students and fostering critical dialogue, and grounding abstract

concepts, this approach also revealed certain tensions and challenges that deserve attention. Often, the success of these strategies depended heavily on the conditions of facilitation and the specific dynamics of each group.

In certain situations, participants were reluctant to share personal reflections, particularly when discussions touched on sensitive topics. This issue was documented in the researchers' diaries from the AI Ambassadors lab (OULU) highlighting the importance of fostering a safe and respectful environment where students feel genuinely heard and not exposed. In other contexts, conversations tended to remain focused on individual concerns without linking them to broader systemic dynamics. A clear example of this occurred in the Trinitat Nova (UB) labs where the initial activity of identifying injustices led participants to concentrate primarily on highly personal issues (e.g., a student receiving more support than others). This required a deliberate effort to engage in critical reflection to situate these narratives within a wider systemic and structural framework.

7.3.1.2.2 Sharing Views to Co-Construct Knowledge

Another key pedagogical decision implemented in this third PAR cycle, continuing a pattern observed in previous cycles, was the intentional use of debate and group dialogue as strategies for co-constructing knowledge and allow translating personal experiences into shared concerns.

To support these processes, various methods and strategies were employed across different labs to facilitate dialogue. These included both less structured formats, based on spontaneous discussion, and more structured techniques. Examples of this latter approach can be found in the use of techniques such as the fishbowl discussion method or the walking debate.

The fishbowl discussion method was employed in the AI Ambassadors lab (UOLU) to facilitate a debate on the impact of artificial intelligence on hiring processes and social justice. This dialogic technique involves a small group of participants engaging in conversation within an inner circle—the "fishbowl"—while the rest of the group observes from an outer circle. After a set time, roles are rotated, allowing more participants to enter the discussion.

Another commonly used technique was the walking debate, implemented in several contexts including Europaschule Linz (AE), Trinitat Nova T and N (UB), Pineda (UB), and both

DYFF and DYFC (TCD). In these sessions, participants physically positioned themselves along an “agree–disagree” continuum in response to a series of statements read aloud. The statements followed a gradual progression: beginning with light, everyday preferences (e.g., “Summer is better than winter”), moving to more personal or relational topics (e.g., “Decisions in my family are made democratically”, “Students’ voices are heard at school”), and culminating in broader political or ethical issues (e.g., “Everyone should have the same rights and duties”).

This progression allowed students to ease into more complex conversations by first engaging with familiar topics, helping to build trust and confidence before addressing more sensitive or abstract issues.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Debate and dialogue-based activities generally fostered active participation, the exchange of perspectives, collective reflection, critical inquiry, and the recognition of diverse ways of knowing. This approach reflects an epistemological stance aligned with Paulo Freire’s thought (2005), which rejects the notion of knowledge as a one-way transmission from teacher to student. However, some challenges also emerged. One recurring issue was the presence of dominating voices, observed in labs such as Pineda (UB), Don Bosco (WAAG), and Europaschule (AE). In these instances, a few outspoken participants tended to steer the conversation, which at times silenced or discouraged contributions from others. Facilitators noted that although these individuals often helped energise the discussion, their dominance risked narrowing the diversity of perspectives within the group. This dynamic often intersected with broader patterns of privilege – particularly along gender lines– as girls and other less dominant participants were more likely to hold back their contributions in mixed settings.

Another challenge involved conversations that stalled or lost focus, especially when participants struggled to connect their own experiences to the topic under discussion. In such circumstances, dialogue remained at a superficial level or veered off into unrelated issues, without reaching deeper levels of critical engagement.

7.3.1.2.3 Thinking Together to Co-Construct Knowledge

Closely aligned with the dialogic and co-constructivist epistemologies discussed above, another widely used pedagogical strategy across the analysed labs was that of thinking

with others to co-construct meaning. Unlike activities focused solely on sharing personal experiences or opinions, this approach involved engaging participants in collaborative tasks that required collective analysis, inquiry, and meaning making. Some examples that depict how this way of knowing was enacted can be found in the following labs: UDDP (ISRZ), in the Pablo Neruda (EUROALTER), in the UDMJ (ISRZ), in the Pineda (UB) and in AI Ambassadors (OULU).

In UDDP (ISRZ), for example, students used the “5 Why’s” method to investigate the issue of food waste. Each group received a blank diagram to collaboratively identify symptoms of the problem and explore its possible causes. In the Pablo Neruda lab (EUROALTER), students engaged in a structured small-group debate on the pros and cons of AI in education and prepared a presentation to share with their peers. A similar collaborative structure was also used in UDMJ (ISRZ) to unpack social constructions of beauty. In groups, students mapped internal and external factors influencing beauty standards onto human silhouettes. This method encouraged participants to reflect on and share personal insecurities, while also recognising broader social and cultural patterns. Finally, in Pineda (UB) and AI Ambassadors (OULU), students explored the question: “How do AI tools support or challenge democratic values?” through group discussions and visual mapping exercises. Across these examples, it is particularly interesting to observe how visual strategies, especially different forms of mapping, played a key role in enabling participants to organise, share, and make visible their processes of collective knowledge construction. In UDDP (ISRZ) a structured mapping tool guided the analysis; in UDMJ (ISRZ), a metaphorical approach using a body silhouette helped surface internal and external influences; and in Pineda (UB) and AI Ambassadors (OULU), participants used analogic or digital mind maps as a way to articulate shared thinking and connections between ideas. These examples underscore not only the relevance of visual tools for fostering collaborative meaning-making but also draw attention to the agency of visual and physical artefacts in facilitating these processes. As reflected through the researchers’ diaries, thinking together, in this sense, is not a purely human affair but it unfolds through the dynamic interplay between humans and non-human elements, including diagrams, maps, bodies, and digital platforms. This recognition invites us to consider pedagogical design not just as the orchestration of human interaction, but as the careful curating of material conditions that can support, shape, and even provoke critical and collective thought.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Overall, these activities generally supported deeper thinking and encouraged participants to move beyond surface-level responses and, by fostering analytical reasoning and collective inquiry, they created conditions for a more grounded and reflective engagement with complex topics. However, some tensions emerged, particularly when the complexity of certain themes proved difficult for participants to grasp. In some cases, facilitators reported that students struggled to establish meaningful connections between abstract concepts. This, for instance, happened in the Pineda (UB) lab, where participants initially struggled to grasp the relationship between democracy and digital technologies. This sometimes led to frustration or disengagement, especially when the activities lacked sufficient scaffolding to bridge the gap between participants' lived experiences and the more theoretical dimensions of the topic.

7.3.1.2.4 Co-Creating to co-construct Knowledge

In addition to dialogic and analytical approaches, creative strategies played a crucial role in supporting the co-construction of knowledge across labs. This emphasis on creative methods reinforces the positive evaluation of artistic approaches observed in PAR cycle 2, which highlighted their effectiveness in deepening engagement, fostering emotional connection, and enabling participants to express complex ideas that might be difficult to articulate through conventional verbal discussion alone. Illustrative examples of how creative strategies were used to support co-creation of knowledge can be found in the Europaschule Linz (AE), Trinitat Nova T and N (UB) and the TCD labs.

For example, at Europaschule Linz (AE), researchers proposed a "Meme Making" activity to engage students in creating memes in small groups about real-life school conflicts. This process, by combining humour and creativity, helped participants to represent different viewpoints and emotional responses to conflict. Furthermore, sharing these memes facilitated collective reflection, making visible the social tensions and diverse reactions within the school community.

Similarly, in the two labs carried out at Trinitat Nova T/N (UB), students used creative methods to deepen their understanding of injustice. Specifically, students in small groups identified an injustice-related issue that was particularly relevant for them (as, for instance, discrimination due to skin colour) and collectively elaborated a visual representation of this injustice as a virus infecting a social cell. This process of transforming their personal experiences with injustice into a visual representation sparked rich debate among the

groups and, in most cases, it allowed them to move from an individual perspective toward a more systemic understanding.

The TCD labs offered a compelling example through the speculative design activity “Break It Before You Make It.” Participants, divided into small groups of 4–5, were tasked with designing the worst possible future city based on themes like education or the environment. They brainstormed and illustrated dystopian urban scenarios that exaggerated negative social and political features, such as exclusionary architecture, surveillance, and youth marginalisation. This activity revealed students’ strong critical awareness of systemic issues and helped map out key themes that guided the subsequent process. Students valued the exercise for its ability to provoke critical thinking while actively engaging their creativity and imagination. Lastly, Verein Saum’s (AE) “Postcards from the Future” activity invited participants to create visual postcards imagining future work scenarios. This approach served as symbolic artifacts that captured students’ hopes, anxieties, and critiques.

Across all these examples, a key element was the way in which the outcomes of the creative process were later shared in plenary sessions. This step not only helped open up the work done in small groups to broader perspectives, but also extended the conversation, generating opportunities for collective meaning-making.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Creative strategies, by engaging multiple senses and modes of expression, provided alternative entry points into complex topics, encouraging alternative exploration and supporting the articulation of perspectives that might otherwise remain unspoken. This aligns with a growing body of research highlighting the transformative potential of arts-based methods in work with young people (Leavy, 2015; Lee et al., 2020). Furthermore, from an epistemological standpoint, these practices resonate with feminist (hooks, 1994) and decolonial epistemologies (Espejo, 2022), which challenge the dominance of rationalist, disembodied, and logocentric knowledge systems to recognise the validity and value of other ways of knowing. The overall reception of creative methods across the PAR cycles was notably positive, both in the observations made by researchers and in the direct feedback from students and teachers. One of the clearest opportunities highlighted was the catalytic function of collective creative processes: by engaging participants in the design and production of shared artifacts, these strategies enabled dialogic spaces that went beyond verbal exchange. The act of jointly deciding how to formalize an idea through a creative

medium helped to ground and sharpen the ideas being explored within each group, giving form to often complex and abstract notions. In this sense, the artistic process supported not only the sharing of knowledge, but also its transformation, allowing, in several labs to move from individual experiences to more systemic understandings of the phenomena at hand.

Moreover, researchers noted that creative strategies offered inclusive avenues for participation. Students who tended to remain silent during debates or discussions found in these methods alternative ways to contribute and take on a central role. This illustrates the power of epistemological pluralism: by acknowledging that people reflect, create, and construct knowledge differently, these approaches helped to validate diverse perspectives and expressions. From a research perspective, these strategies also made visible how young people make sense of the world, revealing concerns, fears, and hopes that might otherwise remain hidden. The expressive dimensions of art-based work created meaningful insight into students' socio-emotional worlds and allowed for collective inquiry.

However, the use of creative strategies also brought certain tensions and challenges. In some labs, the level of abstraction involved in tasks such as metaphorical visualisation or speculative design made the process difficult for some participants. For instance, at Schulungszentrum (AE), where participants showed clear difficulties in connecting with the speculative "What if" approach. For many, the abstract nature of the exercise created a sense of discomfort or detachment, partly due to unfamiliarity with artistic methodologies or with thinking beyond their daily realities. Additionally, a few cases reported that the artistic phases of the lab were not always clearly linked to the subsequent stages of inquiry or action. This occasionally led to confusion about the purpose of the creative work or its relevance to the broader research goals.

7.3.1.2.4 Emotions and Affects as Resources to Co-Construct Knowledge

Within the third PAR cycle, an important element that emerged as a resource for knowledge co-construction was the recognition of emotions and affect as central components of the learning process. Some labs offered compelling examples of how affective engagement enriched participatory inquiry. For instance, in the Europaschule Linz (AE) lab, the "Empathy Exercise – Understanding Perspectives in School Life through Video Analysis" was used to foster students' empathetic understanding of school-based conflict. The group collectively viewed a short film depicting a school fight and then discussed the roles of the individuals involved, such as instigator, bystander, and peacemaker, drawing on their own experiences

to deepen reflection. In small groups, students created additional scenarios and explored how emotional and situational dynamics might influence people's actions and reactions.

In the AI Ambassador project (OULU), emotional responses were explicitly used to guide the collective reflection on the experiential use of the simulator "Survival of the Best Fit", a gamified tool illustrating how bias operates in AI-driven recruitment processes. Specifically, students after playing with the simulator, were invited to participate in an emotion mapping activity. They physically positioned themselves in corners of the room labelled with different emotional reactions (e.g., Frustrated, Amused, Confused, Surprised) based on how the simulator made them feel. This embodied reflection served as a springboard for a structured fishbowl discussion, where students explored the ethical and political implications of algorithmic decision-making.

A related, though more introspective, approach was observed in the Coláiste Bríde lab (TCD), where students participated in a "Guided Reflective Visualization". This method did not foreground emotion explicitly, but it worked through affective and embodied awareness. At the start of the session, students closed their eyes and were guided through a mindfulness-based reflection. They were invited to connect with recent personal experiences, recalling moments from their weekend, their commute to school, and events anticipated in the week ahead. This grounding exercise created a calm, attentive atmosphere that supported deeper engagement in subsequent collaborative tasks related to analysing their neighbourhood.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Overall, the labs that incorporated affective and emotional dimensions into their learning processes reported positive experiences and strong levels of student engagement. Activities that invited participants to reflect on their emotions, build empathy, or connect with their felt experiences often created meaningful spaces for participation and deeper inquiry.

These approaches align with the perspective of transformative pedagogies and critical epistemologies which recognise that affects are not separate from cognition but rather are a vital dimension of how we come to know, relate, and act in the world (Ahmed, 2013; Rolnik, 2023). They, hence, challenge traditional hierarchies that privilege rational, detached forms of knowing and instead highlight the need to engage with embodied experience, emotional resonance, and relationality in collective knowledge-making processes (hooks, 1994).

However, it is important to note that this affective dimension was not explicitly planned or systematically integrated into the pedagogical design of the CCLAB model. Rather, it emerged organically as a byproduct of certain methods or moments in the process. This highlights both a promising opportunity and a critical challenge: the need to further theorize and intentionally incorporate affective dimensions into participatory educational practices. Therefore, there is no clear record of evidence directly linked to the challenges, making it difficult to trace how affective engagement contributed to addressing them

7.3.1.2.5 The Body as a Resource to Co-Construct Knowledge

As a way to more deeply integrate experiential knowledge in the methodological approach, in a few labs across the PAR Cycle 3, the body emerged as an epistemic resource for co-constructing knowledge through performative and embodied methods. For instance, In the DYFF lab (TCD), students participated in a drama-based futuring activity where they created freeze-frame tableaux and short improvised scenes in response to prompts such as "the future of water" or "the future of travel." This embodied method aimed to foster imagination and collaborative meaning-making around urban futures, nonetheless it was not particularly well received by students.

On the other hand, in the two Trinitat Nova labs (UB), Theatre of the Oppressed techniques were used to explore systemic injustices like adultism, gender violence, and monoculture. Students co-created fictional storyboards and performed dramatizations of everyday conflicts. Despite initial resistance and low motivation, group-based facilitation helped unlock participation, emotional expression, and critical reflection. The embodied re-enactments enabled students to not only better understand social injustices, but also collaboratively imagine strategies for nonviolent resistance and institutional change. For example, a forum-theatre scene on homophobia evolved from a proposal for violent retaliation to a discussion about dialogue and collective action, revealing how performative practice can support ethical and political deliberation.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

The use of embodied and performative methods in PAR Cycle 3 revealed important opportunities for deepening engagement. These approaches aimed at activating affective, sensory, and relational dimensions of learning, to allow participants exploring complex social issues in ways that transcend verbal or purely cognitive modes of engagement.

However, their implementation also surfaced significant tensions and challenges. Even though examples such as those from DYFF (TCD) and Trinitat Nova T/N (UB) underscore the potential of the body as a site of knowledge production, they also reveal the limits and resistances that may arise in educational contexts where the body is not typically recognised as a legitimate source of epistemic authority.

In the DYFF lab, the drama-based activity was not well received by students, partly due to the absence of adequate warm-up exercises and the lack of familiarity with theatrical expression. Similarly, in the Trinitat Nova's examples, students initially showed resistance to engaging physically with the topics proposed, requiring individualised facilitation to rebuild trust and comfort. These observations point to an important tension: while embodied strategies can powerfully support the co-construction of knowledge, they often clash with prevailing educational norms that privilege verbal, rational, and disembodied forms of expression. In many formal educational settings, the body is marginal to knowledge production, rendering practices that foreground physical expression as unusual or even disruptive.

Deeply related to the above-mentioned challenges, another relevant observation is the fact that in PAR Cycle 3, embodied and performative strategies were notably less present than in PAR Cycle 2. One contributing factor appears to be the hesitation or lack of confidence among some facilitators, who expressed difficulty in designing or leading such activities. This suggests that, while the pedagogical value of embodied methods is increasingly recognised, their implementation remains uneven and contingent upon the facilitators' training, comfort, and institutional support.

From an epistemological standpoint, this shift raises critical questions about the systemic challenges of sustaining embodied approaches within educational frameworks that continue to privilege disembodied, rationalist, and logocentric forms of knowledge. The reduced use of body-based practices in PAR Cycle 3 does not reflect their diminished relevance but rather underscores the ongoing difficulty of embedding these approaches within dominant norms and institutional constraints.

7.3.1.2.6 "Play-With" as a Resource to Co-Construct Knowledge

Within the third PAR cycle, game based learning emerged as a powerful, though still underexplored, pedagogical resource to support knowledge co-construction.

This potential was clearly illustrated in the Damstede Lyceum lab (WAAG), where students engaged in an augmented reality (AR) game, *Escape Fake*, designed to raise awareness about misinformation. Framed as a mystery to be solved, the activity placed students in the role of "reverse history hackers" working collaboratively to uncover the truth behind a manipulated narrative. Using mobile devices and AR markers placed throughout the classroom, they solved puzzles and engaged with multiple forms of media to critically assess information and identify manipulation strategies. According to the researchers, the game not only captured students' attention but created an immersive environment where abstract concepts like bias, disinformation, and social justice became tangible and emotionally resonant.

Similarly, in the AI Ambassador lab (OULU), playful and hands-on methodologies were employed to stimulate critical reflection on algorithmic bias and the ethics of artificial intelligence. One key activity involved the use of the educational simulator "Survival of the Best Fit", in which students experienced discriminatory AI hiring processes from the perspective of job applicants. In addition, other activities, such as experimenting with Google's Teachable Machine or building decision trees to explore machine learning logic, allowed participants to interact with complex technical concepts in intuitive and playful ways.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

These practices emphasised play as both an epistemic and affective mode of learning, particularly well-suited to explore the sociotechnical dimensions of contemporary challenges. However, the limited expiration of this approach does not allow for a careful systematisation of its risks and benefits.

7.3.1.2.7 Co-Constructing Knowledge Around the Chosen Topic: Opportunities and Challenges

The phase dedicated to co-constructing knowledge with participants reflects the epistemological orientation at the core of the CCLAB model, which intentionally moves beyond traditional academic frameworks. Instead of privileging abstract, individual, or rationalist forms of knowing, the model embraces dialogic, experiential, and relational approaches that view knowledge as co-produced through collective inquiry, embodied engagement, and contextual exploration.

A review of the diverse strategies and epistemic orientations employed across this phase reveals that one of its most significant contributions lies in the activation of epistemic diversity. This resonates with the notion of epistemological pluralism (Miller et al., 2008), which recognises the coexistence of multiple legitimate ways of knowing, often negotiated across differences in perspective, experience, and positionality.

In this light, the validation of diverse modes of knowledge production, such as imagination, creativity, affect, emotion, and embodied experience, not only aligns with the theoretical foundations of critical pedagogies but also with feminist, decolonial, and poststructuralist epistemologies, which challenge dominant logocentric paradigms and foreground the value of situated, creative, embodied and affective ways of meaning-making.

Furthermore, this epistemic diversity also supports inclusion by recognising that different people think, feel, and communicate in different ways—and that such differences are not deficits but vital contributions to democratic learning environments.

However, implementing these epistemic orientations in formal educational settings is not without tensions. In several labs, facilitators faced practical and cultural challenges in enacting methods that depart from conventional classroom norms. Embodied or affective, were sometimes met with skepticism, discomfort, or resistance, both from students and educators. These difficulties point to the influence of educational systems that privilege disembodied, rationalist, and outcome-driven forms of knowledge, often at the expense of more holistic and inclusive pedagogical practices.

Thus, while the strategies deployed in this phase demonstrate the transformative potential of embracing epistemological pluralism, they also highlight the need for systemic change, including teacher training, institutional support, and a cultural shift in how we define, value, and assess knowledge in education.

7.3.1.3 Broadening Perspectives Around the Topic

A central objective of the Question & Analyse phase within the CCLAB model is to deepen participants' understanding of the selected theme by intentionally expanding the range of perspectives, experiences, and forms of knowledge brought into the inquiry process. This phase is not limited to consolidating what the group already knows, but aims to create the

conditions for challenging assumptions, incorporating new voices, and engaging with unfamiliar or divergent viewpoints to deepen their understanding.

This pedagogical moment aligns with the broader aims of the CCLAB model, which draws on critical pedagogies (Ellsworth, 1989; Freire, 2005) to foster critical consciousness among young people, supporting them in identifying and interrogating the social and structural inequalities that shape their everyday realities.

To accompany students in the process of broadening their perspectives and ways of seeing the chosen topic, most contexts implemented cooperative inquiry (Heron & Reason, 2001) as a central strategy to access other visions and knowledges, and to lay the groundwork for processes of transformation and change. However, other complementary strategies were also employed, including artistic fruition, participation in cultural events, and engagement with expert knowledge. In the following sections, we explore in detail these different strategies.

7.3.1.3.1 Cooperative Inquiry to Broaden Perspectives Around a Topic

Across the different labs analysed as part of the third PAR cycle, several initiatives adopted strategies inspired by cooperative inquiry (Heron & Reason, 2001) to investigate the chosen themes in a collaborative manner. These inquiries aimed to expand young people's understanding of the topic by exposing them to diverse perspectives and generating an empirical foundation from which to imagine and discuss potential pathways for transformation and change. Furthermore, they address critical competences of the model such as the ability to identify, articulate, and formulate research questions that are relevant and responsive to community needs and interests; the understanding of various research approaches and methods and the proficiency in applying and experimenting with participatory research tools,

However, it is important to note that not all labs implemented cooperative inquiry explicitly. In some instances, knowledge construction remained confined to the internal work of the group, through co-creative processes, without extending the inquiry outward. This was often due to context-specific factors, such as the nature of the theme selected by the group, as well as methodological constraints, including limited timeframes that affected the scope of the inquiry.

In the labs where a more structured cooperative inquiry process was carried out, two aspects deserve particular attention: first, the specific methods employed to support the investigation; and second, how power and decision-making were negotiated and distributed throughout the process.

Methods to Research Together

As previously discussed, the CCLAB model allowed youth to explore and implement a wide range of participatory research methods. This diversity of approaches reflects the CCLAB's broader epistemological orientation, which values multiple ways of knowing and supports young people in becoming active inquirers into their own realities. Within the third PAR cycle, also, various labs reported the use of participatory and cooperative research strategies as a tool to broaden participants' perspectives and generating knowledge collaboratively.

One of the most common entry points into inquiry was desk research, where students conducted online searches and synthesised available information on the theme they were investigating. For example, in Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), students explored the topic of disinformation through the activity "Fake news or just nothing? Creating a news broadcast". Students gathered five real and five fake news stories and presented them to their peers, who then had to guess which stories were true or false. Similarly, in UDDP (ISRZ), students began by researching food waste online and preparing PowerPoint presentations to share their findings.

Another frequently employed strategy involved conducting interviews and surveys to bring in diverse perspectives from outside the group. For instance, students at UDDP interviewed staff working in the school dormitory about their experiences and opinions on food waste. Similarly, in Coláiste Bríde (TCD), students conducted an interview with a retired teacher as a way to integrate intergenerational perspectives about the history of the neighbourhood into their project. Meanwhile, students in Pineda (UB) used both traditional and visual surveys with their peers to explore their habits and perceptions in relation to digital technologies.

Several labs also integrated observational and visual methods to foster a more attentive engagement with the world. The Photovoice method used in UDDP invited students to take photographs of situations linked to food waste in their everyday lives. These images became

the basis for collective reflection during group discussions, allowing students to creatively express their viewpoints and explore the social and environmental implications of the issue.

In addition, community mapping was used as a tool for reflective engagement in multiple labs. At Coláiste Bríde (TCD), students created personal maps of meaningful spaces in their school, connecting emotional geographies with lived experiences to start exploring issue about how their neighbourhood can be transformed. In the DYFF and DYFC labs (TCD), also mapping and critical observation of the locality and city were central components of the inquiry, prompting students to explore issues and problems of mobility in their urban environment.

Ways of Researching Together

Beyond the specific research methods employed, it is equally important to consider *how* the research process unfolds and *who* holds decision-making power at each stage. In other words: who decides when it is time to start researching? Who chooses what to investigate and how? And who is responsible for making sense of the findings?

In all labs analysed in the third PAR cycle, the *topic* of inquiry emerges through prior processes of co-constructing knowledge within the group. Similarly, the *interpretation* of research findings is carried out collectively. However, the *decision to begin* empirical research tends to be taken by the facilitation or research team. This is partly shaped by the methodological structure of the CCLAB model itself and partly by the time constraints under which each lab operates.

Where we see more variation is in the question of *how* the research is conducted, specifically in the choice and use of methods. In some contexts, such as UDDP (ISRZ), Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), and DYFF/DYFC (TCD), the selection of research strategies was largely determined in advance by educators and researchers. In these labs, facilitators proposed specific tools (e.g., photovoice, mapping, desk research, surveys), and students were guided through their implementation.

By contrast, in Coláiste Bríde (TCD) and Pineda (UB), students were given more freedom to define their own research strategies. However, these two examples reflect different levels and types of pedagogical support. In Pineda, students received minimal preparation before choosing their methods. A facilitator briefly introduced a few possible research strategies, after which each group was asked to decide how they would explore their chosen

subtheme. This led to uneven levels of engagement with the research process. Some groups did not conduct any empirical inquiry at all, while others relied on very traditional or superficial methods, such as basic online surveys, which were insufficient for grasping the complexities or contradictions of the topic. Only one group succeeded in developing a more critical and in-depth approach.

On the other hand, Coláiste Bríde (TCD) followed a more structured and pedagogically guided process. Here, students were supported across several sessions to progressively explore and experiment with different research methods. In one session, students were guided through the “Question Formulation Technique” to learn how to craft effective interview questions. The process involved a rapid brainstorming activity where groups generated a wide range of questions across different themes, followed by a group discussion on what makes a question “good,” including the distinction between open and closed questions and how to avoid bias. Students then collaboratively refined their top questions before sharing their final selections with the whole group. In a subsequent session, students were invited to experiment hands-on with various research methods inside the school. Working in small groups, they explored different areas of the building using surveys, sketching, photovoice, and ethnographic observation. Each group had around 25 minutes to collect and document their findings, followed by a group-sharing phase where they each presented one key insight. Finally, this methodological preparation culminated in a fieldwork session in which students conducted surveys in their neighbourhood, defining their own research agendas. While some students felt that more time was needed this experience was seen as far more impactful than simply discussing issues in the classroom and helped students develop a more critical lens toward their environments, identifying previously invisible local injustices.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Involving participants in cooperative inquiry helped in fostering the co-construction of knowledge and encouraged critical questioning of social inequalities and structural issues, thereby enhancing participants’ critical awareness and broadening their perspective beyond individualistic viewpoints. At the same time, the diverse participatory research strategies employed throughout different labs demonstrate the richness and adaptability of the CCLAB model. This variety reflects a coherent alignment between the project’s theoretical foundations and the concrete methods used to co-construct knowledge,

enabling participants to engage creatively and critically with the topic and making learning both multidimensional and contextually situated.

Nonetheless, during this third cycle, the prominence of cooperative inquiry appears less marked compared to previous cycles. Moreover, important tensions and challenges emerge in how these processes are enacted. One significant tension concerns the extent to which cooperative inquiry processes are researcher-led versus student-led. While co-construction of knowledge remains central, decisions about when and how to investigate often rest primarily with the research team. This dynamic reveals persistent power imbalances within the participatory processes and raises critical questions about whether and how students can take greater ownership of the research process within this model.

At the same time, it is important to reflect on the knowledge and skills that participants bring to the process. It would be naïve to expect students without prior preparation to select the most appropriate research methods independently, as happened in the Pineda lab. In this respect, the structured guidance and accompaniment offered in the Coláiste Bríde lab provided a promising example of how to address this imbalance in know-how between students and researchers, supporting more authentic and empowered participation.

Finally, a broader tension lies between epistemological coherence and practical constraints. While the CCLAB's theoretical foundations embrace diverse ways of knowing and emphasise inclusive participation, practical limitations, such as time, contextual factors and institutional constraints, often limited the full realization of these ideals. This creates an ongoing challenge to reconcile theoretical aspirations with the realities of implementation.

7.3.1.3.2 Artistic Fruition and Participation in Cultural Events to Broaden Perspectives

Aesthetic fruition and participation in cultural events have also been employed to expand participants' perspectives and enriching their ways of understanding and questioning the topics under analysis. For instance, at UDMJ (ISRZ), participants attended the theatre performance *Girls with Horns*, which addresses women's mental health and self-image. The play evoked a strong emotional response and widened participants' understanding around mental health by allowing them to connect personally with the themes, which subsequently sparked rich discussions during follow-up sessions.

Similarly, at LATRA, the interactive staging of *Animal Farm* constituted a central element of the CCLAB. This play, adapted for young audiences, created an interactive environment where children actively participated by voting on characters' decisions and offering suggestions. This interactivity, complemented by small-group reflective discussions involving students, teachers, and parents, facilitated critical engagement with concepts of fairness, power, and the consequences of choices and allowed children to draw meaningful connections between the fictional narrative and their own lived experiences, thus broadening their understanding of social dynamics and justice. Similarly, a biodiversity guided walking tour at DYFC (TCD) fostered situated learning, encouraging students to reflect on environmental issues in their immediate surroundings.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Overall, these examples demonstrate how aesthetic fruition and cultural participation serve as powerful pedagogical tools to deepen emotional engagement and broaden perspectives on complex social issues. However, implementing these approaches can present relevant practical challenges. Access to meaningful cultural events often depends on contextual factors such as geographic location, institutional partnerships, or logistical resources. As a result, this type of activity could only be implemented in a few of the participating contexts, highlighting inequalities in access and opportunities across sites.

7.3.1.3.3 Listening to Experts' Voices to Broadening Perspectives

In a few examples, across the third PAR cycle, experts were invited into the learning spaces to expand young people's understanding of the topics. These encounters aimed at providing other perspectives, lived experiences, and professional insights that enrich participants' critical reflection and engagement.

In the AI Ambassadors lab, a collective interview with a journalist specializing in artificial intelligence in media offered participants a real-world perspective on algorithmic decision-making. Although some of the topics had already been introduced in earlier sessions, hearing them articulated by an experienced professional deepened participants' understanding. The journalist's concrete examples and critical framing of AI's limitations resonated strongly, with students continuing to reference her reflections in the days that followed. In Coláiste Bríde (TCD), the invitation of an elderly former teacher deeply rooted in the local community offered students a vivid, personal account of the neighbourhood's

past. The session, structured around student-led interviews, created a space for intergenerational dialogue and exchanges to build affective connections to local history. Similarly, at UDNZ (ISRZ) the visit from Croatian rapper who shared his personal journey through substance abuse and recovery sparked genuine interest in students and connected well with participants

In contrast, example of expert's interventions in the UDNZ lab (ISRZ), Pineda lab (UB) and DYFF lab (TCD) show that the impact of expert input can vary depending on the format and delivery. At UDNZ, during an informational session on drug abuse facilitators observed a drop in student engagement. Despite a reasonable level of prior knowledge, participants showed limited willingness to incorporate new perspectives or actively challenge each other. A similar situation was observed in Pineda (UB) where a presentation about algorithms and biases received limited attention. Similarly, a more traditional expert talk about water issues at DYFF (TCD) failed to generate significant interest among students.

Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Across these diverse labs, it becomes evident that incorporating expert voices can significantly enrich participants' perspectives. However, the effectiveness of these contributions depends greatly on the format, perceived relevance, and emotional resonance. A key challenge arises when expert input is overly didactic or fails to connect with students' lived experiences, as it can then be perceived as distant or unengaging. Moreover, this format may at times reproduce top-down educational models, echoing traditional learning experiences that stand in tension with participatory and horizontal approaches.

7.3.2 The Envision & Act Phases

This section explores how the different consortium partners approached the Envision & Act phases within their respective labs. At a pragmatic level, this phase is informed by the transformative stage of the ChangeLab intervention method (Engeström et al., 2013; Kajamaa, 2011; Haapasaari et al., 2016).

The CCLAB model expands upon this framework by placing particular emphasis on the Envision dimension. Here, students were encouraged to imagine desirable or preferable futures through the use of transformative tools. This stage aimed at fostering speculative

thinking and creative experimentation as ways to challenge conventional norms and "disrupt the commonplace." On the other hand, the Act phase is conceptualised as a co-creative process, where responses to previously identified tensions are developed collectively to co-designing small-scale interventions which can generate meaningful changes in young people's everyday realities.

The analysis of diverse experiences across contexts reveals that these phases are the most heterogeneous in terms of how were interpreted and implemented. Approaches varied significantly depending on local contexts, resources, and pedagogical orientations. To better grasp this diversity, the following sections explore in greater detail how these phases were conceptualised and how power and decision-making processes were distributed throughout them.

7.3.2.1 The Envision Phase

As previously mentioned, the Envision phase represents a contribution of the CCLAB project to the broader ChangeLab model. Specifically, this phase aims to develop competencies related to imagining alternatives beyond existing paradigms. It encourages participants to question assumptions, explore unconventional possibilities, and engage with the creative and political potential of "What if?" scenarios. More broadly, it seeks to cultivate the capacity to envision futures that go beyond present constraints. According to the literature, the ability to imagine what does not yet exist is fundamental to activating transformative processes in the present (Miller, 2018).

The implementation of this phase across labs revealed a rich diversity of pedagogical approaches and epistemological-methodological perspectives that shape how envisioning is practiced in context. These differences reflect both the specific objectives each context assigns to the envisioning phase and the underlying conceptualizations of what "possible futures" mean within those settings.

Furthermore, this PAR cycle also marks a step forward compared to earlier iterations: in response to the observed difficulties many young people faced when attempting to imagine alternatives, more targeted and supportive methodological strategies were developed and activated to facilitate this process.

7.3.2.1.1 The Diversity of Objectives in the Envision Phase

Based on the analysis of the different labs, four distinct approaches to the objectives pursued during the envisioning phase were identified (Table 17). While these approaches are often complementary and at times overlapping, they illustrate a variety of ways in which the Envision phase can be implemented, shaping both the subsequent phases and the specific capabilities and practices that are developed through the process.

Table 17. Summary of the Diversity of Goals on the Envision Phase

Approach	Goals
Future imagining as a gateway to building shared knowledge	To uncover young people's fears, hopes, and understandings related to the topic under investigation
Future imagining as a tool for critical reflection on the present.	To critically question current realities by imagining alternatives
Future imagining as a strategy for displacing dominant forms of thought and opening space for creative ways of thinking	To go beyond the known and encourage new forms of thought and creative thinking
Future imagining as a preparatory step for the co-design of proposals and actions for change	To lay the conceptual and imaginative groundwork for developing actionable proposals for change

A first approach positions future imagining as a gateway to building shared knowledge and making visible the fears, hopes, and understandings that young people hold regarding the issue under investigation. This approach draws on growing evidence in the literature that imagining possible futures can provide a powerful entry point for exploring how youth perceive their environments (Lukens & DiSalvo, 2012; Malinverni et al., 2025; Maxwell et al., 2019). Relevant examples from PAR cycle 3 include the Schulungszentrum (AE) and Pablo Neruda (AE) labs. At Schulungszentrum (AE), the “Future Exhibition” activity invited students to engage with historical visions of the future as a way of triggering reflection on their ideas, fears and conceptions about the future of work. In Pablo Neruda (AE), the group collectively explored the notions of utopias and dystopias regarding the future of AI as a way to dig into their understandings and perceptions around this topic.

A second approach uses future imagining as a tool for critical reflection on the present. Through a temporal and conceptual shift, imagining futures becomes a resource for

questioning current conditions and initiating the process of thinking about alternatives. Notable examples can be found in UDDP (ISRZ), AI Ambassadors (OULU), and Trinitat Nova (UB). In UDDP (ISRZ), students were asked to create three future scenarios on food waste, optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic, using various creative media to reflect on the complexities of this topic. Similarly, the AI Ambassador (OULU) team used the Futures Wheel method to explore the impacts of AI in decision-making, mapping out first- and second-order consequences of specific design choices and engaging participants in critical thinking through guided questions. In Trinitat Nova T and N (UB), students engaged in a speculative exercise to imagine the most unjust school possible, using this fictional scenario as a way to reflect on their own experiences of injustice in the educational system.

A third way of approaching the envisioning phase is as a strategy for displacing dominant forms of thought and opening space for creative ways of thinking. In this sense future thinking aims at introducing students into imaginative thinking and go beyond usual ways of doing. Relevant examples include Pineda (UB), AI Ambassadors (OULU), DYFF (TCD), DYFC (TCD) and Coláiste Bríde (TCD). In the Pineda (UB) lab, students were prompted to imagine both the best and worst possible futures in relation to mobile phone addiction. This imaginative and speculative exercise helped move the group beyond initial, more normative suggestions (e.g., promoting healthy habits) and opened new avenues for reflection that had not previously been considered. In the AI Ambassador (OULU) lab, one of the key warm-up activities for future thinking was the “Crazy 8s Futures Scenarios.” Students brainstormed future scenarios in rapid succession and then designed an app or service using AI to help with love and friendship decisions. Similarly, in the TCD labs, students were involved in different exercises to warm-up their creative and imaginative competences. Examples include quick design exercise to imagine the bus stop of the future, or the “Future Postcards” activity where students imagined what their city might look like in 2050 and visually represented their vision on postcards, drawing inspiration from historical images of imagined futures.

A fourth approach conceives of envisioning as a preparatory step for the co-design of proposals and actions for change and design of transformative actions. This approach materialises, for instance, in the DYFF, DYFC, and Coláiste Bríde (TCD) labs, where various strategies were used to imagine possible futures in order to lay the groundwork for envisioning concrete proposals to improve the urban environment.

7.3.2.1.2 Future Forecasting VS Speculative Futures

Beyond the diversity of objectives identified in the envisioning phase, it is equally important to pay attention to the epistemological and methodological differences in how future thinking is approached across labs. Two main orientations can be distinguished, each rooted in distinct intellectual traditions and serving different purposes: *future forecasting* and *speculative futures*.

On the one hand, *future forecasting* is grounded in an analytical and prospective reading of the present. From this perspective, imagining the future involves interpreting current trends, analysing data, identifying early signals of change, and projecting plausible scenarios through anticipatory tools and rational inquiry. It reflects an epistemology aligned with scientific, technical, and planning-oriented approaches, aiming to foresee potential developments and design responses accordingly.

A representative example of this approach can be found in the activity *AI Plausible Futures: Futures Triangle*, carried out in the AI Ambassador lab (OULU). This session introduced participants to the Futures Triangle, a foresight tool used to explore the interplay between past constraints, present dynamics, and future aspirations. Working collaboratively on a shared Miro board, participants engaged in a structured analysis by identifying the drivers of change in the present, reflecting on the historical burdens and systemic barriers that hinder progress, and envisioning inclusive and equitable futures shaped by technological developments, especially in AI. The activity encouraged a systematic and evidence-based exploration of possible, plausible, and desirable futures in relation to education, employment, and urban life.

On the other hand, a more open-ended and imaginative orientation emerges under the umbrella of speculative futures. This approach does not aim to extrapolate the future from current trends, but rather uses fiction, creativity, and imagination to open up possibilities beyond the realm of what is already known or considered likely. Epistemologically, it draws from artistic, narrative, and critical traditions that value intuition, emotion, and subversive forms of knowledge. Rather than projecting what might logically follow, it dares to imagine what could be even if it currently seems improbable.

Examples of this speculative orientation can be found in the Future Postcards exercises conducted in the DYFF and Coláiste Bríde (TCD) labs, where students were invited to visually

represent their imagined versions of Dublin in 2050. Similarly, the Future Exhibition activity in the Schulungszentrum lab (AE) engaged students in reflecting on historical future imaginaries as a way to craft their own visions. Similarly in the Pineda (UB) and Pablo Neruda (EUROALTER) labs, the concepts of utopia and dystopia were introduced as tools to explore how either technology addiction or AI might shape the future.

In summary, while *future forecasting* emphasises rational anticipation based on observable trends, *speculative futures* embrace imaginative disruption to challenge the boundaries of the possible. This methodological plurality within the envisioning phase significantly enriches the pedagogical processes, allowing for the development of diverse but complementary capacities related to critical and creative future thinking.

7.3.2.1.3 Methodological Approaches to Envision Futures

As previously mentioned, in this iteration greater emphasis was placed on the implementation of targeted tools and methods to support young people in imagining possible futures. This shift responded directly to the challenges encountered in PAR Cycle 2, where many participants struggled to move beyond present-oriented thinking. In response, a variety of methodological strategies were introduced, tailored both to the specific objectives of the envisioning phase and to the differing conceptual approaches to future thinking observed across labs.

Several of these strategies drew from established frameworks in futures studies and design. For instance, tools such as the Futures Triangle (Abdullah, 2023; Inayatullah, 2013), used in the AI Ambassador lab, provided a structured way to explore how present trends, past constraints, and future aspirations interact. Similarly, the use of future scenarios (Candy & Dunagan, 2017;), speculative design (Auger, 2013; Durall, 2021; Malinverni et al., 2025; Wargo & Alvarado, 2020), and design fiction (Hardy, 2018; Sharma et al., 2022) were central to the methodological approach in several labs—including those led by TCD, UB, ISRZ and the one in Pablo Neruda School (EUROALTER).

Particularly illustrative examples come from the AI Ambassador lab (UOLU). In the session “Envisioning desirable AI futures: Producing Design Fiction”, participants were introduced to the concept of alternative futures through the lens of design fiction. The activity began with a reflection exercise in which participants used a Miro template to articulate desirable AI futures. They considered domains where AI might raise concerns, identified core values that

should guide its use, and reflected on the types of data involved in such systems. Building on these reflections, participants took part in a creative ideation process centred on imagining AI-powered everyday objects that could exist in their envisioned futures. This ideation then transitioned into a storyboarding phase, in which participants began crafting narratives around their imagined futures. Subsequent sessions expanded these narratives through diverse creative activities such as video production, prototyping of artifacts, and the development of visual identities, allowing students to give form to their speculative visions in rich and multimodal ways.

On the other hand, the TCD labs underscored the value of engaging with the past as a springboard for imagining the future. In particular, the activity “Our Evolving Area” grounded future thinking in a historical analysis of the local environment. Participants examined old maps of their locality to trace patterns of continuity and change, while also interrogating the intended purposes and audiences of these maps. This process not only fostered a deeper understanding of how space is shaped by political, social, and economic forces, but also opened up critical questions about whose visions guide urban development. By connecting past trajectories with unrealised possibilities, students were encouraged to reimagine the future of their own city and locality beyond current constraints, developing a more nuanced and situated capacity for envisioning change.

Overall, the use of these diverse tools illustrates how different epistemological and methodological orientations, ranging from analytical foresight to speculative and historical imagination, can expand the ways in which young people engage with possible futures and partially address systemic issues related to imagining alternative futures.

7.3.2.1.4 Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

The third PAR cycle represents a step forward compared to previous iterations, particularly regarding the Envision phase. A wider variety of methodologies and creative tools were implemented to support young people in imagining possible futures, responding to some of the challenges previously identified. However, despite this progress, several persistent difficulties emerged, highlighting the complex nature of future-oriented thinking in participatory settings.

Across diverse contexts, a common challenge was the difficulty many young people experienced in projecting themselves beyond their immediate realities. Even when creative

methods were used participants often struggled to move beyond familiar frames of reference. In the ISRZ lab, for example, students working with future scenarios tended to reproduce similar perspectives and found it difficult to envision alternatives that departed significantly from their everyday experiences. Similarly, in the AI Ambassadors context, activities like the Futures Wheel stimulated critical discussions on the societal impact of AI, yet some conversations drifted toward abstract or far scenarios, losing relevance to the participants' concrete lives.

In other labs, the activities elicited imaginative responses but with limited practical grounding and often shaped around sci-fi cliché. This was visible in DYFF's "Future Postcards" session, where participants envisioned speculative futures featuring technologies like teleportation.

Another relevant example comes from Schulungszentrum (AE), where participants showed clear difficulties in connecting with the speculative "What if" approach. For many, the abstract nature of the exercise created a sense of discomfort or detachment, partly due to unfamiliarity with artistic methodologies or with thinking beyond their daily realities.

These examples, while context-specific, point to broader pedagogical and sociological concerns. Facilitators and researchers across the consortium have noted a recurring perception of a structural difficulty among youth when it comes to envisioning transformative futures. This phenomenon, although beyond the scope of this specific evaluation, invites critical reflection on the educational, cultural, and affective conditions that constrain the development of future-oriented thinking among young people.

Another insight emerging from this cycle is the need to clarify the epistemological and pedagogical orientations that underpin the Envision phase. In practice, the activities reflected different conceptualisations of possible futures, some more analytical, focusing on trend analysis and plausible scenarios, others more imaginative and speculative. While both approaches are valuable and potentially complementary, they rest on distinct assumptions, methodologies, and objectives. Without clear articulation, these differences can lead to confusion in facilitation and uneven learning outcomes.

Finally, in several labs, a gap remained between the envisioning activities and the subsequent Act phase. While the Envision sessions often succeeded in opening spaces for critical reflection, these outcomes did not always translate into concrete proposals or

actions. This reveals an ongoing challenge in designing pedagogical pathways that effectively bridge imagination and transformation.

7.3.2.2 The Act Phase

In the CCLAB model, the Act phase is conceptualised as a co-creative process in which responses to previously identified tensions are collectively developed in the design of small-scale interventions. These interventions are intended to generate meaningful changes in young people's everyday realities, making this phase central to the model's transformative ambition. It aims to foster the capacity to translate reflection into action, empowering young participants to model new solutions and to articulate concrete ideas for personal and collective change.

From the perspective of addressed competencies, this phase involves cultivating a range of critical and practical skills, including the ability to identify and define pathways toward justice-oriented transformation, to plan strategic actions, and to choose appropriate methods, tools, and resources for effective implementation. It also requires adopting a proactive mindset and taking tangible steps toward change, while recognising the importance of forming and sustaining collaborations with relevant stakeholders who can contribute to and amplify the impact of these actions.

However, the cross-cutting analysis of the implementation of this phase reveals that it is particularly challenging within the framework of many labs. Time constraints, institutional boundaries, and the rhythms of formal education often limit the scope for fully developing and enacting interventions. As a result, the Act phase tends to be where the methodological tensions of the CCLAB process become most pronounced.

These tensions manifest in several ways. In many labs, there was an inability to move beyond the ideation or conceptualization stage of action design: interventions remained at the level of reflective proposals or symbolic expressions of learning rather than being realised in practice. In other contexts, difficulties emerged regarding how decisions about which actions to implement were made, raising questions about the balance between facilitation and youth-led initiative, as well as about power dynamics and shared ownership.

In the following sections, we will examine these issues in greater detail in order to better understand the pedagogical, institutional, and logistical challenges that arise during this phase, and to identify the conditions under which the Act phase can more fully achieve its potential.

7.3.2.2.1 Conceptualizing the Act Phase

The overarching aim of the Act phase is to support young people in modelling new solutions and taking concrete steps toward change in their everyday environments. However, the implementation of this phase proved uneven across the different labs. While it was successfully realised in a few instances, in many others the proposed actions remained at a conceptual or reflective level due to time constraints, institutional limitations, or feasibility concerns.

Notably, only two labs fully implemented tangible interventions that were conceived, designed, and carried out by the participants. In the UDMJ (ISRZ) lab, following their prior exploration of social issues about mental health and self-image, students decided to create motivational stickers about the topic and place them around their dormitory. These stickers, developed collaboratively, featured positive messages and artwork designed to boost the self-esteem of their peers. Similarly, in the UDNZ (ISRZ) lab, students tackled the issue of drug use and addiction. After brainstorming around the topic, students decided to design and implement the proposal of regular evening gatherings in the dormitory, the “Night Living Room” sessions, designed to offer an alternative social space that promotes connection and well-being. Although students acknowledged the limitations of their capacity to confront addiction directly, they saw value in small-scale social interventions that could strengthen the dormitory’s sense of community.

In other labs, while there was a clear intention to support youth in designing actionable proposals, those ideas often remained at the level of brainstorming or reflection due to feasibility issues or limited time for implementation. For example, in Pineda (UB), students explored the issues related to democracy and digital technologies, and through the process their focus changed to addressing the lack of spaces for critical thinking in their school. To address this matter, they generated several ideas such as an extracurricular reading group or organising a civic hackathon, yet none of these proposals progressed beyond the ideation phase due to the time limitations. A similar dynamic occurred in Mytilene and Kalloni (LATRA), where students imagined alternative, fairer systems in both fictional and

real-life contexts. They participated enthusiastically in role-play and storytelling, even conceptualising a “fairness board” for classroom decision-making. However, the transition from imaginative engagement to actionable planning remained incomplete.

In contrast, in Coláiste Bríde (TCD), students managed to articulate more concrete proposals aimed at improving aspects of their urban environment. These ideas were developed during prototyping sessions, compiled into visual presentations and shared in a final session with relevant stakeholders. The presentation of their ideas was framed as an opportunity for civic engagement and validation of the students’ work. However, the lack of actual implementation rendered the proposals more symbolic than actionable, and this gap between expression and execution gave rise to an ambiguous experience among participants. Some students described the presentation as deeply meaningful, appreciating the chance to speak directly to institutional figures and feeling that their perspectives were being acknowledged. Others, however, expressed unease. The absence of follow-up or concrete outcomes led them to question whether such exercises merely simulate participation, potentially reinforcing a sense of powerlessness or feeding into false expectations about their capacity to influence change.

A third approach to the *Act* phase emerged in projects where students produced symbolic artifacts that condensed their learning and reflections. Rather than leading to direct action, these artifacts served to communicate insights and ideas to wider audiences. For instance, in UDDP (ISRZ), students participated in a zine-making activity. They used this creative format to reflect on key issues, articulate proposals, and combine text and visuals into narratives for change around food waste issue. The resulting zines were shared within their school and sometimes distributed digitally to broaden their impact. Other examples include the Verein and Schulungszentrum (AE) labs, where participants created podcasts to share their perspectives, the Damstede Lyceum lab (WAAG), where students designed their own disinformation awareness games and the AI Ambassador lab (OULU) where they produced a short audiovisual production using design fiction to creatively explore the implications of artificial intelligence in everyday life.

7.3.2.2 Decision-Making and Power Dynamics in the Act Phase

Analysing how the *Act* phase is conceptualised and implemented not only reveals a spectrum of approaches, from concrete interventions to symbolic representations, but also brings to the surface critical questions regarding the epistemological and methodological

foundations of participatory action research. A key issue regarding the ways in which decision-making is enacted in the Act phase: Who decides what action is to be taken? To what extent are these processes youth-led, and how is power negotiated in shaping the outcomes of the lab?

From the cross-cutting analysis, it becomes evident that in several labs, the format of the action to be undertaken was predetermined by the facilitators or researchers. For example, in UDDP (ISRZ), the action was framed around zine-making; in Auta Lasta (OULU), students designed and produced digital jewellery using fabrication tools; in AI Ambassador participants developed audiovisual design fiction pieces; in Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), the task was to create a disinformation-themed game; and in Verein and Schulungszentrum (AE), youth produced podcasts.

While these activities allowed for creative co-design within a defined medium, the structural boundaries, particularly the format and tools, had already been set. This raises significant ethical and epistemological tensions. On the one hand, the predetermined nature of the "what" and "how" may risk instrumentalising youth participation, reducing it to filling in pre-designed templates. On the other, this structure often facilitated smoother implementation and helped guide participants through complex tasks, which can be particularly useful when time or resources are limited. Interestingly, in many of these labs, students responded positively to this production phase, even if the format of the outcome was predetermined. Several participants described it as one of the most engaging moments of the process, where the opportunity to create a tangible product led to a shift in their relationship to the project, increasing their sense of ownership and motivation. This suggests that structure and constraint do not inherently limit meaningful participation, but the dynamics of how these frameworks are introduced and by whom remain critical.

In contrast, other labs offer examples where the content and format of the action were left more open-ended, with greater emphasis placed on youth agency in defining the focus and nature of the intervention. For instance, in UDMJ (ISRZ), students independently proposed an intervention within their dormitory, motivational stickers to support peer well-being. Similarly, in UDNZ (ISRZ), the group co-developed the idea of "Night Living Room" social evenings to foster inclusion and address issues related to addiction and social isolation. Other contexts, such as Pineda (UB), Mytilene and Kalloni (LATRA), and Trinitat Nova T and N (UB), also aimed to facilitate open-ended action planning processes.

However, it is important to note that, despite the more open structure, only in a few labs were these student-generated proposals actually implemented. For the most part, they remained at the level of intention or reflective discussion, often due to feasibility constraints or lack of time and institutional support.

This contrast reveals a fundamental methodological tension: more structured formats may enhance implementation and engagement, but at the cost of limiting youth-led decision-making. Conversely, open-ended approaches may support stronger youth ownership and agency yet face greater barriers to realising action in practice. These dilemmas challenge binary assumptions about structure versus freedom and invite us to deeper reflect on how to design participatory frameworks that balance guidance, autonomy and feasibility.

7.3.2.2.3 Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

The Act phase in the CCLAB model was conceived as a moment of consolidation, where young people move from envisioning possible futures to co-designing and prototyping actions that could lead to meaningful transformation. This phase brought significant opportunities, including increased engagement, a sense of ownership over the process, and, at times, a deepened connection between young people and their communities.

However, the implementation of the Act phase revealed a number of recurring tensions and structural challenges. One of the most pervasive obstacles was the constraint of time. This frequently reduced the ability to move from ideation to action, often forcing participants and facilitators to rush through the final stages of the cycle. As a result, many ideas remained at the level of proposals or symbolic outputs, rather than fully implemented actions. Furthermore, in some labs, this resulted in participants feeling rushed or overwhelmed, with the quality of the action subordinated to the need to present something before the end of the lab's timeline. This tension was particularly visible in transitions from the Envision phase to the Act phase. While the former often stimulated creative and critical reflection, the latter required a shift toward pragmatism, planning, and decision making on ideas that often were still not completely consolidated.

Another tension lies in the gap between visibility and voice, on one hand, and real impact, on the other. In several labs, ideas generated by participants were presented to relevant stakeholders, such as city council representatives, or social workers. While these presentations were often meaningful and valued, they also raised ethical questions. For

some students, being invited to present their ideas was experienced as validating and motivating. However, for others, it raised concerns about false hope and performative participation. The act of being "heard" does not necessarily translate into structural change or material outcomes, highlighting the risk of symbolic inclusion without real power redistribution.

Moreover, the analysis shows epistemological tensions around the definition of "action" itself. In some labs, actions were predefined by facilitators or shaped by existing project structures, which limited the possibility of youth-led decision-making. In other situations, participants had more freedom to choose both the content and format of their actions but lacked the structural support to bring their ideas to fruition. These contrasting dynamics reveal the importance of critically interrogating who defines what counts as action, and under what conditions.

Ultimately, the challenges and frictions of the Act phase foreground the need for reflexivity in participatory research design. Methodological decisions are never neutral. They shape the space of possibility for participants and influence how power circulates within the lab. For participatory processes to be genuinely transformative, they must grapple with these tensions openly, recognising that empowering youth requires more than inviting them to speak or create. It means rethinking the temporalities, expectations, and ethics of action itself.

7.3.3 The Reflect Phase

In the CCLAB model, the Reflect phase is conceived as the concluding stage. While reflection takes place throughout the entire lab, the primary aim of this phase is to encourage participants to critically review the processes undertaken during the lab, discuss key outcomes, consider the potential impact of their proposals, and, more broadly, engage in a collective space for reflection. Building on the findings of previous PAR cycles, specific refinements were introduced in the third PAR cycle to address the challenges related to students' limited engagement in the reflective stage. In particular, the most relevant improvements involved experimenting with creative formats to support a shared final evaluation and embedding opportunities for reflection more consistently across all phases of the lab. The following section presents the facilitation strategies employed to achieve these aims.

7.3.3.1 Reflection as a Final Shared Evaluation

Most of the labs deliberately designed and facilitated a concrete reflective exercise or closing ritual. To this end, different strategies were employed. Within them, the most prominent were the organization of Focus Group with youth or the use of creative and playful methods.

7.3.3.1.1 Focus Groups to Support Final Shared Evaluation

In several cases, the final shared evaluation was facilitated through the organization of a focus group with the participating youth. This happened in Trinitat Nova T and N (UB), Pineda (UB), Coláiste Bríde (TCD), UDNZ (ISRZ) and UDMJ (ISRZ). The focus group aimed at providing an opportunity to look back over the entire process and offered a space for collective reflection both on and beyond the lab, while also serving to ritualise the closure of the process. The focus group was also a valuable tool for assessment, as it forms part of the Critical ChangeLab model's evaluation plan. Thus, the focus group served a dual purpose: to provide participants with a sense of closure to the process, and to evaluate the experience from a research perspective.

Through the focus group, participants managed both to evaluate the process as well as to open new paths for discussion. For instance, In the Trinitat Nova T Lab (UB), students drew parallels between friendships, institutional relations, and the importance of mutual care, recognising that emotional responsibility and collective awareness are foundational to building equitable, participatory communities within educational spaces. In Trinitat Nova N lab (UB), a notable tension emerged during the discussion regarding participants' understandings of democratic practices giving rise to a strong debate on defending their rights and the value of protest and dialogue. Similarly, in the Pineda lab (UB) students, beyond expressing a general feeling of not having enough time to work in depth, they also opened a conversation focused on the perception of democracy at school, where students expressed that neither they nor their teachers had the power to change the system, describing the school as a 'dictatorship' rather than a democracy.

7.3.3.1.2 Creative Methods to Support Final Shared Evaluation

In some labs, the reflective component was embedded within a creative or maker activity, such as zine making in DYFF (TCD), DYFC (TCD) and UDDP (ISRZ), PechaKucha creation (AI Ambassadors-OULU lab) or podcast creation (Verein Saum-AE) or game design (Don Bosco and Damstede Lyceum-WAAG labs).

This approach emerged from discussions in earlier PAR cycles, where the research team observed that participants were far more engaged during the making phases than during dedicated reflection sessions. In response, some partners intentionally combined the two dimensions, designing reflecting-while-making activities that encouraged critical thinking while sustaining participants' motivation and creative flow.

Many labs included the zine creation as a concluding and reflective activity. In DYFF and DYFC (TDC), participants were introduced to the concept of zine and shown how to make one. They were given a prompt to respond to and have 30 mins to draw or collage their reflection or response to the prompt. The teacher from the DYFF lab noted that basing the zine prompts on the CCLAB phases had a "definite effect" and made an "impact" on how students reflected on their learning journey. UDDP (ISRZ) also used zine making as one of their reflective activities. In this example, the zine was also the main outcome of the lab. Participants were organised in groups, each of which designed and produced a zine with the main insights they have achieved during their research process on food waste (the topic of the lab) to distribute it at the dormitory (see Figure 10). However, with the end of the school year approaching, a lot of participants were unable to attend sessions due to their obligations related to school assignments. This resulted with poor attendance, smaller number of produced zines – only two – and only partially a successful session.

Figure 10. Fragment of One of the Zines Produced by Participants in ISRZ – Dora Pejačević

Finally, the Pablo Neruda lab (EUROALTER) also included the zine creation as a strategy to conclude and reflect about the lab. This activity involved creating a chart to record each of

the actions and discussions carried out throughout the process. The approach proved highly effective, particularly as students chose to work in groups, fostering discussion and the exchange of ideas. The assessment method itself was especially valuable: it enabled students to take a comprehensive view of the entire lab, revisiting each stage while providing a clear, structured space to express both what they appreciated and what they found less engaging.

In the AI Ambassadors lab (OULU), participants were encouraged to create PechaKucha presentations to summarize their process and discuss about it. The specific learning goal of this reflective Pecha Kucha was to develop participants' ability to synthesize and communicate their experiences of participation in the AI Ambassador program clearly, creatively, and concisely within a structured, time-limited format. This method encourages critical reflection, helping participants to articulate what they did, how they approached a topic, and what they learned, while also fostering visual storytelling skills using impactful imagery and minimal text.

Instead, the Verein Saum lab (AE) concluded with a podcast creation. The culminating moment of reflection took place during the podcast creation session, where participants were able to reflect on and gather all the reflections and contributions from the previous sessions.

Finally, the Don Bosco and the Damstede Lyceum labs (WAAG). In those labs, the reflective phase was proposed through two playful and creative activities: "Remake and existing game" and "Playing each other's games". Participants first receive a printout of all the concepts they have encountered so far as a reminder. Then they can choose a game they want to work with. They can choose between Jenga, Memory, Go Fish or Twister. In their group, they work on redesigning the game. They are allowed to add something or change something using the concepts of the labs and test it. Then, participants play each other's games and give constructive feedback. They are asked to do so with empathy, putting themselves in the shoes of someone younger than themselves (the target audience for the games). Students finish their game and create clear instructions so that others can play it. Then they switch, so that each group can play the game created by another group.

To sum up, these activities sought to embed critical reflection within a playful, engaging format. In this way, the activity acted as a catalyst, helping participants feel comfortable expressing themselves without the formality of a focus group, allowing feedback, insights, and critiques to emerge more spontaneously and with a lighter tone.

7.3.3.2 Reflection Woven Throughout the Lab

Some CCLABs integrated reflection as a continuous practice, often embedded within creative or collaborative work, rather than reserving it for a distinctive “final” moment. In this approach, reflection aligns with the research notion of reflexivity, where reflective thinking is woven throughout the entire inquiry process. This allows participants to develop a more conscious awareness of the process itself, make informed decisions, and express their views on the functioning of the ongoing lab. Facilitators, in turn, can incorporate participants’ suggestions into future sessions, enabling them to exercise their agency and voice in shaping the lab’s evolving design. This ongoing dialogue transforms reflection into an active tool for co-creation and shared ownership of the process.

A relevant example is shown in DYFC (TCD), where they used a “Stop-Start-Continue” game at the end of each session. In this activity, participants use post-it notes to place their reflections and suggestions in a large whiteboard or flipchart divided into three sections: *Stop* (things that are not working or should be discontinued), *Start* (new ideas or changes students would like to see) and *Continue* (aspects that are working well and should be maintained). After every participant has placed their suggestions in the board, the facilitator reads through them with the group, encouraging open discussion and clarification where needed. Where feasible, suggestions are implemented or followed up on in future sessions. This activity is an adaptation of the Fridge-Bin-Washing Machine activity, an evaluation instrument used during PAR Cycle 1 –but discarded in PAR Cycle 2 because it was not working well for all groups– to gather continuous feedback from the participants across the lab. It encourages reflection on what is working, what needs improvement, and what new ideas could be introduced. There is a responsibility to act on feedback and suggestions if you ask for them from students, which may put a facilitator in an awkward position or create additional work in an all-day week-long programme.

Similarly, at the end of each session of the AI Ambassadors lab (OULU), participants were encouraged to make a brief reflection through the creation of a social media post. At the end of each day, each group creates one social media post to reflect on their experiences, insights, or questions. This could be a photo, video, quote, sketch, or short caption, anything that captures what made them reflect about AI in everyday decision making. The goal was to “produce materials to trigger public awareness and debate about AI in decision-making.” The researchers provided information about the social media accounts used for creating

posts. Guiding prompts included: What did I learn or unlearn today? What surprised or challenged me? What's something I want others to know or think about? How does this topic/discussion connect to the world or my community? What does be an AI Ambassador mean to me today?

7.3.3.3 Opportunities, Tensions, and Challenges

Across the different labs, the reflective phases, whether woven into the process, anchored in a closing activity, or linked to creative outputs, played a critical role in consolidating learning, strengthening social cohesion, and surfacing unresolved tensions. Participants often reported feeling more aware of injustice and the potential of collective action.

In this third iteration, the use of playful and participatory formats often helped overcoming the reluctance to reflective moments identified in the previous iterations, while also fostering a sense of being heard. However, deep reflection is necessary to understand and address the lack of motivation that young people have sometimes shown when participating in activities that require greater concentration and attention, such as reflection. The inclusion of games and stimulating activities is the result of observations in previous PAR cycles that led researchers to reformulate their strategies in response to the lack of interest, participation, and ability of some groups to engage in reflective activities. Although the results have been evaluated positively in this third PAR cycle as far as the reflective phase is concerned, researchers and educators need to question these issues from a perspective that goes beyond the limits of the scope of CCLAB model.

7.3.4 Transversal Issues and Tensions

Through the analysis of the different PAR cycles, a series of general issues have emerged, insights that go beyond specific methods or phases and instead speak to the ethical, political, and epistemological dimensions of participatory practice. These reflections are not tied to a particular stage of the process but rather arise from the intersections between diverse experiences, tensions, and situated challenges encountered throughout the labs.

In this section, we do not focus on methodological procedures per se, but rather on the broader questions and dilemmas that surfaced across different contexts. These reflections stem from a triangulated analysis involving the collective reflections of the researchers, the

feedback and lived experiences of participating students, and the insights shared by educators.

Together, these perspectives have allowed us to identify a set of transversal themes that illuminate the complexity and ambivalence of participatory inquiry. What follows is a discussion of the most salient of these reflections, which aim to open up critical conversations rather than close them, and to inform both the ongoing rethinking of the PAR model and the practical engagement of those who facilitate or participate in such processes.

7.3.4.1 Facilitation Strategies VS the Mismatch with Traditional Schooling

As already pointed out in the previous iterations, hierarchies in traditional education environments and adult control played a significant role in several CCLABs, making students struggle to experience true agency. In some labs, attempts to introduce collaborative, student-led practices clashed with rigid school norms and student expectations, particularly regarding discipline and roles. This was described in the Europaschule (AE) lab, where attempts to cocreate classroom rules conflicted with the local school culture. Specifically, the idea of transferring part of the responsibility for classroom management to the students clashed both with their expectations and with the usual hierarchical structure, limiting the effectiveness of the method. Resistance arose, as many considered classroom management to be the teacher's exclusive responsibility. In this sense, the teacher's intervention to impose silence reinforced this barrier and hindered the collective construction of solutions.

Similar situations emerged during the Mytilene and Kalloni (LATRA) labs and in the DYFF (TCD) and DYFC (TCD) labs. In Mytilene and Kalloni, researchers described how the first session of the lab resembled a conventional school lesson: students entered the room, took their usual seats, and prepared to start, unaware that something different was unfolding. Despite being informed that this was not a standard class but part of a broader initiative involving theatre and creative workshops, they approached it with the same mindset as any other lesson. The familiar classroom environment, along with the presence of their regular teacher, likely reinforced that perception.

Likewise, in DYFF (TCD), facilitators observed that adult control constrained participants' agency: students raised their hands to go to the toilet, were assigned seating, and were even grouped through prearranged post-its rather than collaboratively. Similar patterns

were reported in DYFC (TCD), where the structured nature of the workshops, resembling traditional schooling, limited the space for participants to assume agency.

On the other hand, labs such as UDNZ (ISRZ), UDMJ (ISRZ) and Trinitat Nova T/N (UB), suggest that when structured but flexible environments are provided, this facilitated a growing sense of empowerment in youth. For instance, UDNZ (ISRZ) described that participants enjoyed PAR Cycle 3 more than the previous one (in which the group had also participated) primarily because they felt they had more opportunities to influence the process and to speak openly and freely about the topic. Similarly, also in UDMJ (ISRZ) and Trinitat Nova T/N (UB), both participants and facilitators emphasised the importance of adaptability and of creating a safe space. Trust-building was identified as a crucial dimension for encouraging greater participation and expression. For instance, in Trinitat Nova T and N, the use of small groups with research mentoring facilitated focus and engagement, which proved particularly relevant given the pre-existing power dynamics (including bullying, ableist tendencies, and far-right ideology) that negatively shaped the group's democratic disposition and constrained participation in some activities. Similarly, in UDMJ (ISRZ), open discussions were essential for addressing sensitive topics such as self-perception and mental health. Participants valued the possibility of sharing personal and intimate experiences, which deepened group trust and reinforced engagement.

To sum up, this overview highlights that the Critical ChangeLab framework is not merely a "lesson plan" but rather an "attitude towards youth agency" in its implementation. Furthermore, it highlights, the previously identified lack of democratic experiences among youth. As stated by one participant in the Mytilene and Kalloni lab (LATRA), when asked about how classroom rules are made and who decides them: "the teacher always decides" (LATRA, Researcher Diaries).

While these considerations may partly exceed the scope of the CCLAB model, they nevertheless point to a broader need in terms of educational policy: to promote schools as democratic spaces. This requires, on the one hand, policies that embed democratic culture in schools not only as a subject in the curriculum, but as a lived practice, and on the other, the establishment of real mechanisms for student participation in institutional decision-making.

7.3.4.2 Symbolic Participation and the Risks of Disillusionment

Another tension that reinforces the outcomes identified during the previous evaluation is the risk of generating processes in which youth participation becomes merely symbolic, lacking real impact or continuity. This concern was explicitly voiced by students who participated in PAR Cycle 2, many of whom expressed a growing sense of fatigue and resistance toward projects that invite them to share their voices, opinions, and ideas, but ultimately fail to translate those contributions into meaningful change.

In this third cycle, this resistance to symbolic participation was particularly evident in the case of Coláiste Bríde (TCD). At the end of the lab, students were given the opportunity to present their proposals for improving their neighbourhood to a group of local stakeholders. While the opportunity to speak was initially perceived as empowering, many participants later expressed frustration and scepticism. They felt that their ideas were not taken seriously and that the presentations resembled symbolic performances rather than genuine dialogues with the potential to influence decision-making. As one student put it: "It gave us a voice, but I don't think anyone will actually do anything about it" (TCD, Coláiste Bríde, Focus Group).

Despite feeling heard, the students' reflections revealed a fragile sense of hope and a limited perception of their own agency. The experience, while validating on the surface, left many with the impression that their participation had no real consequences. One participant summarized this sentiment by saying: "It was like a false sense of hope... because it's unlikely we'll hear from them again." This perception of being involved in processes that do not lead to visible outcomes contributes to a broader disillusionment with participatory initiatives and raises important ethical and pedagogical questions.

From a critical perspective, it becomes essential for educators and researchers to reflect on the viability and sustainability of the projects we invite students to engage in. Repeated exposure to initiatives that never materialise or fail to generate follow-up can have a counterproductive effect, diminishing students' willingness to participate and eroding their trust in institutional actors. In this sense, the accumulation of symbolic experiences may hinder rather than foster youth engagement.

Addressing this tension requires a commitment to designing participatory processes that go beyond tokenism. It is crucial to ensure that youth contributions are not only acknowledged but also integrated into decision-making frameworks in ways that are visible and meaningful. Without this commitment, we risk reinforcing scepticism and disengagement, rather than cultivating genuine agency and transformative potential.

7.3.4.3 Intersectionality and Participation

PAR Cycle 3 revealed recurring themes related to different intersectional dynamics and their impact in shaping participation, agency, and critical consciousness among participants. In particular, dimensions related to gender, cultural and migrant background, socio-economic status and age were analysed.

- **Gender and power dynamics:** Across several labs, including Europaschule Linz (AE), DYFF (TCD), Coláiste Bríde (TCD), Skupna Točka (KI), Don Bosco (WAAG) and Pineda (UB), gendered power dynamics consistently shaped participation. Male students frequently dominated discussions and assumed leadership roles, even in female-majority groups. Young female participants, particularly those from ethnic or migrant backgrounds, were often sidelined or less active unless alternative, creative methods were introduced. These dynamics reflect entrenched patriarchal norms, where traditional discursive formats privilege masculinised modes of expression, for example asserting a loud argument in an open debate. This happened particularly at Pineda and at Trinitat Nova (UB), where if not for creative interventions like art and design methodologies, some female voices would have been muted and excluded from the public discussion. This tendency is even more visible in the Pineda lab (UB). In this context, when the lab moved from debate-based methods to creative tasks, the group of racialised girls showed a strong shift in their engagement and ended up designing the most critical and reflective proposals of the whole group. These patterns underscore the importance of rethinking facilitation strategies and integrating inclusive, multimodal formats that challenge dominant discursive norms and open space for marginalised perspectives to emerge and thrive.
- **Race, culture, and internalized oppressions:** Across several labs, including Trinitat Nova-Group N (UB), DYFF (Trinity College), Pineda (UB), LATRA and AI Ambassadors (Oulu), racialised and migrant-background youth navigated complex dynamics of cultural belonging and exclusion. Participants encountered conflicting narratives, such as the veil that covers a young woman's hair being framed either as oppression or as a personal choice (Trinitat Nova Group N - UB). These tensions often revealed underlying xenophobia, essentialist assumptions, and unequal recognition of students' lived experiences. In Trinitat Nova, a student's explicitly racist remark ("F**cking pakistanis") exposed deep-rooted biases and the difficulty of fostering

truly inclusive dialogue. Meanwhile, cultural diversity was superficially celebrated in examples such as the Europaschule Linz lab (AE) without addressing the structural hierarchies that persist in school environments. Some students from ethnic minorities and non-European background have internalised other dominant narratives, such as anti-LGBTQ+ discourse or anti-migrant sentiments, demonstrating how overlapping systems of oppression can reproduce marginalisation even within minority groups. On this matter, it was particularly relevant a moment where a racialised girl's defence of the veiling of woman's hair as choice clashed with a peer's framing of it as oppression, revealing colonial gendered discourses (Trinitat Nova Group N - UB). Yet, again, creative methods such as arts-based practices pervasively implemented in almost all labs, emerged as powerful tools for visibility and resistance, suggesting that reimagined participatory formats can better challenge hegemonic narratives and affirm diverse identities within educational spaces.

- Socioeconomic class, migration, and the limits of participation:** Across labs such as Schulungszentrum (AE), Trinitat Nova Group N (UB), Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), and Verein Saum (AE), socioeconomic precarity significantly shaped young people's capacity for engagement. In Schulungszentrum (AE), unemployed migrant youth struggled to engage in speculative or creative tasks, likely due to material instability and future planning temporal deprivation, where immediate needs preclude long-term thinking. Similarly, at Verein Saum, participants found it difficult to imagine futures beyond their current circumstances, signaling the impact of class-based constraints on agency. At Damstede Lyceum (WAAG), mockery of authority figures reflected both resistance to systemic neglect and disillusionment with institutional power. Meanwhile, the educator at Trinitat Nova (UB) linked weaker argumentation skills to students' disadvantaged backgrounds, risking a deficit perspective that overlooks structural barriers and reinforces inequality.
- Adulthood and power hierarchies:** In multiple labs, including Mytilene and Kalloni (LATRA), Trinitat Nova Groups T and N (UB), AI Ambassadors (Oulu), Coláiste Bríde (TCD), DYFC-Dublin (TCD), and Europaschule Linz (AE), youth participants highlighted the persistent influence of adulthood in shaping their experiences. Young people frequently described adults as gatekeepers of legitimacy, with teachers or facilitators controlling decision-making and limiting genuine youth agency. At

Mytilene and Kalloni lab (LATRA), students critiqued top-down rulemaking, while at Group T from Trinitat Nova Institute, viewed collective action as a form of resistance against adult power. In Europaschule Linz (AE), participants resisted adult-directed team assignments but lacked the structures to collaborate autonomously, reflecting internalised hierarchies. Educator biases, particularly assumptions about the capabilities of socioeconomically disadvantaged or racialised youth, were evident in both groups at Trinitat Nova (UB), reinforcing marginalization under the guise of pedagogical guidance and even risking the unintentional reinforcement of deficit-based thinking. These examples demonstrate that institutional power dynamics intersect with age, class, and race, often undermining the democratic aims of participatory methodologies. Challenging adultist assumptions is essential to foster truly inclusive, youth-led engagement within educational and research settings.

In conclusion, this analysis illustrates that the feeling of being entitled to speak and to participate develop unevenly across the intersecting identities of participants throughout almost all CCLabs. While some youth identified racism, others failed to recognise homophobia or other forms of exclusion, underscoring the need for an intersectional approach integrated within the methodologies of each Lab. To advance equitable participation, intersectionality must inform both the analytic and practical dimensions of the PAR design. This involves centring marginalised voices through creative, multimodal methods, disaggregating participation data, and equipping facilitators to navigate complex power dynamics with clarity and care. Structural barriers, such as linguistic barriers or other types of exclusion, must be addressed through targeted material and effective support. Ultimately, operationalising intersectionality requires reflexive, responsive methodologies that foreground race, class, gender, and age not as isolated variables, but as interlocking systems of power. Only through such intentional design can participatory processes avoid reproducing the very hierarchies they aim to challenge.

7.4 Overall Considerations on the Outcomes of PAR Cycle 3

The third PAR cycle shows notable progress compared to previous PAR cycles, specifically addressing needs identified in earlier iterations. Key developments can be summarised as follows:

- 1. Shared understanding of learning and expected learning outcomes:** While the second iteration already introduced the definition of specific learning goals and a competencies framework that helped align perspectives on learning, the revision of the competencies model between the second and third PAR Cycles, reducing learning objectives to four key areas, proved to be more agile and effective. This streamlined structure facilitated both the organisation of the Labs and their evaluation, and contributed to consolidating a shared vision of learning goals and methodological alignment among partners.
- 2. Stronger integration of youth voices into the methodological design:** Efforts were made to incorporate youth voices into the methodological design of the CCLAB. In particular, as outcomes of the second PAR cycle, several key aspects emerged as critical to improve the design of the methodological model:
 - Participants showed a clear preference for addressing issues directly affecting their everyday lives, rather than abstract or distant global challenges.
 - Difficulties in understanding systemic interconnections were evident, with participants often adopting individualistic perspectives and struggling to grasp the complex, interrelated nature of social and ecological problems.
 - Hands-on, practical activities and artistic or creative methods were strongly favoured, indicating the need to prioritise experiential and expressive approaches in the model.
 - There was a certain reluctance toward deliberative and reflective moments, suggesting that these practices require more thoughtful integration to be effective and engaging.
 - Activities connected to contexts outside the institution proved particularly impactful, reinforcing the importance of situating learning in real-world environments.
 - Participants had trouble imagining alternative futures, highlighting the need to incorporate more tools that foster critical imagination and prospective thinking.

- Intersectional factors such as gender, migration background, and socio-economic conditions played a significant role in shaping participation, pointing to the necessity of paying additional attention to these dimensions.

In response, the third PAR cycle implemented several strategies to address these issues. Notably, there was a broader use of creative and artistic methods aimed at fostering inclusive participation and generating alternative forms of deliberation. Deliberate efforts were also made to collaboratively define themes with participants, grounding the process in their lived experiences and ensuring their voices actively shaped the lab's development.

Additionally, strategies were introduced to support a shift from individualistic to more systemic and collective perspectives. These included approaches focused on sharing visions, co-creation, collaborative inquiry, and prioritising the co-construction of knowledge over individual viewpoints. Furthermore, to overcome resistance to purely dialogical or reflective practices, methods integrating the body, emotions, and affect were employed as resources for collective thinking and knowledge generation. In this line, also, during the final evaluation, creative and playful strategies were tested to move beyond debate-centred models.

Finally, methods to support the exploration of alternative futures were expanded, incorporating tools that foster critical imagination and prospective thinking, and greater attention was given to observing how intersectionality shapes participation.

Taken together, these developments reflect a consistent effort to move beyond traditional academic models of knowledge construction, embracing a situated, experiential, affective, creative, and embodied approach. Nonetheless, despite these improvements, specific challenges persisted in the PAR Cycle 3. The most significant were related to time constraints, the mismatch between the value of the CCLAB model and traditional schooling and issues related to participants' agency. As in PAR Cycle 1 and PAR Cycle 2, students' sense of agency remains relatively weak. Moreover, new concerns emerged regarding the risks of symbolic participation and repeated exposure to initiatives that fail to materialise, which may ultimately reduce students' willingness to engage and hinder rather than foster youth participation.

3. Need for a more defined methodological structure: To support meaningful implementation by educators, balancing flexibility with practical guidance, the third phase of analysis focused on integrating various methods into the model's architecture. Special emphasis was placed on identifying within each stage of the CCLAB model:

- **Key pedagogical moments**, understood as critical moments within process that highlight essential aspects of the process and its goals.
- **Strategies**, understood as different approaches that have been employed in the key pedagogical moment to achieve specific educational goals. These strategies provide overarching orientations within which concrete methods and activities are selected and implemented.
- **Methods**, as examples of concrete techniques that have been showed to be effective to support specific learning goals related to the overarching strategy.
- **Strengths and Opportunities**, understood as the observed benefits and potential related to specific strategies and methods.
- **Challenges**, understood as tensions, difficulties and issue that need to be taken into account by researchers and practitioners.

These outcomes, reported in previous sections, are summarised in Table 18.

Table 18. *Summary of Key Outcomes*

Phase of the CCLAB Model	Key Pedagogical Moments	Strategies	Methods	Strengths / Opportunities	Challenges
Question & Analyse	Defining the theme of the PAR cycle Goal: centre the PAR cycle on youth	Pre-defined theme	Pre-defined theme with voluntary enrollment	Although a pre-defined theme can pose the risk of constraining participants' engagement, such risk does not arise when participation is based on voluntary enrollment.	
		Broad theme co-shaped	Mapping of participants'	Deepen participants'	Time constraints and institutional

Phase of the CCLAB Model	Key Pedagogical Moments	Strategies	Methods	Strengths / Opportunities	Challenges
		with participants	concerns (e.g., what topic matters to you and do you want to make visible?") Frustration mapping	engagement and perceived agency	constraints may reduce the freedom to co-define the theme
		Theme fully defined by participants			
	Co-constructing knowledge around the chosen theme Goal: building a shared understanding of the theme	Sharing situated experiences to co-construct knowledge	–	Increased engagement when participants are invited to engage with topics that connect to their lives Helpful to anchor abstract concepts	Risk of touching sensitive issues Risk to remain at the level of personal concerns without connecting this issue to systemic dynamics
		Sharing views to co-construct knowledge	Fishbowl discussion method Walking debate Spontaneous debate	Foster exchange of perspectives and collective reflection	Presence of dominating voices / unequal participation Conversation that lost focus
		Thinking together to co-construct knowledge	"5 whys" method Visual mapping	Visual strategies enabled participants in organizing and sharing their process of knowledge construction Allow move beyond surface-level responses	Possible difficulties in establishing connection with abstract concepts
Co-creating to co-construct knowledge	Meme making Symbols creation Speculative design (e.g.,	Recognise the value of different ways on knowing Allow inclusive participation	The proposed activity needs to be well integrated with the process (otherwise it may		

Phase of the CCLAB Model	Key Pedagogical Moments	Strategies	Methods	Strengths / Opportunities	Challenges
			“break it before you make it”) Postcards from the future	Allow grounding complex/abstract concepts Allow embodied experimentation with collective decision-making	look as a “decoration”)
		Emotion and affect as a resource to co-construct knowledge	Empathy exercise Collective reflection based on emotional response Guided visualization	Enhance students’ engagement	–
		The body as a resource to co-construct knowledge	Freeze-frame tableaux Theatre of the oppressed	Support perspective-taking and empathy	Resistance to embodied practices by some students Contingent upon the facilitator training in body-based practices
		Play-with to co-construct knowledge	Use specifically designed games to support reflection	Support engagement Allow to interact with complex concepts in a playful way	–
	Broadening perspectives around the topic Goal: create conditions for challenging assumptions, incorporating new voices and	Co-research around the topic	Desk research Conducting interview and surveys Observational and visual methods (e.g., photovoice)	Encourage critical questioning of social issues Enhance participants’ critical awareness Allow shift in viewpoints	Decision making during the research process: who chooses what to investigate and how? Need for training participants in research methods

Phase of the CCLAB Model	Key Pedagogical Moments	Strategies	Methods	Strengths / Opportunities	Challenges
	engage with unfamiliar viewpoints		Ethnographic methods (e.g., field diaries) Community mapping		
		Inclusion of external actors/voices	Artistic fruition and participation in cultural events Visit to other institutions Experts' interventions	Deepen emotional engagement Broaden perspectives	Experts' intervention if not properly framed may run the risk of reproducing top-down educational models
Envision	Imagining alternative futures Goal: move beyond present constraints and explore other possibilities	Future forecasting	Future triangles Future wheel	Support critical reflection on the present Allow engage with the past to reflect on the present and the future	Difficulties in thinking beyond current realities Risk of overemphasising feasibility
		Speculative futures	Future postcards Future scenarios Speculative design Design Fiction Future Exhibition	Displacement of dominant forms of thoughts Helpful in moving beyond normative approaches	Reproduction of sci-fi cliché Gap between imagined possibilities and actionable tasks
Act	Co-create small scale interventions Goal: support transformative agency; identify paths and actions toward transformation	Final outcomes fully defined by participants through the process	Brainstorming and prototyping Public presentation of the proposal	Increase sense of ownership and motivation	Difficulties in truly implementing the proposals Risk of reproducing false hope of "projects that go nowhere"
		Final outcomes as a predefined design task	Zine-making Podcast creation Game design	Creation of a tangible output that give account of the learning process	Limiting youth decision making

Phase of the CCLAB Model	Key Pedagogical Moments	Strategies	Methods	Strengths / Opportunities	Challenges
			Audiovisual production		
Reflect	Shared evaluation Goal: encourage participants to critically review the processes undertaken	Final shared evaluation	Focus group Creative methods	Closing ritual Allow overall participatory evaluation Open paths for new debates Creative methods support more plural forms of deliberation	-
		Reflection woven in the lab	Start-stop-continue technique Reflection through the creation of a social media post	Allow continuous feedback from the participants across the lab.	Facilitators responsibility to act on feedback and suggestions

8. Final Reflections on the Iterative Design Process

The co-design of the CCLAB model among multiple partners and stakeholders has proven to be a complex and layered endeavour. Inevitably, it has required an ongoing meta-reflection on decision-making, participation, and co-creation itself. From the outset, the process demanded the construction of a shared understanding that could not be taken for granted but had to be progressively built through the interplay between empirical practice and theoretical reflection. This shared understanding did not emerge as a static agreement, but rather as a living, evolving construct shaped by discussions, negotiations, and embodied experiences across different contexts. It has meant collectively interrogating the meaning of the concepts we employ –not only in their theoretical sense, but also in terms of how they orient our actions, position us as facilitators, and structure the dynamics within the labs. After the first PAR cycle, for example, it became evident that we needed to articulate a clearer and more consensual meaning of what we refer to when we speak of democratic education, participation, and learning. These questions resurfaced time and again, leading us repeatedly to confront deeper issues: what exactly do we mean by action? How do we understand agency, and whose agency is being fostered or constrained in particular moments of the process? Evaluation has played a central role in this regard, functioning not only as a mechanism of accountability but also as a generative practice that progressively shaped shared understanding, fostered methodological alignment, and incorporated diverse voices into the iterative design.

At the same time, the process has required us to reflect critically on how participation takes shape in practice. Questions about decision-making, who ultimately decides, and in what way, have accompanied the whole process. These reflections, in turn, compelled us to look at our own positioning as researchers and facilitators, and to ask whether the level and type of involvement we expect should be the same for all participants. During the second PAR cycle, these issues became especially pronounced. On one hand, there was a clear recognition of the need to strengthen the integration of young people's voices in the design process. On the other, tensions arose around what kind of engagement could be meaningfully expected from them. A telling example was the attempt to involve youth in the

co-definition of competences, a proposal that ultimately had to be abandoned because it proved too abstract and disconnected from their lived experience. This moment crystallised an important insight: co-creating does not necessarily mean identical forms of participation (Bettencourt, 2020). As Thomas & O’Kane (1998) remind us, participatory processes involve a distribution of responsibilities that must recognise the different skills, experiences, and goals that participants bring. In this sense, the attempt and its failure were instructive. They forced us to acknowledge the limits of certain expectations and to refine our understanding of what democratic co-creation can look like in practice. As a youth researcher cited by Tuck et al. (2008) put it: “fantasies that people might have about PAR, especially among youth, is that we all have to be the same and do everything the same way. PAR isn’t synchronized swimming!” (p. 68).

This process has also been one of learning from practice, drawing insights from what unfolded, making adjustments, and opening up new questions. In this regard, several shifts are particularly worth highlighting. First, over the course of the labs, there was a gradual move towards strategies, methods, and ways of working that sought to move beyond traditional academic models of knowledge construction, instead embracing situated, experiential, affective, creative, and embodied approaches. This reflects a clear commitment to epistemic diversity and pluralism, valuing multiple ways of knowing. At the same time, the evidence gathered throughout the process increasingly underscored the value of creative and artistic strategies, not only as moments of expression or production of results, but as transversal practices that actively shaped the construction of knowledge among young people. Finally, another important shift was the growing recognition of the need to carefully observe what was happening in practice, not only in terms of young people’s responses, but also in relation to our own ways of acting as researchers and facilitators. This required a more critical and reflexive stance towards the kinds of discourses and practices we were enacting within the process. Nevertheless, while meaningful progress and transformations took place, it is equally important to acknowledge the challenges that remained unresolved. Among the most significant were the difficulty of truly fostering transformative agency among young people, and the persistent constraints imposed by the temporal limits of the institutional framework, boundaries that, despite our efforts, proved difficult to overcome.

Looking back, the co-design process can be understood less as a path toward a finished product and more as a journey of collective exploration. The tensions, frictions, and

moments of failure were as generative as the agreements and achievements, for they revealed the lived complexities of practicing democracy in education. The process has shown us that building a shared framework is not about erasing differences, but about learning to work with them –recognising that plurality is both a challenge and a resource. In this sense, the project has been as much about developing democratic education as about enacting it.

9. Recommendations for Practitioners

Building on the outcomes of the evaluation process, this final section outlines a set of recommendations for educators engaged in democratic education. The recommendations are organised into two main blocks: the first addresses broader, more general considerations, while the second focuses on more specific and practical aspects related to the implementation of the CCLAB model.

9.1 General Recommendations

This section presents a set of recommendations that go beyond the specific implementation of the CCLAB model and address, more broadly, ways of rethinking educational practices across diverse contexts. Each recommendation is grounded in empirical evidence gathered during the process and is accompanied by possible action points.

9.1.1 Transform Learning Environments in Everyday Democratic Spaces.

One of the strongest findings across the evaluation and different contexts was the persistent lack of democratic experiences in the lives of young people. Many students reported feeling that they had little or no voice in their schools and almost no influence over their immediate environments. This sense of exclusion was reinforced by the absence of genuine democratic spaces within the school setting. Students highlighted the extremely limited opportunities for meaningful participation in decision-making processes that directly affect them, expressing a clear desire for more opportunities to contribute to school governance.

At the same time, and closely linked to these perceptions, the evaluation revealed a recurrent mismatch: efforts to introduce collaborative, student-led practices often clashed with rigid institutional norms and entrenched expectations, particularly around discipline and hierarchical roles. This evidence underscores the importance of deliberately reimagining schools, and learning environments more broadly, as spaces where students can directly experience democratic participation. Such spaces should provide opportunities to exercise agency, engage in dialogue, and influence decisions that matter to them.

Finally, in line with the previous evidence, our findings suggest that democratic understanding cannot be fully developed through abstract or institutional discussions

alone. Instead, it must be nurtured through lived experience, collaborative decision-making, and opportunities to practice democracy in meaningful, contextually relevant ways. Bridging the gap between knowing *about* democracy and learning to *do* democracy may therefore require a shift in pedagogical focus, from theory to practice. Schools must move from simply teaching about democracy to becoming sites of democracy, where everyday practices reflect democratic values such as inclusion, deliberation, and shared responsibility. Cultivating democratic culture, therefore, requires not only curriculum changes, but also intentional efforts to create the conditions, both structural and relational, that make democratic participation possible and meaningful in students' daily lives.

This evidence again reinforces the need to place a stronger effort in designing experiences that, instead of teaching about democracy, enable students to experience democratic participation. This requires, on the one hand, embedding democratic culture into schools not merely as a curricular topic but as an everyday lived practice, and on the other, establishing real and sustainable mechanisms for student participation in institutional decision-making. In this sense, the following action points are proposed:

- Move beyond a narrow, voting-based view of democracy by fostering deliberation, everyday participation, and shared decision-making.
- Create genuine opportunities for students to exercise agency, moving beyond rigid school routines (e.g., fixed seating, teacher-imposed groupings, overly structured sessions).
- Actively support student engagement and ensure that participation is grounded in genuine involvement and relevance; without engagement, participation cannot be meaningful.
- Challenge institutionalized habits and hierarchies that constrain participation, and help students imagine and experiment with alternative forms of collective organization.
- Scaffold collaborative work and co-creation process as space for experimenting on democracy by explicitly embed meta-reflection on the challenges of living and doing together within the process. The challenges surrounding collaborative work can be used as entry points for pedagogical reflection. Rather than viewing such

difficulties as failures, they can be leveraged as opportunities to engage students in critical reflection on the complexities of democratic practices.

- Foster a deeper appreciation for listening, not only as a communication skill but as a democratic practice and as a critical awareness to question whose voices are heard and whose are silenced.

9.1.2 Democracy in Education as an Attitude Toward Youth Agency

Closely connected to the previous point, another key consideration concerns the need for continuous and critical reflection by facilitators and educators on the type of facilitation model they are enacting, as well as their predisposition towards youth involvement and agency. In this sense, democratic education should not be approached merely as a “lesson plan,” but rather as an “attitude towards youth agency” in its implementation. For educators, this implies:

- Continuously questioning our expectations of young people and reflecting on the extent to which these expectations may limit their decision-making possibilities.
- Maintaining a constant attentiveness to what emerges from the process, in order to remain flexible and responsive to ongoing dynamics and challenges.
- Building trust and creating safe spaces where participants feel free to express themselves (through icebreakers, small group work, mentoring, and careful attention to power dynamics such as gender, bullying, or ideology).
- Sharing observations with participants and using them as the basis for collective reflection and action.
- Critically reflecting on the coherence between what we ask to young people, what we propose as educators, and the conditions imposed by the institutional infrastructure in which participants are embedded
- Foster a proper balance between structure and freedom by offering progressive autonomy, accompanied by clear guidance on the processes.

9.1.3 Democracy and Epistemological Pluralism

A key learning that emerged from the evaluation process was the importance of validating and providing resources that enable diverse voices to express themselves through the most meaningful and accessible means. This became particularly evident in the multiple cases, where the use of creative, artistic, and affective strategies allowed more marginalised groups to find their voice and become active participants in the process. Furthermore, creative methods were particularly well received by participants. Students highlighted how these approaches allowed them to become more engaged with the proposal and appreciated being able to break out of the usual formats and express themselves in a different way. On the other hand, several educators also stressed the potential for integrating these methodologies into future school projects, even if some of them felt that they lacked sufficient artistic knowledge to do so effectively.

In this sense, recommendations for educators address the following aspects:

- Engage in critical self-reflection about which forms of knowledge they recognise as valid and which they tend to dismiss.
- From a practical standpoint, incorporate visual, design-based, and embodied methods (e.g., collective boards, co-created artefacts) to strengthen engagement and create opportunities for different students to participate.
- Engage in specific training aimed at widening their knowledge and confidence in using visual, design-based, and embodied methods.
- Recognise and validate emotions as epistemic resources that shape how students relate to knowledge, to their peers, and to the world.

9.1.4. Be Aware of the Risks of Symbolic Participation

Another tension that emerged throughout the evaluation process concerns the risk of youth participation becoming merely symbolic, lacking real impact or continuity. This concern was explicitly voiced by students, who expressed a growing sense of fatigue and resistance toward projects that invite them to share their voices, opinions, and ideas but ultimately fail to translate those contributions into meaningful change. From a critical perspective, it is essential for educators and researchers to reflect on the viability and sustainability of the

initiatives we invite students to engage in. Repeated exposure to projects that do not materialise or lack follow-up can be counterproductive, diminishing students' willingness to participate and eroding their trust in institutional actors. In this sense, the accumulation of symbolic experiences risks hindering rather than fostering youth engagement. Addressing this tension requires a clear commitment to designing participatory processes that move beyond tokenism. Without such commitment, we risk reinforcing scepticism and disengagement instead of cultivating genuine agency and transformative potential. In this regard, the following points become crucial:

- Critically question the viability and sustainability of proposed projects to ensure they can be sustained or generate ongoing impact, rather than initiatives that “go nowhere.”
- Develop strategies to create meaningful connections with the surrounding community, so that proposals have real and tangible impact.
- Plan labs with careful attention to school calendars and time constraints.
- Advocate for sustained engagement over longer periods to enable durable cultural and democratic change.
- Always take into account the sustainability of both the process and the lab.

9.2 Recommendations for the Implementations of the CCLAB Model

9.2.1 Question & Analyse Phases

From the analysis of this phase, three key pedagogical moments were identified, together with a series of challenges linked to each of them.

- 1. Defining the theme of the PAR cycle:** This moment concerns the ways in which the topic of inquiry is selected and framed. The manner in which this decision is made has a direct impact on students' engagement, shaping their sense of ownership, relevance, and motivation to participate. When the theme emerges from students' lived realities, their involvement tends to be deeper and more sustained. Conversely, themes imposed externally or perceived as distant may risk disengagement.

2. **Co-constructing knowledge around the chosen topic:** This moment reflects the effort to build a shared, multidimensional understanding of the theme. One of the main challenges observed was students' difficulty in recognising the interconnected and systemic nature of social and eco-social issues. Their perspectives often remained fragmented, expressed either through a narrow focus on isolated behaviours, a limited geographic perspective, or a disconnection from the structural roots of problems. These challenges highlight the pedagogical necessity of providing students with conceptual and practical tools that allow them to navigate the complexity of contemporary entanglements. Rather than reducing problems to isolated or purely individual issues, students need opportunities to connect their personal concerns and experiences of inequality with broader systemic dynamics, and to begin to understand themselves as actors within larger socio-ecological systems.

3. **Broadening perspectives around the topic:** This moment focused on expanding participants' viewpoints by introducing diverse voices, experiences, and forms of knowledge into the inquiry process. Here, the challenge lies in moving beyond familiar frameworks and cultivating openness to perspectives that are different, uncomfortable, or marginal. This involves both pedagogical design and an attentiveness to power relations, ensuring that the inclusion of multiple perspectives does not reproduce hierarchies but instead nurtures dialogical and transformative learning.

From these considerations, several recommendations for practice emerge:

- **Root CCLABs in students' lived experiences:** Evidence shows a clear tendency for students to prioritize local issues that feel immediate and tangible over global challenges that appear distant in time and space. This implies enabling students to have a meaningful voice and decision-making power in selecting the topic, paying explicit attention to issues that directly affect their everyday lives and making connections outward from that point of reference.

- **Foster systemic and collective thinking:** This implies design pedagogical strategies that help students move beyond individualistic or reductionist perspectives. This involves equipping them with both conceptual frameworks and practical tools for recognising structural and systemic dimensions of problems. Pedagogical moves

may include facilitating shifts from personal anecdote to collective reflection, cultivating critical empathy and perspective-taking, and using interdisciplinary approaches that illuminate the social, ecological, and historical entanglements of contemporary challenges.

- **Explore multiple approaches to co-construct knowledge.** This implies building learning environments that validate and integrate different pathways for knowledge creation, sharing experiences and perspectives, engaging in collective reasoning, co-creating artifacts, mobilising emotions, the body, and play as legitimate resources for inquiry. In addition, actively connecting with actors and realities outside the institution can help broaden students' perspectives, anchor their inquiry in real-world contexts, and foster a deeper sense of relevance and responsibility.
- **Engage participants in empirical co-research processes.** The CCLABs offer positive evidence of relevance of engaging students as active participants in empirical research processes. The empirical approaches applied to involve young people in investigating real-world eco-social issues offered students opportunities to connect with their surroundings, hear underrepresented voices, and reflect deeply on the complexities of the issues they explored. This finding suggests the importance of involving participants in empirical research work, stressing the importance of researching not as a way of collecting information but as an empirical work that allows shaping understanding and building relationships.
- **Anchoring activities in local realities.** In the CCLAB, the integration of activities to connect with the local context, contributed to student engagement, critical reflection, and a stronger sense of purpose. In this sense, facilitating the connection with diverse external scenarios can strengthen the students' sense of agency and the real impact of their projects.

9.2.2 Envision Phase

From the analysis of the Envision phase, it emerged that future-oriented methods served as powerful entry points for fostering critical awareness among young participants, enabling them to reflect on the socio-political and ecological issues shaping their lives. These methods were effective in helping students recognise and articulate present-day challenges; yet a recurring difficulty was their capacity to imagine alternative futures. One

of the most prominent challenges was the struggle to move beyond existing realities. Across contexts, many participants found it difficult to project themselves into futures that diverged meaningfully from the present. Even when engaging with creative and speculative methods, their visions often remained anchored in familiar frames of reference. Closely linked to this tendency, a second challenge concerned the disconnection between imagined futures and critical insights, or the difficulty in translating abstract visions into actionable strategies, highlighting the need to carefully scaffold the transition from creative speculation to actionable planning. Building on these considerations, several points for reflection and recommendations emerge:

- **Recognise imagination as a core educational competency:** In order to address the contemporary crisis of imagination, educational systems must position imagination, particularly radical and critical imagination, not as a peripheral or optional skill, but as a central component of learning. This requires embedding imaginative competencies within policy frameworks and curricular structures, ensuring that imagination is formally recognised as a vital skill for the 21st century.
- **Support school-based and local initiatives that foster imaginative skills:** This implies designing learning experiences should integrate speculative, critical, and collaborative exercises, helping students build the conceptual tools and vocabularies necessary to articulate visions of alternative futures, particularly for youth from vulnerable backgrounds.
- **Clearly frame the objectives of envisioning:** Distinguish between forecasting, which relies on rational anticipation based on trends, and speculative approaches, which deliberately disrupt expectations to explore new possibilities.
- **Critically interrogate implicit narratives in future-oriented practices:** Educators should reflect on the tension between imagining alternatives and pursuing solutions, and consider the influence of solutionist approaches, particularly technosolutionism, on young people's imaginative capacities.
- **Bridge imaginative activities with research and lived realities:** This involves navigating the tension between staying confined to what is socially perceived as "possible" or "probable" and fostering speculative approaches that open meaningful spaces for creativity, affect, and alternative imaginaries.

- **Support the transition from imagining to action:** This implies providing guidance, scaffolding, and structures to help students translate ideas into meaningful initiatives.
- **Leverage challenges as pedagogical opportunities:** this address using the difficulties in imagining the future as a way to make visible the ways in which imagination is shaped by cultural frameworks, and to work with students to critically examine, expand, and transform these limits.

9.2.3 Act Phase

The analysis of the Act phase revealed the most uneven outcomes across contexts. Nonetheless, two primary tensions became particularly evident. On one hand, there was a persistent constraint of time; on the other, students often exhibited a generally negative perception of personal agency, seeing themselves as marginal actors in processes of social change. This perspective reinforced disengagement and disaffection, highlighting a crucial ethical dimension of participatory education.

These observations raise important ethical questions about the focus on production and action within educational settings. There is a pressing need to critically reflect on the potential consequences of involving students in initiatives that ultimately lead nowhere. Even when such projects are grounded in good intentions, they risk reinforcing disillusionment if students perceive them as ineffective or disconnected from tangible outcomes. An ethical approach to participatory education must consider not only what students are asked to produce, but also how their efforts are valued, sustained, and meaningfully linked to real-world impacts.

Rethinking the temporal dimensions of pedagogical practice is central to addressing these challenges. Educators must critically examine how the logic of productivism and the demand for rapid results may operate as implicit agendas within their work. Revitalizing the relationship between youth and democracy, as the model aspires to do, requires slow and sustained rhythms that allow time for trust-building, reflection, and the maturation of ideas. In many analysed labs, students were asked to make large leaps within compressed timeframes, without adequate space to integrate concepts or develop meaningful outcomes. As Han (2023) notes, “The obligation to act, or even the acceleration of life, reveals itself as an effective means of domination. If no revolution seems possible today, it

may be because we have no time to think” (p. 30). A hyper-productivist approach, therefore, risks exhausting or even suspending agency, highlighting the tension between productivity and imagination. Creating reflective and generative spaces that nurture agency requires reconsidering the temporal rhythms of pedagogy.

Key recommendations to address these challenges include:

- **Address scepticism and symbolic participation:** Ensure that youth contributions lead to tangible outcomes, avoiding tokenistic actions and reinforcing meaningful engagement.
- **Avoid focusing solely on final products:** Action should not be equated solely with achieving predetermined outcomes; processes themselves are valuable sites of learning and reflection.
- **Make processes and results visible:** Transparently share both the process and its outcomes with participants and wider audiences to reinforce the value of contributions.
- **Plan for sustainability:** Design actions that can be sustained or have ongoing impact rather than initiatives that “go nowhere.” This includes carefully labs with attention to school calendars and temporal constraints, and advocating for extended engagement to enable durable cultural and democratic change.

9.2.4 Reflect Phase

In the CCLAB, we observed a certain resistance among students toward specific forms of reflective practice. This resistance was linked both to their preference for action-oriented, hands-on activities and to the perceived lack of relevance of reflection. As educators, researchers, and practitioners, this observation calls for critical self-reflection on our own positioning: it may point to a broader social trend that privileges doing, making, and producing over pausing and questioning (Han, 2023). We must decide whether to reproduce this tendency or to challenge it.

Alongside this broader consideration, some practical recommendations also emerge. These relate to rethinking how deliberative and reflective practices can be framed so that they resonate more closely with students’ ways of constructing knowledge.

Key considerations and recommendations include:

- **Embed continuous reflection throughout the process:** Reflection should not be treated as a discrete or isolated activity, but rather integrated into the ongoing flow of participation, allowing students to connect insights to action in real time.
- **Experiment with alternative strategies:** Explore different resources and modalities that enable students to engage in reflection beyond traditional written or oral forms.
- **Leverage challenges as reflective opportunities:** Moments of difficulty, disagreement, tensions or resistance to reflection should not only be seen as obstacles but also as triggers for critical reflection on the ongoing process and how it mirrors social tensions and tendencies.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Evaluation Report for PAR Cycle 2

General Information Form

General information	
Partner	

Institution (where the PAR cycle is being implemented)	
Name of the institution	
Describe your relationship with the institution (e.g., links with other initiatives, engagement with the project, etc.)	
Is the PAR cycle related to other cultural, political, or social events? (please specify)	
Geographical location (city, state/province, country)	
Type of institution (e.g., formal education, non-formal education –if non-formal, please specify type such as after-school club, music academy, etc.)	
Participant Recruitment and Involvement	
How were participants recruited?	
Demographic characteristics of participants (gender, age, background, etc.)	
Involvement of other stakeholders. Are any other stakeholders involved in the PAR cycle? (Please specify)	

Schedule	
Number of sessions	
Dates	

Time	
Topic	
What is the topic of the cycle? How was it defined?	

Researchers' Diaries Form

Researchers' Diaries
<p>Before filling out the form, please consider the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>A separate form must be completed for each session conducted.</u> • The form should be filled out after each session (we recommend NOT completing them all at the end of the PAR cycle). • The team should complete one form collectively (NOT one form per researcher).

General Data	
Date and time	
Place	
Number of participants and role	

Methods (Add to the Document as Many Tables as Methods Used During the Session)	
Name	
<p>General Learning Goal. Specify which CCLab competences the method addresses. You may choose more than one if applicable</p>	<p>Knowledge and critical understanding of the world competence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness to other beliefs, worldviews and practices competences. • Imaginative and inventive competences. • Transformative Agency competences. • Critical Self- Reflection competences. • Democratic disposition competences. • Creative competences. • Research related competences.
<p>Specific Learning Goals. Indicate specific learning goals of the method, if applicable.</p>	
<p>Steps. Provide a short step-by-step description of the method.</p>	
<p>Participation. On a scale of 0 to 5 (0 being the lowest and 5 the highest), how effectively did the method support participation through various means (e.g., oral</p>	

contributions, written responses, drawings, etc.)?	
Objective Achievement. On a scale of 0 to 5 (0 being the lowest and 5 the highest), how successfully did the method achieve its intended goal?	

Structure of the Session
Briefly summarise the session's structure (e.g., 1. introduction, 2. icebreaker, 3. mind-map, 4. discussion).

Significant Moments & Critical Incidents	
<p>The idea of significant moment is based on the notion of Critical Incident. A Critical Incident (CI), according to Flanagan (1954), is defined as an event or situation that significantly impacts the outcomes of a process or activity. It is characterised by being observable (the incident is a specific, observable behaviour or event) and significant (it substantially affects the process of the PAR cycle) (Kreps, 2018). See more on Critical Incident Technique in: Flanagan, J. C. (1954). The critical incident technique. <i>Psychological Bulletin</i>, 5, 327–358. https://doi.org/10.1037/h0061470</p> <p>Kreps, G. L. (2018). Critical Incident Technique. In A. A. Raney & J. Bryant (Eds.), <i>The International Encyclopedia of Communication Research Methods</i>. Wiley. https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118901731.iecrm0052</p> <p>Please consider the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide detailed descriptions of the Critical Incidents to ensure they can be thoroughly understood and analysed. - Complete this section ONLY if a significant moment or Critical Incident occurs in any of the aspects mentioned in the table. - When selecting significant moments please consider both moments where participants demonstrated changes in their attitudes/learning as well as moments where participants demonstrated challenges, difficulties and tensions. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' knowledge and critical understanding of the world.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated evidence of <u>learning, insights, tensions, or difficulties</u> in their understanding of a specific phenomenon? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying everyday conflicts and contradictions. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the implications and interrelations of phenomena and their historical dimensions. • Critically understanding power relations and sources of inequalities related to the defined phenomena. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants openness to other beliefs, worldviews and practices competences.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated learning, <u>insights</u>, <u>tensions</u>, or <u>difficulties</u> regarding their openness to other beliefs, worldviews, and practices? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying biases in worldviews. • Reflecting on multiple perspectives. • Inhabiting and appreciating different viewpoints. • Commitment (or lack of) to listening to marginalised voices. • Openness and flexibility (or lack of) to revise one's perspectives and opinions. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' Imaginative and inventive competences.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated <u>learning</u>, <u>insights</u>, <u>tensions</u>, or <u>difficulties</u> regarding their skills for imagining alternatives? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploring the political and creative potential of the 	

<p>"What If?" question to challenge existing paradigms and imagine alternative scenarios.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering imagination of possible worlds and futures. • Challenging assumptions and accepted norms. • Thinking about unestablished possibilities. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' transformative agency competences.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated <u>learning, insights, tensions, or difficulties</u> related to transforming ideas into actions? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying pathways to possible actions. • Collectively defining clear and shared goals for transformation. • Developing action plans to achieve these goals. • Selecting appropriate tools for goal achievement. • Initiating practical actions for change. • Identify, seek, foster, and maintain collaboration with other stakeholders. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' critical self-reflection competences.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated <u>learning, insights, tensions, or difficulties</u> regarding critical self-reflection? Examples include:</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine one's own viewpoints, thoughts and biases • Reflect on and evaluate one's learning process, project development, and outcomes. • Reflect on one's role and agency as an active civic participant. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' democratic disposition.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated <u>learning, insights, tensions, or difficulties</u> related to democratic practices and values? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflecting on the complexities and nuances of democratic attitudes. • Becoming more aware of the presence or absence of democratic practices and values in their own contexts. • Promoting democratic practices and values within their communities. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' creative competences.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated <u>learning, insights, tensions, or difficulties</u> related to creative competences? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use creative and artistic resources to investigate and expose issues. • Use creative and artistic resources to make 	

<p>participation and deliberative processes more accessible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use creative and artistic resources to support social engagement. 	
<p>Significant moments related to participants' research competences.</p> <p>Did you observe any significant moments where participants demonstrated <u>learning, insights, tensions, or difficulties</u> related to research competences? Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability (or lack of) to use research as a tool for transformation. • Capacity (or lack of) to articulate, research questions that are relevant. • Understanding (or lack of) of various research approaches. 	
<p>Conflicts and tensions.</p> <p>Were there any tensions or conflicts during the session that impacted the PAR cycle process?</p>	
<p>Others</p>	

<p>Notes for Improvements and Considerations for the Next Session</p>
Empty space for notes

